

PROCEEDINGS OF THE 1ST ReLDI CONFERENCE ON LANGUAGE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

THE PALACE OF SCIENCE
BELGRADE
25-26 September 2025

ISBN-978-86-907922-0-7

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

Programme chair

Tanja Samardžić, ReLDI member, IDSIA USI-SUPSI

Local organiser

Mirjana Starović, ReLDI member, Lexicom Belgrade

Local advisory members

Vlado Delić, University of Novi Sad

Sabina Halupka Rešetar, University of Novi Sad

Boško Nikolić, University of Belgrade

Ranka Stanković, University of Belgrade

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Boban Arsenijević, University of Graz

Duygu Ataman, Middle East Technical University, Ankara

Vuk Batanović, University of Belgrade, ReLDI member

Christian Bentz, University of Passau

Silvia Bernardini, University of Bologna

Ksenija Bogetić Pejović, Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

Milica Denić, University of Geneva

Ljiljana Dolamić, Cyber-Defence Campus, armasuisse

Tomaž Erjavec, Jožef Stefan Institute

Adriano Ferraresi, University of Bologna

Darja Fišer, University of Ljubljana and CLARIN ERIC

Goran Glavaš, University of Würzburg

Gordana Hržica, University of Zagreb

Tihana Kraš, University of Rijeka

Nikola Ljubešić, Jožef Stefan Institute, ReLDI member

Aleksandra Miletić, University Paris Nanterre

Filip Miletić, University of Stuttgart

Maja Miličević Petrović, University of Bologna, ReLDI member

Mirjana Mirić, Serbian Academy Of Sciences and Arts

Sandra Mitrović, IDSIA Lugano

Giuseppe Samo, University of Geneva and Idiap

Yves Scherrer, University of Oslo

Milan Sečujski, University of Novi Sad

Nikola Simić, University of Novi Sad

Marko Simonović, University of Graz

Irena Srdanović, University of Pula

Miloš Stanojević, University College London

Siniša Suzić, University of Novi Sad

Kristina Štrkalj Despot, Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics

Slavko Žitnik, University of Ljubljana

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Thematic commentaries

- How language technology transforms language services – A translator’s perspective* 4
Aleksandar Janković
- How language technology transforms language services – A translation education perspective* 7
Maja Miličević Petrović

Main scientific programme

- Croatian and Serbian speech-to-text conversion between literal and standard* 10
Tanja Samardžić, Peter Rupnik, Nikola Ljubešić, Mirjana Starović
- Explainable linguistic variety classification: The case of Bosnian-Croatian-Montenegrin-Serbian* 17
Aleksandra Miletić, Timothee Mickus, Yves Scherrer
- Acoustic trends across sentiment-labelled speech in the Croatian parliament* 26
Ivan Porupski, Nikola Ljubešić
- Genderedness dictates the choice of agreement with numeral phrases in Serbian* 38
Stefan Milosavljević, Jelena Stojković
- Torlak theme vowels in the verbal domain: A corpus-based study* 48
Stefan Milosavljević, Marko Simonović, Anđela Babić, Mirjana Mirić, Jelena Stojković

Programme Synergies

- Towards benchmarking text classification for South Slavic languages in the era of large language models* 59
Taja Kuzman Pungerešek, Peter Rupnik, Ivan Porupski, Nikola Ljubešić
- Embedding text in emotion and evocation vector spaces* 63
Mihailo Škorić, Ranka Stanković
- From names to places: Serbian entity linking through the lens of GIS* 68
Ranka Stanković, Saša Petalinkar, Milica Ikonić Nešić
- From bilingual learners’ dictionary to dynamic platform for learners: Towards AI-augmented Japanese-Croatian (WaKu) and Japanese-Serbian (WaSe) language learning resource* 72
Irena Srdanović
- Taming Croatian News with TakeLab Retriever* 75
Ana Barić, Laura Majer, Marko Čuljak
- COMtext.SR – A community-supported project to develop open language resources for Serbian* 79
Vuk Batanović, Lenka Bajčetić, Aleksandra Todorović, Tanja Samardžić

HOW LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGY TRANSFORMS LANGUAGE SERVICES — A TRANSLATOR’S PERSPECTIVE

Aleksandar JANKOVIĆ,¹

¹Director, Create Translation Agency, Belgrade

COMMENTARY

Keywords: Language technology; Translation profession, Machine translation; Post-editing; Future-proofing

This paper explores how language technology has transformed translation services over the past two decades, as seen from the perspective of a practicing translator. The narrative begins with early reliance on paper dictionaries and typewriters, moving through the introduction of CAT tools such as Trados, the rise of machine translation, and most recently, the integration of AI. These technological shifts have altered not only workflows but also pricing models, client expectations, and the very nature of the translator’s effort, with post-editing emerging as a central task. While automation has increased pace and consistency, it has also driven down rates and reshaped the market, particularly in smaller contexts such as Serbia. The boundary between human and machine contributions continues to blur, with AI beginning to revise its own output and new tools such as AI-powered wearables promising further disruption. Despite these changes, client relationships still rest on trust, reliability, and availability, though even here technology is ever-present. Looking ahead, the challenge is not only continual learning but also broader personal growth: developing empathy, ethics, and cultural mediation to reinforce the human dimension of language work.

1 RADICAL CHANGES WITHIN A SINGLE CAREER SPAN

The journey from submitting essays on paper as a student to now working with AI-driven translation tools shows just how radically technology has been changing language services within a single career span.

Rather than giving an overview of how language technology has developed, I want to offer an insider’s perspective as an end user: how two decades of innovation have reshaped this work, some of the current trends, and how we might think about the future. As a disclaimer, my reflections are drawn from personal experience and should be regarded as indicative rather than definitive.

Today’s advances of AI in language services sometimes feel like an end of an era, or coming full circle, considering where the technology in the language services started. This framing is of course subjective as this point in time is experienced in a different way by students fin-

ishing their studies and looking at their future options in the job market. This is a phase in which language professionals will need to figure out their role in the environment shaped by technology.

2 A COUPLE OF DICTIONARIES AND THE ELECTRIC TYPEWRITER

About twenty plus years ago, a translation task meant a couple of dictionaries open at once, hours of typing with hardly any shortcuts. The work relied on paper dictionaries and glossaries I had compiled myself. Deadlines were measured in days rather than hours, there was more room for drafting, though far less support in terms of tools. For my generation, the first contact with technology was the electric typewriter. Then came the word processor and the internet, followed by CAT tools and Google Translate and other machine translation systems.

3 FROM CAT TO ONLINE PLATFORMS

My first encounter with CAT¹ technology came in the form of Trados. This upskilling was a challenge I embraced without resistance. I welcomed with optimism those early experiments, as it was clear that translation was beginning to move in a new direction, one that would gradually reshape the profession. Some other challenges with upskilling, brought on a bit later with Covid and distance interpreting, were not met with the same amount of enthusiasm. The platforms proved to be additional stressors due to noise and technical difficulties beyond the control of the interpreter who was not present at the event, in the booth.

These days, the transformation is profound. We hardly ever see paper originals, most projects arrive and leave online, as screens are populated with suggestions from machine translation and AI assistants. There is a difference in the role of the translator, types of tasks we perform, client expectations in terms of speed, accuracy, and pricing model. The original optimism seems to be getting a bit more cautious.

¹CAT stands for Computer-Assisted Translation.

4 INCREASED OUTPUT, LOWER PRICE

Pace and consistency improved by automation but the impact on pricing was more complex. On the one hand, we see a pricing model where fees were tied to match categories of translation units (the higher the match percentage, the lower the fee), which drove the price of some tasks down. On the other, automation allows us to at least maintain or sometimes increase income by higher output within the same amount of time. This helps offset the lack of price adjustments in the Serbian market, where rates have hardly moved in two decades.

5 BOTH DEMAND AND SUPPLY RESHAPED

The integration of CAT tools with machine translation, and more recently with AI, has been reshaping both demand and supply. On the demand side, the services that AI can now handle, such as translation of routine business correspondence or general texts are increasingly automated. What arrives instead are very long and complex contracts or reports, often requiring time-consuming Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and formatting. These assignments may come with unrealistic deadlines and can only be managed by a Language Service Provider (LSP) or an informal team, leaving individual freelancers at a disadvantage. On the supply side, the pressure is evident. Some people are reconsidering their career path, or at least expecting less from translation as primary livelihood, because of the changing mix of technology, politics and economics. In smaller markets, enrolment levels in translation studies may even contribute to a sense of market saturation. Increasingly, the trade appears to be shifting into a side activity, with limited freelance opportunities remaining.

This evolution has also changed the kind of effort the work requires. One of the new roles that has emerged is machine translation post-editing. Where I once built every sentence from scratch, I now spend much of my time correcting machine output with my attention spread across dozens of small decisions rather than the flow of writing. It feels less like the creative act of producing language and more like the evaluative task of processing it.

6 THE MOVING LINE OF THE TASKS DIVISION BETWEEN HUMAN AND MACHINE

There has also been a shift in how we divide the tasks between human and machine. At first it seemed the machine was not encroaching on the human segment as we held our space with cultural mediation, nuance beyond word for word equivalence or some other specialized tasks like court certified translation and interpreting.

But the line keeps moving. Recently, I have seen AI taking on post-editing of its own translation. In one recent project, AI's context awareness and my prompting gave me surprisingly solid edits of its translation. The "temperature setting" (a cleverly named slider in the Trados-ChatGPT integration settings meant to adjust contextual departure from literal translation) seemed ineffective. However, when prompted, ChatGPT edited the translation it had just produced. The results were actually usable. I haven't found a fully automated solution yet, but I am convinced it is coming.

7 CLIENT RELATIONSHIPS CHANGE LESS

Today, translation is only one part of what I do, alongside formatting, OCR, quality assurance, post-editing, and at times advising clients. Unlike workflows and pricing, client relationships have remained relatively untouched by technology in any fundamental way. What has always mattered most is reliability built through quality, consistency, and responsiveness. Technology may have streamlined communication but it has only touched the fundamentals of good business practice.

In the context of client relationships, we position ourselves relative to technology as a way of compensating for lost income. One strategy is availability as competitive advantage. It puts you on speed dial for clients and fosters loyalty and repeat business as clients value the last minute saves.

This, of course, comes with trade-offs. It may leave you exposed to more idle time if you avoid committing to larger, time-consuming projects. Clients tend to see these types of projects as a value in itself and may use it as leverage to push prices down.

The cost and reliability of technology also play a role with prices being prohibitive in some cases. To protect both my clients and my reputation from unexpected glitches of new versions of software or hardware, I rely on a main "mission critical" setup. Any new software or hardware is tested first on a backup system before it is deployed. But this approach effectively doubles the investment in the tools we use.

8 SIGHT TRANSLATION WITH THE TECHNOLOGY IN THE ROOM

Today technology in language services is pretty much universally available. One exception are the tasks requiring physical presence of court-certified interpreter. Yet even here, the line is blurring. Recently, as I was providing a sight translation of a contract, the client pulled out his phone, opened Google Translate, and pointed the camera at the text. He read the translation on the screen while listening to me. Legally, my presence was

still required for the signing. But the technology was already in the room, optional for now.

This month has brought major announcements of AI powered wearables (earphones, glasses) equipped with simultaneous interpreting functionality. This is clearly the direction of future development. It may still seem far off, but the pace of progress may catch us by surprise again.

9 LOOKING AHEAD

As the role of translator continues to change, our next challenge is to look ahead to the future of the profession, and how we can be ready for it.

Some fifteen years ago, when I set out to build my own business, I searched for a name that would capture what I believed mattered. Even then, I had the sense that our profession would require us to reinvent our roles, to create work rather than simply apply for positions. That idea led me to name the agency Create.

The sound of the future for translator in the age of technology seems to me like a mix of cacophony and symphony of both the swan song and the dawn chorus. From the perspective of my generation, it feels easier to accept today's flux, knowing we are closer to the end than the beginning of our professional path. Having seen such vast changes within the span of a single career, I remain curious about what lies ahead.

When thinking about future-proofing our skillset, continual learning is only a part of the picture. Personal growth, in whatever form is most relevant to each professional, remains the foundation for navigating the future with resilience, adaptability and creativity. As technology transforms language services, we should reflect that transformation through our own growth in empathy, ethics, and cultural mediation. In this way, we amplify the human touch which remains our edge as we embrace the evolving technology.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

HOW LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGY TRANSFORMS LANGUAGE SERVICES – A TRANSLATION EDUCATION PERSPECTIVE

Maja MILIČEVIĆ PETROVIĆ

University of Bologna

COMMENTARY

Keywords: language technology, language industry, translator training, new professional profiles, new vs. old skills

1 INTRODUCTION

A recent advertisement by a private university in Italy reads “Linguistic mediation is not dead, it is just speaking new languages”. The slogan is telling, and despite being launched in a specific marketing context, it reflects more general truths and views also expressed in academic and industry analyses: linguistic mediation might be perceived as deceased, but is actually not at all so if we look beyond its traditional form.

This commentary discusses the evolving nature of professional linguistic mediation in the light of rapid technological and social changes. After an overview of the situation in the job market, attention is moved towards how higher education institutions attempt to address the changes through their study programmes.

2 PROFESSIONAL TRANSLATION OF TODAY

The landscape of language professions has changed dramatically in recent decades, with (written) translation at the forefront. Translation has been a highly technologized activity at least since the 1990s: traditional human efforts first gave way to CAT – Computer-Assisted Translation implemented through terminological databases and translation memories, increasingly integrating (N)MT – (Neural) Machine Translation, which gradually transformed into MTPE – Machine Translation Post-Editing, where translators no longer translate, but correct or otherwise improve translations produced by machines. The most recent shifts linked to the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the form of Large Language Models (LLMs) are thus just the latest of a long line of earthquakes that shook the profession.

Throughout these developments, the relationship between translation and technology swung back and forth between supportive and disruptive (Bernardini & Gaspari, 2025): CAT tools, for instance, never constituted competitors, and were meant to help human translators achieve consistency and save time with repetitive texts; it is mostly since the advent of NMT in 2016 that true disruption started being perceived, through fear of job loss due to machines approaching human parity. Today’s sit-

uation is that parity is not yet achieved in most tasks, but progress in that direction is constantly being made. Translation remains fully human-dominated only in specific, mostly creative contexts such as literary translation, with a paradigm shift towards MTPE/AI use broadly implemented in most other domains, even raising the question of whether human translators should still be called that (Ferraresi, 2025).¹

To balance things out with some benefits for the profession, the amount of text to be translated keeps growing (there is a “content explosion”)², and new tasks involved in managing the volume of data keep emerging – tasks translators are well-equipped to handle (Ferraresi, 2025; Massey et al., 2023), both downstream (e.g. content creation) and upstream (e.g. terminology management or workflow automation). The changes in the job market are thus not entirely bad, as language industry continues to expand in size and scope. But as per the slogan cited above, translators need to diversify their portfolios, increasingly engaging either with knowledge of additional domains (e.g. tourism), or with technologically oriented aspects of text processing.

In a broader perspective, the situation is quite similar to what happens in other language-related professions, which are also evolving. Language teaching increasingly depends on technological competence, requiring teachers to integrate AI-based tools and language learning apps into their pedagogical practices. At the same time, linguistics – traditionally an academic discipline *par excellence* – is moving toward a more vocational orientation: a growing number of linguistics graduates go on to work in data science, or AI-driven content management. The emerging career paths, although often distant from traditional occupations, demonstrate the expanding relevance of language expertise in technology-intensive environments. Naturally, the diversification also requires adaptive expertise.

¹Interpreting – language mediation in the spoken modality – remains somewhat more protected (albeit not immune), in virtue of its real-time nature and a more central position of the human interpreter.

²See e.g. <https://multilingual.com/magazine/january-2025/how-language-industry-jobs-are-shifting-left/> (accessed 20/11/2025)

3 TRANSLATOR TRAINING FOR THE FUTURE

Rapid changes in the job market raise numerous questions for language-related higher education. With institutional mechanisms typically being much slower than market changes, a mismatch persists between university curricula and industry demands: while the industry calls for professionals also skilled in data handling, automation, and often programming, many academic programmes remain anchored in more traditional approaches. This divergence contributes to declining enrolments in language and linguistics courses, partly driven by perceptions of limited career prospects.

To remain relevant, universities must reconfigure both content and pedagogy. When it comes to translation in particular, the academic community has been extraordinarily active in monitoring the profession and suggesting training updates,³ as witnessed by numerous dedicated publications, with the journal *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer* as a constant, and with multiple thematic issues focused on the changes brought about by the development of technology (Bernardini & Gaspari, 2025; Massey et al., 2023; Mattioda et al., 2023). Institutions, within their administration-bound limits, try to keep up the pace, primarily by reforming the degree programmes and curricula in the direction of enhancing the technological component. The side of the coin that remains less addressed is whether the elements taken for granted in linguistic mediation/translation degree courses, such as the teaching of languages and linguistics, are in need of reform too.

3.1 Bringing in new skills

There is probably no translation degree programme in the world that is not aware of technology taking over much of the work they have been training students for. The main approach taken in trying to adapt courses to these needs is integrating digital competences, including AI literacy, into linguistic education. Multiple bodies and projects have proposed updated competence frameworks along these lines. The Erasmus+ project UPSKILLS – *UPgrading the SKills of Linguistics and Language Students*,⁴ for instance, has identified new professional profiles emerging from the intersection of languages/linguistics and technology; using a variety of methods within the project, and engaging in follow-up activities since its conclusion, the team documented new professional roles involving data curation and language technology design, also proposing a tar-

³Jointly with professional organisations and public institutions; see <https://knowledge-centre-translation-interpretation.ec.europa.eu/en>, among others.

⁴See <https://upskillsproject.eu/>, <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/projects/search/details/2020-1-MT01-KA203-074246>

get overarching profile for language/linguistics graduates labelled *language data and project specialist*.⁵

The Department of Interpreting and Translation of the University of Bologna, one of the UPSKILLS project partners, can be taken as an example of how new skills and competences are implemented in new degree courses or new curricula. In addition to including technology-centred courses and a three-course minor called Language, Technology, Research to its BA programme (which has been rebranded from *Intercultural Linguistic Mediation* to *Languages and Technologies for the Intercultural Communication*), the department implemented a curriculum in *Translation and Technology* within its MA degree course in *Specialized Translation*.⁶ With compulsory courses dedicated to Terminology, Corpus linguistics, Natural language processing, and Language data analysis, the curriculum places a lot of emphasis on developing research-related skills jointly with technical skills. This is especially the case within the 1st year course Profession-based research, where 40 hours of lectures are connected to a 250-hour internship during which the students engage in an industry research project jointly supervised by an academic and an industry supervisor. Internships have so far taken students to language service providers (working on terminology extraction, quality management, or evaluation of text-to-speech systems), to research infrastructures such as CLARIN (for work on ontologies), and even to public health institutions (working on the use of LLMs in producing standardized medical reports).

3.2 Old skills with a twist

While the above examples from the University of Bologna show how academic programmes can evolve toward a more flexible, interdisciplinary model that equips graduates for the changing realities of the language professions, true interdisciplinarity is rarely achieved by simply adding new skills on top of the old ones. Innovation in translator training must go beyond adding technical modules; it also requires a rethinking of how linguistic knowledge is taught and applied.

Empirical evidence from the UPSKILLS project points not only toward the need to add new skills, but also toward an inclination in language- and linguistics graduates to remain enclosed in “linguistic boxes”, i.e. in a specific way of analyzing language that they have mastered during their studies and that they find difficult to

⁵See <https://upskilling.dipintra.it/>. See also the eTransFair project, <https://transvienna.univie.ac.at/en/research/previous-research-projects/etransfair/>, and the LT-Lider project, <https://lt-lider.eu/>.

⁶<https://corsi.unibo.it/laurea/LingueTecnologieComunicazioneInter-culturale>, <https://corsi.unibo.it/2cycle/SpecializedTranslation/course-structure-diagram/piano/2025/6826/C09/000/2025>

change when addressing industry tasks; such an inclination is highly likely to result from the way they were taught about language, which typically involved a heavy focus on a single theory, or another type of approach seen as exclusively correct (Miličević Petrović, 2025). In other words, the knowledge about language that future language professionals possess is useful and generally appreciated, but it could benefit from more flexibility. Given that most new professions and most new trends in the translation profession are technology-oriented, it would be useful for future translators to learn more about how language is represented by computers and about the seemingly rule-less operation of NMT systems and LLMs. This new knowledge would be there to complement the more traditional rule-based approach typical of linguistics courses, rather than replacing it.

3.3 Open questions

Not much certainty is present when it comes to the specifics of the future of language professions. It is, however, rather evident that both technology and human skills are here to stay, complementing and balancing each other out, with creativity and quality control as predominantly human skills and tasks.

Keeping in mind the need to bring languages and technology together in translator education, one of the questions that remain is who the language professionals of the future are. Students who enrol in language-related courses traditionally do so for love of languages, or more specifically because they enjoy translating. If the very activity is taken out of the equation, can we expect the typical student profile to change? If neighbouring areas of expertise that translators turn to (e.g. inclusivity, easy language) are also becoming increasingly automated, will future students working on languages mostly be those interested in computer science? Or will the world need to come to terms with in-depth technological knowledge as a core requirement for most professions, allowing other specific interests to prevail?

Yet another, somewhat related question concerns knowledge about language outside language-related degree courses. With LLMs so pervasively present, should everyone working with/on language(s) have at least an elementary education in linguistics and/or translation? Implementing tailor-made courses covering the basics of linguistic analysis, with a possible focus on aspects particularly relevant in a given context (such as phonetics for text-to-speech specialization), would greatly benefit collaboration between fields.

Finally, technology does not develop at the same pace in all contexts, but the language job market is more global than ever, posing similar requirements to professionals in objectively different settings. How should dif-

ferent countries cope? And could countries like Serbia be better positioned with their mostly not-translation-specific degree courses compared to countries that have invested a lot of effort into specialization?

4 CONCLUSION

By bringing together theoretical and applied knowledge, and by cultivating both linguistic insight and technological fluency, the next generation of translators (and other language professionals) can remain essential in an increasingly automated world. But for this to be possible, universities should embrace their role not as passive observers of industry trends but as co-creators of professional futures, making sure to select relevant skills to add to the curricula, be they technology-related or not.

REFERENCES

- Bernardini, S., & Gaspari, F. (2025). The evolution of translation (studies) in the technocene. *Translation and Translanguaging in Multilingual Contexts*, 11(3), 237–251. Retrieved November 18, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1075/ttmc.00167.ber>
- Ferraresi, A. (2025). Formare esperte e esperti in traduzione: Sfide di oggi, scenari di domani. In *Translating Europe Workshop*. Retrieved November 20, 2025, from https://www.federlingue.it/export/sites/unione/federlingue/TEW_Milano_Ferraresi.pdf
- Massey, G., Piotrowska, M., & Marczak, M. (2023). Meeting evolution with innovation: an introduction to (re-)profiling T&I education. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer*, 17(3), 325–331. Retrieved November 21, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1080/1750399X.2023.2237321>
- Mattioda, M. M., Molino, A., & Cinato, L. (2023). L'intelligenza artificiale per la traduzione: orizzonti, pratiche e percorsi formativi. *mediAzioni*, 39, A1–A16. Retrieved November 21, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.1974-4382/18784>
- Miličević Petrović, M. (2025). (Applied) linguistics in the era of artificial intelligence: challenges and opportunities for teaching. In M. Dinić Marinković, N. Panić Cerovski, & B. Kovačević (Eds.), *Applied linguistics today 8 – Modern approaches to old and new challenges* (pp. 33–67). University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philology. Retrieved January 27, 2026, from https://doi.org/10.18485/dpls_pld.2025.8.ch2

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

CROATIAN AND SERBIAN SPEECH-TO-TEXT CONVERSION BETWEEN LITERAL AND STANDARD

Tanja SAMARDŽIĆ,¹ Nikola LJUBEŠIĆ,^{2, 3, 4} Mirjana STAROVIĆ,⁵ Peter RUPNIK²

¹Dalle Molle Institute for Artificial Intelligence USI-SUPSI, Switzerland

²Dept. of Knowledge Technologies, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Institute of Contemporary History, Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁴Faculty of Computer and Information Science, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁵Lexicom, Belgrade, Serbia

While many new speech-to-text models have been proposed in recent years, evaluating their performance is a challenging task, particularly for less resourced languages. In this paper, we analyse model performance against a multi-reference gold standard dataset in Croatian and Serbian focusing on the differences between a more standard and a more literal version of the multi-reference. We analyse the performance of 7 public, freely available models with varied training and fine-tuning settings. Our results show that, in general, models obtain better scores when evaluated against literal transcripts, but also that this trend is weaker in the best performing models suggesting that some gains in the performance might come from standardising the output.

Keywords: speech-to-text, automatic speech recognition, multi-reference evaluation, benchmark, Croatian, Serbian

1 INTRODUCTION

After several decades of research, the speech processing technology has finally become available for practical use in languages other than English. Croatian and Serbian are among those languages that have seen significant development in recent years. In addition to being supported in commercial applications, these languages are increasingly represented in academic research through the development of data sets containing audio-to-text alignment, as well as through training and fine-tuning contemporary model architectures.

These developments resulted in a series of solutions that are currently available for these languages and created the need for an objective and transparent comparison of these solutions. While commercial solutions are advertised to perform at certain Word Error Rates (WER), independent academic evaluations are largely missing. Also, the scores achieved by academic (non-commercial) solutions are rarely published.

This problem is recently addressed by the project *Mak na konac* (MNK) (Samardžić et al., 2024), which offers a data set for multi-reference evaluation. The need for multi-reference evaluation is especially pronounced when evaluating solutions based on pre-trained models because the user has no control over the selection of pre-training data. In other words, modern models cannot be compared on the same training and test data, which used to be the comparison standard before pre-trained models were introduced. Multi-reference evaluation is a way of neutralising the effects of training data

by giving each model a chance to match one of the multiple references, the one that turns out the closest to its (unknown) training data.

One of the several options covered in the MNK multi-reference is a binary distinction between *literal* and *standard* gold transcription. The literal version contains elements of speech such as short repetitions, fillers, mistakes, non-standard and dialect features. The standard version is closer to originally written text, where such speech elements are removed. Given the great variability in how present-day models are trained, it is hard to tell whether their output can be expected to be closer to speech or to written language.

The goal of our study is to determine which one of the MNK multi-reference options, literal or standard, results in better WER scores when evaluating a series of open-access speech-to-text models. We analyse the scores of 7 models previously evaluated in the MNK project on four data sources (two Croatian and two Serbian). Our findings are intended to determine whether modern speech-to-text models tend to output more literal transcripts (including elements of spoken language) or standardised text characteristic of writing.

2 RELATED WORK

The performance of speech-to-text models on Croatian and Serbian data is relatively rarely reported. We are aware of only one report of a Kaldi (Povey et al., 2011) recipe for Serbian (Popović et al., 2015), which shows a big performance drop on the out-of-domain

Table 1: The first five rows of an evaluation report. Each row contains multiple WER scores for one audio segment. The full evaluation report analysed in our study contains around 11'000 of such rows. It is available for reproducibility together with the analysis code in our shared folder referenced in the text.

Segment ID	WhisperV	WhisperS	WhisperSJV	Transducer	CTC	W2V2XLSR	W2V2Slavic
170918_13_14	[0.286, 0.143, 0.125, 0.000]	[0.429, 0.286, 0.500, 0.375]	[0.429, 0.286, 0.250, 0.125]	[0.571, 0.429, 0.375, 0.250]	[0.571, 0.429, 0.375, 0.250]	[1.000, 0.857, 0.750, 0.625]	[0.857, 0.857, 0.714, 0.500]
170918_14_15	[0.429, 0.400]	[0.286, 0.400]	[0.714, 0.300]	[0.857, 0.300]	[0.857, 0.300]	[0.857, 0.300]	[0.857, 0.300]
170918_15_16	[0.111, 0.091]	[0.000, 0.182]	[0.556, 0.455]	[0.667, 0.364]	[0.556, 0.455]	[0.556, 0.364]	[0.556, 0.455]
170918_16_17	[0.100, 0.100]	[0.100, 0.100]	[0.100, 0.100]	[0.300, 0.300]	[0.400, 0.400]	[0.100, 0.100]	[0.300, 0.300]
170918_17_18	[0.222, 0.455, 0.111, 0.364, 0.100, 0.333, 0.000, 0.250]	[0.111, 0.364, 0.000, 0.273, 0.200, 0.417, 0.100, 0.333]	[0.222, 0.455, 0.111, 0.364, 0.100, 0.333, 0.000, 0.250]	[0.556, 0.455, 0.444, 0.364, 0.400, 0.333, 0.300, 0.250]	[0.667, 0.545, 0.556, 0.455, 0.500, 0.417, 0.400, 0.333]	[0.444, 0.636, 0.333, 0.545, 0.300, 0.500, 0.200, 0.417]	[0.444, 0.545, 0.333, 0.455, 0.300, 0.417, 0.200, 0.333]

test set. Several models, including some similar to those included in this study, are previously evaluated on Croatian data (Ljubešić et al., 2022). The performance of large and medium Whisper models (Radford et al., 2022) fine-tuned on Serbian data is reported on the Hugging Face repository (Sagić, 2023). The most comprehensive evaluation is performed as part of the *Mak na konac* project (Samardžić et al., 2024), showing considerable differences compared to the previously reported scores, despite the flexible evaluation that allows each model to obtain its best possible score. The *Mak na konac* data can be considered out-of-domain evaluation, while the previously reported scores were obtained on similar data on which the models were fine-tuned, which might explain the difference.

Multi-reference evaluation is rarely reported even outside of the Croatian and Serbian data. It is typically performed on Arabic because no wide standard is available for this language (Ali et al., 2015). The differences between the evaluation on the standard vs. non-standard reference is discussed in the case of Swiss German (Nigmatulina et al., 2020) showing that the word-level performance is better on standardised data, but non-standard data allow better character-level performance. A combination of non-standard and standard reference is used for obtaining flexible scores that dis-

regard the errors due to the noise in the non-standard data. Multi-reference data sets have been published for Slovenian (Žgank et al., 2014; Verdonik et al., 2024), but without a systematic evaluation of models.

3 DATA AND METHODS

The audio part of the MNK test data is available online on Hugging Face.¹ The multi-reference transcript is not publicly available, to prevent model contamination, but researchers can obtain a rich evaluation report on a submitted output of a model. For the reproducibility of our study, we make available the parts of the reports that we analysed together with the code used for the analysis.²

Our analysis is performed on the evaluation reports for seven models listed in Table 2 and for four data parts described in Table 3. The first five lines of one of the analysed evaluation reports is shown in Table 1. For each audio segment (ID in the first column) and each tested model, we obtain an array of WER scores (here rounded up to three decimal places). The first half of each array contains the scores on the standardised versions of the multi-reference, while the second half of each array contains the scores obtained on the lit-

¹https://huggingface.co/datasets/classla/mak_na_konac/viewer/default/SR1?row=4

²<https://drive.switch.ch/index.php/s/kUDbQbkHksIrES6>

Table 2: Summary of key features of the models tested in the MNK project. The overall WER scores shown in this table represent the weighted average over the best scores for all segments in a given data part. The best averages are in bold.

Model	Architecture	Training	Size	Best performance (WER)			
				HR1	HR2	SR1	SR2
WhisperV	Transformers	Pre-trained on fully aligned multilingual data	Large	16.18	9.61	14.62	11.39
WhisperS	Transformers	WhisperV fine-tuned on Serbian	Large	27.38	20.59	16.89	15.84
WhisperSJV	Transformers	WhisperV fine-tuned on a larger Serbian data set	Large	27.73	19.58	15.51	14.28
Transducer	RNN	Trained from scratch on Croatian	Small	24.97	8.90	20.08	19.80
CTC	RNN	Trained from scratch on Croatian	Small	27.02	8.52	20.88	20.25
W2V2XLSR	Transformers	Pre-trained on partially aligned multilingual data, fine-tuned on Croatian	Large	37.55	13.58	26.08	27.26
W2V2Slavic	Transformers	Pre-trained on partially aligned Slavic data, fine-tuned on Croatian	Large	37.88	12.65	23.83	25.14

Table 3: Summary of key features of the test data.

Data part	Source	Language	Region	Size
HR1	Radio Student	Croatian	Zagreb	5h
HR2	TV Dalmacija	Croatian	Split	5h
SR1	Peščanik	Serbian	Belgrade	5h
SR2	Južne vesti	Serbian	Niš	5h

eral versions of the multi-reference. For example, the model WhisperV obtains eight scores on the segment 170918_17_18, the first four of these scores (0.222, 0.455, 0.111, 0.364) are obtained on four standardised versions of the multi-reference, while the second four scores (0.100, 0.333, 0.000, 0.250) are obtained on four literal versions. The number of scores per audio segment and per model can go over 70 depending on the presence of numbers and abbreviations, but also on the length of the utterance.

The models are tested in the *Mak na konac* project (Samardžić et al., 2024), which has also provided the multi-reference gold standard. The evaluation reports are created in the original evaluation but have not been analysed up to now. Each evaluation report is a large table that contains meta-data and CER (character error rate) scores in addition to the WER (word error rate) scores shown in Table 1. For this study, we use only the WER scores and focus on only one of many possible factors that can be analysed, namely the difference between the scores on the standardised and literal transcripts, leaving other possible factors (e.g. regional variation, the differences in transcribing digits and abbreviations, genre, speakers’ metadata) for future research.

3.1 Key features of the test data

The test set is designed to include two variants for each of the two languages. The variant spoken in Zagreb (HR1) can be considered close to the standard Croatian, while Split is a Southern Croatian region with marked dialectal features. The same design is followed in the case of Serbian, where Belgrade (SR1) is close to the standard and Niš (SR2) is a Southern variant with marked dialectal features.

Somewhat surprisingly, the models’ performance turned out better on the the Southern versions both in Croatian and Serbian, while the Zagreb sample turned out the most difficult. It appears that other elements, that are yet to be understood, influenced the model performance more than their regional markedness.

3.2 Key features of the tested models

We analyse the performance of seven freely available models previously tested in the *Mak na konac* project:

- WhisperV: multilingual Whisper large-v3, which is pre-trained on 1 million hours of weakly labelled data and 4 million hours of pseudo-labelled data, produced with its predecessor, Whisper-large-v2. It is capable of automatically determining the language of the input speech as well as translating input speech into a variety of languages.
- WhisperS and WhisperSJV: two variants of the WhisperV model fine-tuned on transcribed Serbian audio. The first variant is fine-tuned on Mozilla Common Voice 13 and Google Fleurs, while the ASR training data set for Serbian JuzneVesti-SR v1.0 (Rupnik

& Ljubešić, 2022) is added to the training set for the second variant.

- Transducer and CTC are parts of NVIDIA’s NeMo toolkit. The main difference between the two variants is that Transducer takes previously generated letter as input at the next step, while CTC does not (it combines the acoustic and the language model in a more traditional way). In both of these settings, we test the model that was trained on Croatian parliamentary data set ParlaSpeech-HR (Ljubešić et al., 2022).
- W2V2XLSR and W2V2Slavic are models based on the wav2vec2 architecture. This means that they are first trained on large quantities of unlabelled audio alone. The former is then fine-tuned on a multilingual text and speech datasets (XLS-R), while for the latter, the VoxPopuli Slavic labelled data (Wang et al., 2021) are used.

Regarding the models, the most important difference is whether they are pre-trained or trained from scratch. The latter option allows more control over the training data and fitting the models more closely to the target, but these models are smaller and might not capture all the nuances that can be accommodated by the pre-trained models that are bigger. On the other hand, the bigger models require much more data to be trained, which is why they cannot be trained for any single language (except English) specifically.

Another factor that we take into consideration is the presence vs. absence of fine-tuning. The only model that is not specifically fine-tuned for any Croatian or Serbian target data is WhisperV, although it is very likely that some Croatian and Serbian data are included in its, highly multilingual, training set. Two tested solutions (WhisperS and WhisperSJV) are created by fine-tuning Whisper on two small sets of Serbian data. The other models are trained on Croatian data (recordings of the Parliament sessions). Transducer and CTC are trained from scratch, while W2V2XLSR and W2V2Slavic are fine-tuned on Croatian data while pre-trained on multilingual and Slavic data respectively.

According to the evaluation reports, the best performing model overall is, again surprisingly, WhisperV, followed by the two small models trained on Croatian (Transducer and CTC), while the worst solutions are the two W2V2 models fine-tuned on Croatian. Interestingly, these rankings are invariant across the two languages. The only solutions that do show some sensitivity to the language are the two Whisper models fine-tuned on Serbian data: their scores are generally better on Serbian than on Croatian data.

3.3 Collecting the counts

We group the extracted scores so that all scores for standard transcripts (the first half of the arrays in Table 1) are in one group and all scores for the literal versions (the second half of the arrays) in the other. We then sum up for each segment all the scores in one group, to obtain one value for the literal and one for the standard versions for that segment. Next, we compare the sums and define the following cases:

- 'literal' : $\text{sum}(\text{literal}) < \text{sum}(\text{standard})$
- 'standard' : $\text{sum}(\text{standard}) < \text{sum}(\text{literal})$
- 'tie' : $\text{sum}(\text{standard}) = \text{sum}(\text{literal})$

In the first two cases, the “winner” is the lower sum of WER scores, while there is no winner in third case.

Once the winner is known for each segment, we count the number of wins for each case and the number of ties in each data part. We then scale the counts to obtain normalised values (between 0 and 1) showing the proportion of each case for each model in each data part. These proportions tell us how often the scores differed between standard and literal transcripts and, out of all different scores, how often they were better for the literal and how often for standard transcripts. Note that the ties can be due to the lack of differences in the multi-reference or due to the models’ mistakes cancelling out each other even when the references differ. For now, we cannot distinguish between these two reasons for ties since we do not have access to the references.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the proportions of the three outcomes: better WER scores when the models are evaluated against the standard version of the reference, better WER scores on the literal versions and equal scores on both versions. Each stacked bar represents one model that is evaluated and each plot represents one data part.

The first finding that becomes apparent when comparing the plots is that the proportions of ties are almost constant for all models on the same data part. This proportion is the highest in SR1 (0.68) and the lowest in HR1 (under 0.5 for all the models). Recall that these proportions depend on the (unknown) proportions of the reference transcripts where there were no differences between the two versions. Looking at the plots, it is likely that the differences are the smallest in SR1 and the biggest in HR1. In the case of SR1, this finding corresponds to what could be expected given that this data part represents a variant close to the standard. The opposite is true in the case of HR1, where the literal version of the reference seems to be rather different from the standard version. This might be due to the use of other forms of non-standard language (e.g. slang), but

Figure 1: Proportions of cases in which the models’ WER scores were better for the standard version of reference (top bars), or for the literal version (middle bars) or equal (bottom bars).

this is still to be established. We can also see that the proportions of ties vary somewhat less in the two Serbian than in the two Croatian data parts. The fact that there is more variation between the models on Croatian data might have something to do with the use of Croatian data for training. With the exception of the models fine-tuned on Serbian, the proportions are smaller for the models that perform better (WhisperV, Transducer and CTC). This means that better models have fewer mistakes that cancel out each other. In other words, when models’ performance is better, the equal scores are more due to the lack of differences between the references than to models’ mistakes.

Comparing the proportions of literal vs. standard, we see that the models get better scores on literal references (bigger darker bars) overall. In other words, when there is a difference between the references, the literal one gives better scores. Interestingly, this pattern is the weakest in the case of the best performing model, WhisperV in all four data parts (smaller darker bars than in other models), which means that this model gains its advantage by standardising its output. In the case of HR2, the same strategy seems to have been applied by the two small models trained from scratch on Croatian (Transducer and CTC), which are the only ones to outperform WhisperV. By getting the standard of the refer-

ence right in more cases, these models have fewer ties and more success on the standard reference.

The results of the model WhisperS, which is WhisperV fine-tuned on a relatively small Serbian data set, provide an interesting insight into what can happen when fine-tuning a large multilingual model on a specific data set. The drop in the performance compared to the original model (without fine-tuning) on all data parts (cf. Table 2) indicates a potential overfitting. Note also that the drop is more pronounced on the Croatian parts, which can be seen as an additional confirmation of overfitting. This pattern itself is not very surprising, but our results reveal a more interesting trend: this is the model that has the lowest rate of better scores on the literal reference. In fact, this is the only model whose scores are better on the standard reference across all data parts. It looks like fine-tuning pushed the model to more standardised outputs. The fine-tuned model seems to output what is expected in a given context, neglecting to some degree what it receives as the audio input. This behaviour might be a case of increased model “hallucinations” deserving a further investigation in future work.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we have addressed the question of whether modern models, (pre)-trained on large data

sets output transcripts that are closer to the standard language moving away from literal transcription. The results of our study indicate that the majority of the tested models obtain better scores on the literal version of the multi-reference than on the standard version. However, the best performing model overall (Whisper without fine-tuning) gets slightly higher scores on the standard version than all the other models. It seems that standardising the output a little more than the other models allows it to generalise better and perform relatively well on diverse data parts. When fine-tuned on a small language-specific data set, this model is pushed even further towards standardising, but this behaviour results in a performance drop suggesting that the standardising strategy is not helpful when the model is overfitting.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the *Mak na konac* project for their help in providing the evaluation reports. We also thank the data providers for sharing their contents: Radio Student Zagreb 'Ponedjeljkom u 3 PM', TV Dalmacija (<https://dalmacija.tv/>), Peščanik (<https://pescanik.net/>), and Južne Vesti (<https://www.juznevesti.com/>).

This work was partially funded by the programme P6-0411 "Language Resources and Technologies for Slovene", the CLARIN.SI infrastructure, and the project J7-4642 "MEZ-ZANINE - Development of Spoken Language Resources and Speech Technologies for the Slovenian Language", all financed by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS).

REFERENCES

- Ali, A., Magdy, W., Bell, P., & Renais, S. (2015). Multi-reference wer for evaluating asr for languages with no orthographic rules. In *2015 IEEE Workshop on Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding (ASRU)* (p. 576-580). doi: 10.1109/ASRU.2015.7404847
- Ljubešić, N., Koržinek, D., Rupnik, P., & Jazbec, I.-P. (2022, June). ParlaSpeech-HR - a freely available ASR dataset for Croatian bootstrapped from the ParlaMint corpus. In D. Fišer, M. Eskevich, J. Lenardič, & F. de Jong (Eds.), *Proceedings of the workshop parlaclarin iii within the 13th language resources and evaluation conference* (pp. 111-116). Marseille, France: European Language Resources Association. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.parlaclarin-1.16/>
- Ljubešić, N., Koržinek, D., Rupnik, P., Jazbec, I.-P., Batanović, V., Bajčetić, L., & Evkoski, B. (2022). *ASR training dataset for croatian ParlaSpeech-HR v1.0*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1494> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- Nigmatulina, I., Kew, T., & Samardžic, T. (2020, December). ASR for non-standardised languages with dialectal variation: the case of Swiss German. In M. Zampieri, P. Nakov, N. Ljubešić, J. Tiedemann, & Y. Scherrer (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 7th workshop on nlp for similar languages, varieties and dialects* (pp. 15-24). Barcelona, Spain (Online): International Committee on Computational Linguistics (ICCL). <https://aclanthology.org/2020.vardial-1.2>
- Popović, B., Ostrogonac, S., Pakoci, E., Jakovljević, N., & Deli, V. (2015). Deep neural network based continuous speech recognition for serbian using the kaldi toolkit. In A. Ronzhin, R. Potapova, & N. Fakotakis (Eds.), *Speech and computer* (pp. 186-192). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Povey, D., Ghoshal, A., Boulianne, G., Burget, L., Glembek, O., Goel, N., ... Vesely, K. (2011, December). The kaldi speech recognition toolkit. In *Ieee 2011 workshop on automatic speech recognition and understanding*. IEEE Signal Processing Society. (IEEE Catalog No.: CFP11SRW-USB)
- Radford, A., Kim, J. W., Xu, T., Brockman, G., McLeavey, C., & Sutskever, I. (2022). *Robust speech recognition via large-scale weak supervision*. arXiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.04356> doi: 10.48550/ARXIV.2212.04356
- Rupnik, P., & Ljubešić, N. (2022). *ASR training dataset for serbian JuzneVesti-SR v1.0*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1679> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- Sagić, A. (2023). *Whisper-large-v3-sr-combined*. Retrieved 2024-05-28, from <https://huggingface.co/Sagicc/whisper-large-v3-sr-combined>
- Samardžić, T., Rupnik, P., Starović, M., & Ljubešić, N. (2024). Mak na konac: A multi-reference speech-to-text benchmark for croatian and serbian. Institute of Contemporary History. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13936420> doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13936420
- Verdonik, D., Dobrovoljc, K., Erjavec, T., & Ljubešić, N. (2024, May). Gos 2: A new reference corpus of spoken Slovenian. In N. Calzolari, M.-Y. Kan, V. Hoste, A. Lenci, S. Sakti, & N. Xue (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2024 joint international conference on computational linguistics, language resources and evaluation (lrec-coling 2024)* (pp. 7825-7830). Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lrec-main.691/>
- Wang, C., Rivière, M., Lee, A., Wu, A., Talnikar, C., Haziza, D., ... Dupoux, E. (2021). Voxpopuli: A large-scale multilingual speech corpus for representation learning, semi-supervised learning and interpretation. *CoRR*, [abs/2101.00390](https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.00390). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.00390>
- Žgank, A., Vitez, A. Z., & Verdonik, D. (2014, May). The Slovene BNSI broadcast news database and reference speech corpus GOS: Towards the uniform guidelines for future work. In N. Calzolari et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ninth international conference on language resources and evaluation (LREC'14)* (pp. 2644-2647). Reykjavik, Iceland: European Language Resources Association (ELRA). http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2014/pdf/710_Paper.pdf

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

EXPLAINABLE LINGUISTIC VARIETY CLASSIFICATION: THE CASE OF BOSNIAN-CROATIAN-MONTENEGRIN-SERBIAN

Aleksandra MILETIĆ,¹ Timothee MICKUS,² Yves SCHERRER^{2,3}

¹UMR 7114 MoDyCo (CNRS & Paris Nanterre University, France)

²Department of Digital Humanities (University of Helsinki, Finland)

³Department of Informatics (University of Oslo, Norway)

This paper presents a preliminary evaluation and analysis of a method for explainable linguistic variety classification applied to Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin, and Serbian. Neural models have become the de-facto standard for most NLP tasks and applications, but the factors influencing their predictions remain to a large extent opaque. Using Twitter data, we aim to detect the linguistic features that contribute most to the classification decisions and conduct an extensive manual analysis of these features. The results show that the global model behaviour of neural classifiers aligns with existing knowledge about variation in these varieties, although the models struggle to identify features specific to a single variety, especially in the case of Bosnian and Montenegrin. Overall, the paper showcases the applicability of the examined explainability method in sociolinguistic contexts characterized by complex variation patterns, thereby demonstrating the interest of explainable machine learning methods for corpus-based variation research.

Keywords: language variety classification, explainability, Bosnian-Croatian-Montenegrin-Serbian

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an initial evaluation and analysis of explainable classification of linguistic varieties for Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin, and Serbian (BCMS). During ex-Yugoslavia, these varieties were considered as belonging to the same standard language (typically referred to as Croato-Serbian or Serbo-Croatian). Since the end of Yugoslavia in the 1990s, national standards have emerged. The status of these varieties with respect to each other is frequently discussed and often understood in academic circles as pertaining to identity construction (Alexander, 2013). And while they are mutually intelligible, differences exist (Ljubešić et al., 2018). This situation makes BCMS a prime candidate for work on distinguishing between similar languages, as attested by its regular presence in the VarDial shared tasks since their very first iteration in 2014 (Zampieri et al., 2014, 2015; Malmasi et al., 2016; Zampieri et al., 2017; Chifu et al., 2024).

Indeed, language identification, and in particular the discrimination between closely related language varieties, has been a relatively well researched topic in recent years (Jauhiainen et al., 2019). However, most work has aimed at improving classification accuracy and at making the experimental setup as realistic as possible, while comparatively less effort has gone into analyzing which features contribute most to the model predictions. Yet such an analysis is relevant both from an NLP point of view, as it increases model interpretability, and from a linguistic point of view, as it can provide new

Figure 1: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia and neighbouring countries. Map data ©2023 GeoBasis-DE/BKG (©2009), Google.

insights on how language varies across regions. This is particularly relevant for BCMS: descriptions of the linguistic variation exist, but empirical corpus-based work is still sparse (Ljubešić et al., 2018; Miletić & Miletić, 2024).

Although the advent of quantitative, corpus-based methods has enabled linguists to obtain relatively objective, high-level classifications of linguistic areas, tracing back these classifications to individual features (e.g., words) has proven challenging (Leinonen, 2008; Eisen-

stein et al., 2010; Hovy & Purschke, 2018; Kuparinen & Scherrer, 2024). To answer this challenge, we draw on the growing list of work in interpretability and explainability in machine learning, and in particular on explainable dialect classification (Xie et al., 2024). We use these methods to extract the most relevant features for each variety from trained classifiers. We then conduct an extensive manual analysis of these features, classifying them according to the level of linguistic structure concerned by the variation (phonetics, morphology, lexicon, etc.). This allows us to examine the relationship between different feature categories and individual varieties, making it possible to compare model behaviour to the results from previous empirical studies on variation in BCMS.¹

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 BCMS and variation

Linguistic variation between Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian concerns all levels of linguistic structure: phonetic, phonological, morpho-syntactic, and lexical, and even orthographic conventions can vary. Ljubešić et al. (2018) conducted a corpus-based study of BCMS in which they examined the geographical spread of 16 linguistic variables on phonetic, morphosyntactic and lexical levels. The results situate Croatian and Serbian at the opposing ends of the continuum, whereas Bosnian and Montenegrin tend to align with the one or the other depending on the variable.

Variation illustrations are provided in Figure 2 (extracted from the corpus used in this study; see Section 3). The lexical item *sevap* ‘good deed’ is typical of Bosnian, and the grapheme *š* is only used in Montenegrin. Other features can have an asymmetrical spread: the short form of the infinitive *našutat* ‘to kick’ in the Bosnian example is also found in Croatian and Montenegrin, whereas for Serbian the long form *našutati* would be expected (Ljubešić et al., 2018, p. 18-19). This is also the case for the most salient form of variation between these varieties: the difference between the ekavian and the ijekavian pronunciation, reflected by the *e:i*je variation. Serbian is the only of the four national standards based on both pronunciations. Therefore the presence of an ekavian form would be strongly indicative of Serbian. This is instantiated in the word *svet* ‘world’ in the Serbian example; in Bosnian, Croatian and Montenegrin, the ijekavian equivalent *svijet* would be expected as more frequent (Ljubešić et al., 2018, p. 18).

Ljubešić et al. (2018) also note the asymmetry in the spread of different variables, which can make some

Figure 2: Examples of distinctive features for language variety identification. The coloured characters and words indicate features that are specific to the variety in parentheses. Red: morphological; blue: phonetic/phonological; violet: lexical; green: spelling; orange: named entities.

Bosnian:
Neke osobe je sevap našutat [’] ‘It’s a good deed to kick certain people’
Croatian:
”to je nogomet ” um ne, to nije vidlo n od nogometa ”that’s football” um no, not even close’
Montenegrin:
A kako š utra ima da pane jedna četvorka iz biologije! ‘I’m so getting a B in biology tomorrow!’
Serbian:
beograd je svet , a? ‘belrade is the world, huh?’

of the four varieties harder to identify than others. This seems to be the case both for humans and for NLP systems. Miletić and Miletić (2024) report higher levels of human annotator uncertainty when identifying instances from Bosnia-Herzegovina and Montenegro compared to Croatia and Serbia. And Rupnik et al. (2023) note that their classifiers perform well on Serbian (1.0 micro F1) and Croatian (0.83), but the results are lower on Bosnian (0.75–0.80), and they drop significantly on Montenegrin (0.10–0.36).

In this light, our experiments aim to answer the following questions:

- How easy/hard is it to identify features relevant for different varieties with our approach?
- Is it possible to identify features that are uniquely relevant to a single variety?
- Do the examined models rely on all levels of variation equally or do they favour some of them?

2.2 Explainable classification of linguistic varieties

The ever widening use of neural network-based architectures and large language models in NLP has led to an increasing need for transparency and understandability of these models. Initial work included building an interpretable model around the prediction model in order to provide insights into classifier predictions (Ribeiro et al., 2016), introducing representation erasure (Li et al., 2017), and examining the role of convolutional neural network filters (Jacovi et al., 2018). Belinkov et al. (2020) proposed a categorization of explainability research including the following categories: classifier probing, behavioural studies, test suite development, and interactive visualization creation.

¹Our data and code is available at <https://github.com/Helsinki-NLP/explainable-bcms-classification>

Two recent papers specifically explore the idea of applying methods from explainability research to linguistic variety classification. Rönqvist et al. (2022) focus on the task of identifying registers in web texts and automatically extracting the most characteristic keywords of each register. They train an XLM-R classifier on the register identification task and use the Integrated Gradients (IG) method (Sundararajan et al., 2017) to determine which individual words contribute most to the classification. The extracted keywords are then aggregated over instances and over several independent runs. Xie et al. (2024) work with binary dialect identification tasks: Mainland vs. Taiwan Mandarin and Sicilian vs. Italian. They use a different explainability method called *leave-one-out* (LOO). Just like IG, LOO is a post-hoc approach, i.e., it operates at inference time, on a normally trained dialect classification model. It works by removing one feature at a time from the input and interpreting the change in prediction probability as a *relevance score* of that particular feature.

In this work, we adopt the LOO method for the following reasons:

- The logic behind the approach is transparent and it aligns with the expectation that more distinctive features should have a stronger impact on the classifier;
- The methodology was reasonably well documented and straightforward to implement;
- The output is readily interpretable by human annotators.

3 DATASET

As mentioned above, the socio-linguistic reality of BCMS is complex. As a quick illustration, in the 2023 Montenegro census, 43.2% of citizens identified as speakers of Serbian, 34.5% as speakers of Montenegrin, and 7.3% as speakers of Bosnian.² And in the 2013 Bosnia-Herzegovina census, 52.9% of citizens identified as speakers of Bosnian, 30.8% as speakers of Serbian, and 14.6% as speakers of Croatian.³ In order to fully capture the spread and the properties of these varieties, a comprehensive, large-scale sociolinguistic corpus would be needed. Unfortunately, to the best of our knowledge no such resource is currently available. For the purposes of this study, we therefore consider Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian as loosely corresponding to the variety spoken in the respective country and influenced by the national standardization efforts throughout the past decades. This aligns with the approach adopted by Ljubešić et al. (2018), who examine the

spread of linguistic variables within the four countries, thus allowing us to draw comparisons where relevant. There is also a quantitative argument to be made for this approach: one can reasonably expect a national standard to affect linguistic practices in its respective country, and thereby it can be expected that e.g. the Bosnian-Herzegovinian subset of our data should largely map onto the Bosnian national standard. This is, of course, mainly an approximation of a more complex linguistic landscape, and one that need not be entirely appropriate. The results presented here should be interpreted in the same light.

We rely on a dataset proposed by Rupnik et al. (2023), whose various iterations have been regularly used in the NLP domain for the task of distinguishing between similar languages (Zampieri et al., 2014, 2015; Malmasi et al., 2016; Zampieri et al., 2017; Chifu et al., 2024). The data was collected from the social media platform Twitter (rebranded as X in 2023). The original annotation of linguistic varieties was done in several steps. In the first two steps, users susceptible to tweet in BCMS were identified based on variety-specific word lists containing highly frequent items, and subsequently language identification tools, including ones specifically aimed at BCMS, were used (Ljubešić et al., 2014). The final annotation into the four varieties was executed by a single human annotator, with a single label given to each Twitter user (Ljubešić & Kranjčić, 2015).

In this study, we use a revised version of the dataset, in which the *dev* and *test* sets were re-annotated in a multi-label setting, by multiple annotators speaking all four varieties (Miletić & Miletić, 2024). Thus the evaluation sets used here reflect possible ambiguities and overlaps between the four varieties.

The original dataset exhibited a strong skew towards Serbian. We therefore downsized this class to the next largest class in the dataset (Croatian). In a second step, we modified the size of instances: originally, they corresponded to the full tweet production of a single user. For the purposes of our experiments, we segmented each instance into sentences and projected the label of the full instance onto each of the sentences. Since the resulting annotation has not been validated manually, it is possible that instances not carrying clear markers of a given variety still carry the corresponding label. We further discuss this in Section 5.

A quantitative overview of the dataset is available in Table 1. For ease of presentation, we count multilabel instances in the *test* and *dev* sets as belonging to each of the classes for which they have been annotated. Details on multilabel instances can be found in Appendix A.

²https://www.monstat.org/uploads/files/popis%202021/saopstenja/SAOPSTENJE_Popis%20stanovnistva%202023%20II_cg.pdf

³<http://www.statistika.ba/?show=8#link4>

Table 1: Dataset overview. Sizes given as number of instances.

Classes	Train	Dev	Test	Subtotal
Bosnian	16,463	7,610	7,606	31,679
Croatian	23,691	11,141	11,310	46,142
Montenegrin	13,155	4,488	8,513	26,156
Serbian	23,784	13,076	13,431	50,291
Total	77,093	36,315	40,860	154,268

4 METHODOLOGY

Our experimental setup involves three steps:

1. We train models on the linguistic variety classification task.
2. We extract variety-specific features from the trained models using the Leave-one-out approach.
3. We manually annotate the extracted features and assess their relevance.

Given that finetuned BERT models have been shown to be well-suited to the task of distinguishing between similar varieties (Gaman et al., 2020; Chifu et al., 2024), we train two BERT-based classifiers: a multilingual XLM-RoBERTa model (Conneau et al., 2020) and a language-specific BERTic (Ljubešić & Lauc, 2021). As a baseline, we use a logistic regression model from which we directly extract the most relevant features per class.

4.1 Logistic regression

Training We use a simple logistic regression model, as provided by the *scikit-learn* library, with 500 iterations, integers set to `numpy.int8` to save memory, and otherwise default parameters. We encode the text samples as bag-of-words count vectors without any weighting or pruning. Also, we do not perform any subword segmentation.

Feature extraction For each class, we identify the 30 features (words) with the highest weight coefficients in the trained model. This approach only yields features that were present in the training set. For comparability with the BERT-based approach, we only retain those features that also appear in the test set.

4.2 BERT-based models

Training We perform supervised fine-tuning on the training data for 10 epochs and select the best model checkpoint based on validation accuracy.

Feature extraction We apply the **leave-one-out (LOO) method** proposed by Xie et al. (2024). This method processes each sentence of the test set independently to

detect the features that contribute most to the classification decision. It consists of the following steps:

1. Take a test instance x , pass it through the classifier, and keep both the predicted class \hat{y} and the prediction score ℓ . If the classifier’s prediction is incorrect ($\hat{y} \neq y$), move on to the next instance.⁴
2. Select and remove a word from the test instance (we denote this modified instance as x_i , where word i has been removed), run it through the classifier again, and record the new prediction score ℓ_i .⁵
3. Calculate how much removing the word affects the classifier’s performance by subtracting the new score from the original score: $\Delta_i = \ell - \ell_i$. We refer to Δ_i as the *impact score* for word i .
4. Repeat steps 2 and 3 for every word in the instance.
5. Identify the 5 words with the highest impact scores.⁶

The steps outlined above generate instance-level *explanations*, identifying the words that have the greatest influence on each individual instance.

We aggregate the explanations across all instances of the test set for evaluation. The resulting list is processed in the following way:

1. For each extracted item, we compute the average impact score on the basis of the individual impact scores.⁷
2. For each class, we select the 100 items with the highest average impact scores for the analysis. This means that for each model, a total of 400 features are examined.
3. The extraction is done in two ways: 1) by selecting the items that were extracted only for a single variety (denoted SV in Table 3), and 2) by allowing for items that were extracted for several classes but not all of them (denoted MV in Table 3). This is motivated by the observation that linguistic features often do not have the same spread across the linguistic varieties discussed in Section 2.1.

⁴This is equivalent to the *isCorrect* condition described by Xie et al. (2024).

⁵Xie et al. (2024) remove words based on their position in the sentence, meaning if a word appears multiple times, only one occurrence is removed at a time. Their method focuses on the occurrence that leads to the largest score change. Instead, we remove all occurrences of the word simultaneously.

⁶While Xie et al. (2024) do not mention this threshold in their written methodology, it is included in their implementation.

⁷Xie et al. (2024) use TF-IDF to rank the words. We find that the simpler approach of averaging the scores is sufficient for our purposes.

Table 2: Classification accuracies across models.

Model	Accuracy
LR	52.3
XLM-R	68.0
BERTiĆ	73.1

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Linguistic variety classification

Table 2 shows the classification accuracies obtained by the logistic regression baseline and the BERT-based classifiers. Unsurprisingly, the neural models outperform the baseline by a wide margin, and the language-specific BERTiĆ beats multilingual XLM-R. However, the performances of neural models remain relatively low (73.1 and 68.0 accuracy points respectively). This could be due to the fact that the original corpus instances were split into sentences, and the variety label attributed to the original instance was projected onto all resulting sentences. This can in fact lead to having instances that do not carry specific markers, but which are attributed to a single variety.

5.2 Variety-specific feature extraction

Both logistic regression and leave-one-out classification yield lists of variety-specific linguistic features. These features were manually annotated as belonging to *Lexicon*, *Phonetics/phonology*, *Morphology*, *Named Entities*, *Spelling*, *Other* or *Unmarked*, the last one indicating items that do not contain any variety-specific information. The annotation was done by a single annotator, who is a linguist and a native speaker of Serbian. The results of the annotation are shown in Table 3.

5.2.1 GLOBAL ANALYSIS

We examine first the general usefulness of the extracted features. The main goal of our setup is to identify marked features that are specific to one or several varieties. The presence of unmarked features is therefore undesirable and these features can be seen as errors. The LR model presents a relatively low percentage of unmarked features in the analyzed list, whereas they systematically represent >10% of the top 100 features for the neural models (e.g. *volim* ‘I love’ extracted from BERTiĆ for Serbian, *zna* ‘he/she knows’ extracted from XLM-R for Bosnian). In this respect, they seem less reliable than the LR model.

On the other hand, the LR model has a much higher prevalence of features in the *Other* category compared to the neural models. This category contains mostly corpus artifacts: occasional words in other languages, hash tags, URLs and user names. 57.5% of the analyzed fea-

tures from the LR model are therefore irrelevant from the linguistic point of view.

Similarly, although to a lesser extent, the BERT-based models show a significant reliance on named entities. Our manual analysis shows that these are often related to geographic terms specific to a single country (e.g. *Podgoričani* (inhabitants of Podgorica, the capital of Montenegro) extracted from BERTiĆ for Montenegrin; *Mostar* (city in Bosnia and Herzegovina) extracted from XLM-R for Bosnian, etc.) and therefore conflate regional topical differences with variation pertaining to linguistic structures.

It is also notable that the behaviour of the neural models is comparable whether we take into account features specific to a single variety (rows marked SV in Table 3) or those that were extracted for multiple varieties (but not all of them; rows marked MV). For instance, the difference between the two extraction scenarios for the phonetic features is 2.5% for BERTiĆ and 1.5% for XLM-R.

Among the extracted linguistic features, the most prominent category concerns *Phonetics/phonology*, independently of the model and of the extraction mode. It is followed by *Morphology* and *Lexicon*. We take a closer look at the distribution of these across varieties and discuss salient examples.

5.2.2 ANALYSIS BY VARIETY AND BY FEATURE CATEGORY

The distribution of analyzed features by feature category is presented in Table 4.

The overall frequency of phonetic and phonological features seems to be driven by Serbian: this category covers 64% of the analyzed features extracted from BERTiĆ, and 57% of those extracted from XLM-R. For the other three varieties, this percentage is much lower (12-24%). All of the Serbian features from this category are ekavian forms having ijekavian equivalents in the other three varieties (cf. *lep* ‘beautiful’, which would be expected as *lijep* in Croatian, Bosnian and Montenegrin). Conversely, the features extracted for this level for the other three varieties predominantly contain ijekavian forms having ekavian equivalents, but there are also some more specific features. For Croatian, both models propose inflected forms of *kava* ‘coffee’ (the expected form in Serbian being *kafa*, while Bosnian also allows *kahva*). Also, both models identify the form *đe* ‘where’ for Montenegrin (whereas *gdje* would be expected in Croatian and Bosnian, and *gde* in Serbian).

The most morphological features were found in the lists for Croatian, independently of the model. They overwhelmingly concern the use of the short infinitive, such as *dobit* ‘to receive’ and *doć* ‘to come’ (the corresponding long forms being *dobiti* and *doći*). However,

Table 3: Leave-one-out result annotation. Percentage of extracted features per category. Individual values may not sum to totals due to rounding.

Model	Scenario	Phon.	Morphology	Lexicon	Named Entities	Spelling	Other	Unmarked
LR	MV	27.5	0.0	6.7	1.7	2.5	57.5	4.2
BERTić	SV	29.5	6.0	8.3	15.5	0.5	27.3	13.0
	MV	27.0	4.3	10.8	18.0	0.5	28.3	11.3
XLM-R	SV	25.8	4.8	6.3	16.0	0.8	34.5	12.0
	MV	27.3	5.3	6.5	12.0	0.8	29.3	19.0

Table 4: Features extracted for **multiple varieties**: Distribution per feature category and linguistic variety.

		Phon.	Morphology	Lexicon	Named Entities	Spelling	Other	Unmarked
BERTić	Bosnian	15.0	0.0	6.0	28.0	2.0	37.0	12.0
	Croatian	17.0	14.0	19.0	9.0	0.0	24.0	17.0
	Montenegrin	22.0	8.0	4.0	21.0	0.0	22.0	23.0
	Serbian	64.0	2.0	4.0	4.0	0.0	26.0	0.0
XLM-R	Bosnian	16.0	0.0	8.0	27.0	0.0	26.0	23.0
	Croatian	12.0	19.0	5.0	7.0	1.0	39.0	17.0
	Montenegrin	24.0	0.0	4.0	11.0	2.0	33.0	26.0
	Serbian	57.0	2.0	9.0	3.0	0.0	19.0	10.0

some of the infinitives also reflect a difference in the derivation patterns of some verbs, which contrast verbs ending in *-irati* in Croatian with verbs ending in *-ovati* in Serbian (cf. *organizirat* ‘to organize’; the expected form in Bosnian, Montenegrin and Serbian would be *organizovati*; Ljubešić et al., 2018, p. 16). Lexical items mostly reflect terms for which a different root is used in Serbian (cf. *dojam* ‘impression’ and *otok* ‘island’ in Croatian, whereas *utisak* and *ostrvo* would be expected in Serbian; Nikolić, 2011).

The features extracted for Bosnian and Montenegrin present similar distributions: the bulk of linguistically relevant features rely on phonetics and phonology, there are relatively few features pertaining to morphology and lexicon, and there is higher reliance on named entities compared to Croatian and Serbian. The models do manage to identify *raja* ‘people, folks’ as a lexical item specific to Bosnian, and XLM-R picks up on *profesorica* ‘professor (feminine)’ for Montenegrin (expected form in Serbian: *profesorka*, whereas *profesorica* would be expected both in Bosnian and Croatian; Ljubešić et al., 2018, p. 18).

These results align with previous observations on the relationship between these four varieties. Croatian and Serbian seem the most distinctive when looking at the linguistic features. The classification of Serbian relies heavily on the *e:ije* variation thanks to the asymmetrical spread of the ekavian forms. On the other hand, the relevance of lexical and morphological features for the classification of Croatian may be due to the fact that the phonetic features are not sufficiently distinctive (given

that Bosnian and Montenegrin are also ijekavian). The fact that there are fewer morphological and lexical features detected for Bosnian and Montenegrin aligns with the findings by Ljubešić et al. (2018), discussed in Section 2.1. Globally, our analysis reveals that the model performance seems to align with previous research on these varieties.

We also examine extraction results when only features relevant for a single variety are allowed. This is motivated by the fact that such features would be of particular value for automatic variety identification. In this scenario, the models do not fare well. Given the ambiguity of ijekavian forms between Croatian, Bosnian and Montenegrin, in this scenario we would expect less of a reliance on phonetic and phonological features for these three varieties. But when looking at the results in Table 5, we see only a slight dip for Montenegrin and Croatian, with a slightly more pronounced effect on Bosnian compared to results in Table 4. For BERTić, dips are observable too for the morphological features. Conversely, there is a slight increase in the lexical feature count, but the category that gains the most features in this setup is named entities. This may be an indication that phonetic and morphological features specific to only one of these three varieties are hard to identify. This is further underscored by the fact that the extracted features are mostly the same as the ones extracted in the more relaxed scenario allowing for features relevant for multiple varieties. The vast majority of them are not specific to a single variety.

Table 5: Features extracted for a **single variety**. Distribution per feature category and linguistic variety.

		Phon.	Morphology	Lexicon	NE	Spelling	Other	Unmarked
BERTiC	Bosnian	7.0	0.0	8.0	34.0	2.0	36.0	13.0
	Croatian	16.0	11.0	20.0	14.0	0.0	26.0	13.0
	Montenegrin	20.0	5.0	11.0	20.0	0.0	25.0	19.0
	Serbian	65.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	0.0	26.0	0.0
XLM-R	Bosnian	5.0	0.0	7.0	36.0	0.0	41.0	11.0
	Croatian	10.0	19.0	6.0	10.0	1.0	40.0	14.0
	Montenegrin	25.0	0.0	3.0	16.0	2.0	39.0	15.0
	Serbian	63.0	0.0	9.0	2.0	0.0	18.0	8.0

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an initial evaluation and analysis of the Leave-one-out method for explainable linguistic variety classification, proposed by Xie et al. (2024), on Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin, and Serbian. This consisted in training two BERT-based classifiers, using the Leave-one-out method to extract features that contribute most to classification decisions, and manually analysing the list of extracted features.

Our results indicate that the model behaviour generally aligns with existing linguistic knowledge about variation between these four varieties: classification of Serbian relies heavily on the asymmetry of the *e:ije* variation and exploits the presence of ekavian forms; the feature list for Croatian contains a more even spread of phonetic, morphological and lexical features, with the morphological features capturing the variation between the short and the long infinitive, and some verbal derivation regularities; comparatively few morphological and lexical features are extracted for Bosnian and Montenegrin, which instead exhibit a higher reliance on named entities. All of these observations are in line with conclusions put forward by Ljubešić et al. (2018), which point to Croatian and Serbian as being at the opposing ends of the continuum, whereas Bosnian and Montenegrin tend to align with the one or the other, and display fewer features specific only to them.

Overall, the paper showcases the applicability of the chosen explainability method in sociolinguistic contexts characterized by complex patterns of variation, and thereby demonstrates the interest of explainable machine learning methods for corpus-based variation research.

7 LIMITATIONS

The work presented above has several limitations worth discussing. First, we evaluated a single explainability method. In future work, we will extend this to a wider selection of approaches. Second, the qualitative analysis is based on a manual annotation produced by a single

human annotator. The difficulty of the task reported by the annotator seems to justify the addition of a second annotator and an evaluation of inter-annotator agreement. Third, a quantitative evaluation of extracted features against ground truth would complement the current evaluation method. Since wide-coverage lexicons are available for Croatian and Serbian, we will implement this in our future work.

REFERENCES

- Alexander, R. (2013). Language and identity: The fate of serbo-croatian. In *Entangled histories of the balkans-volume one* (pp. 341–417). Brill.
- Belinkov, Y., Gehrmann, S., & Pavlick, E. (2020, July). Interpretability and analysis in neural NLP. In A. Savary & Y. Zhang (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 58th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics: Tutorial abstracts* (pp. 1–5). Online: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2020.acl-tutorials.1/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.acl-tutorials.1
- Chifu, A.-G., Glavaš, G., Ionescu, R. T., Ljubešić, N., Miletić, A., Miletić, F., ... Vulić, I. (2024, June). VarDial evaluation campaign 2024: Commonsense reasoning in dialects and multi-label similar language identification. In Y. Scherrer, T. Jauhainen, N. Ljubešić, M. Zampieri, P. Nakov, & J. Tiedemann (Eds.), *Proceedings of the eleventh workshop on nlp for similar languages, varieties, and dialects (vardial 2024)* (pp. 1–15). Mexico City, Mexico: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.vardial-1.1/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.vardial-1.1
- Conneau, A., Khandelwal, K., Goyal, N., Chaudhary, V., Wenzek, G., Guzmán, F., ... Stoyanov, V. (2020, July). Unsupervised cross-lingual representation learning at scale. In D. Jurafsky, J. Chai, N. Schluter, & J. Tetreault (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 58th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics* (pp. 8440–8451). Online: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2020.acl-main.747/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.747
- Eisenstein, J., O’Connor, B., Smith, N. A., & Xing, E. P. (2010, October). A latent variable model for geographic lexical variation. In H. Li & L. Màrquez (Eds.), *Proceedings*

- of the 2010 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing (pp. 1277–1287). Cambridge, MA: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/D10-1124/>
- Gaman, M., Hovy, D., Ionescu, R. T., Jauhiainen, H., Jauhiainen, T., Lindén, K., ... Zampieri, M. (2020, December). A report on the VarDial evaluation campaign 2020. In M. Zampieri, P. Nakov, N. Ljubešić, J. Tiedemann, & Y. Scherrer (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 7th workshop on nlp for similar languages, varieties and dialects* (pp. 1–14). Barcelona, Spain (Online): International Committee on Computational Linguistics (ICCL). <https://aclanthology.org/2020.vardial-1.1/>
- Hovy, D., & Purschke, C. (2018, October–November). Capturing regional variation with distributed place representations and geographic retrofitting. In E. Riloff, D. Chiang, J. Hockenmaier, & J. Tsujii (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2018 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing* (pp. 4383–4394). Brussels, Belgium: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/D18-1469/> doi: 10.18653/v1/D18-1469
- Jacovi, A., Sar Shalom, O., & Goldberg, Y. (2018). Understanding convolutional neural networks for text classification. In *Proceedings of the 2018 emnlp workshop blackboxnlp: Analyzing and interpreting neural networks for nlp* (p. 56–65). Brussels, Belgium: Association for Computational Linguistics. <http://aclweb.org/anthology/W18-5408> doi: 10.18653/v1/W18-5408
- Jauhiainen, T., Lui, M., Zampieri, M., Baldwin, T., & Lindén, K. (2019). Automatic language identification in texts: A survey. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 65, 675–782. <https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.1.11675>
- Kuparinen, O., & Scherrer, Y. (2024, May 20). Corpus-based dialectometry with topic models. *Journal of linguistic geography*. doi: 10.1017/jlg.2024.6
- Leinonen, T. (2008). Factor analysis of vowel pronunciation in Swedish dialects. *International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing*, 2(1-2), 189–204. <https://doi.org/10.3366/E175385480900038X> doi: 10.3366/E175385480900038X
- Li, J., Monroe, W., & Jurafsky, D. (2017). *Understanding neural networks through representation erasure*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1612.08220>
- Ljubešić, N., Fišer, D., & Erjavec, T. (2014, May). TweetCaT: a tool for building Twitter corpora of smaller languages. In N. Calzolari et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ninth international conference on language resources and evaluation (LREC'14)* (pp. 2279–2283). Reykjavik, Iceland: European Language Resources Association (ELRA). <https://aclanthology.org/L14-1642/>
- Ljubešić, N., & Kranjčić, D. (2015). Discriminating between closely related languages on twitter. *Informatica*, 39(1).
- Ljubešić, N., & Lauc, D. (2021, April). BERTiC - the transformer language model for Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian. In B. Babych et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 8th workshop on balto-slavic natural language processing* (pp. 37–42). Kiyv, Ukraine: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2021.bsnlp-1.5/>
- Ljubešić, N., Petrović, M. M., & Samardžić, T. (2018). Borders and boundaries in Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian: Twitter data to the rescue. *Journal of Linguistic Geography*, 6(2), 100–124.
- Malmasi, S., Zampieri, M., Ljubešić, N., Nakov, P., Ali, A., & Tiedemann, J. (2016, December). Discriminating between similar languages and Arabic dialect identification: A report on the third DSL shared task. In P. Nakov, M. Zampieri, L. Tan, N. Ljubešić, J. Tiedemann, & S. Malmasi (Eds.), *Proceedings of the third workshop on NLP for similar languages, varieties and dialects (VarDial3)* (pp. 1–14). Osaka, Japan: The COLING 2016 Organizing Committee. <https://aclanthology.org/W16-4801/>
- Miletić, A., & Miletić, F. (2024, May). A gold standard with silver linings: Scaling up annotation for distinguishing Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian. In S. Balloccu, A. Belz, R. Huidrom, E. Reiter, J. Sedoc, & C. Thomson (Eds.), *Proceedings of the fourth workshop on human evaluation of nlp systems (humeval) @ Irecoling 2024* (pp. 36–46). Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.humeval-1.4/>
- Nikolić, M. (Ed.). (2011). *Rečnik srpskog jezika*. Matica srpska.
- Ribeiro, M. T., Singh, S., & Guestrin, C. (2016). "Why should i trust you?": Explaining the predictions of any classifier. In *Proceedings of the 22nd acm sigkdd international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining* (p. 1135–1144). New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939778> doi: 10.1145/2939672.2939778
- Rönqvist, S., Kyröläinen, A.-J., Myntti, A., Ginter, F., & Laipala, V. (2022, May). Explaining classes through stable word attributions. In S. Muresan, P. Nakov, & A. Villavicencio (Eds.), *Findings of the association for computational linguistics: Acl 2022* (pp. 1063–1074). Dublin, Ireland: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.findings-acl.85/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2022.findings-acl.85
- Rupnik, P., Kuzman, T., & Ljubešić, N. (2023, May). BENCHiC-lang: A benchmark for discriminating between Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian. In Y. Scherrer, T. Jauhiainen, N. Ljubešić, P. Nakov, J. Tiedemann, & M. Zampieri (Eds.), *Tenth workshop on nlp for similar languages, varieties and dialects (vardial 2023)* (pp. 113–120). Dubrovnik, Croatia: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.vardial-1.11/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2023.vardial-1.11
- Sundararajan, M., Taly, A., & Yan, Q. (2017, 06–11 Aug). Axiomatic attribution for deep networks. In D. Precup & Y. W. Teh (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 34th international conference on machine learning* (Vol. 70, pp. 3319–3328). PMLR. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v70/sundararajan17a.html>
- Xie, R., Ahia, O., Tsvetkov, Y., & Anastasopoulos, A. (2024, February). Extracting lexical features from dialects via interpretable dialect classifiers. *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference of the North American Chapter of the As-*

sociation for Computational Linguistics: *Human Language Technologies (Volume 2: Short Papers)*, 54–69. (arXiv:2402.17914 [cs]) doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.naacl-short.5

- Zampieri, M., Malmasi, S., Ljubešić, N., Nakov, P., Ali, A., Tiedemann, J., ... Aepli, N. (2017, April). Findings of the VarDial evaluation campaign 2017. In P. Nakov, M. Zampieri, N. Ljubešić, J. Tiedemann, S. Malmasi, & A. Ali (Eds.), *Proceedings of the fourth workshop on NLP for similar languages, varieties and dialects (VarDial)* (pp. 1–15). Valencia, Spain: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/W17-1201/> doi: 10.18653/v1/W17-1201
- Zampieri, M., Tan, L., Ljubešić, N., & Tiedemann, J. (2014, August). A report on the DSL shared task 2014. In M. Zampieri, L. Tan, N. Ljubešić, & J. Tiedemann (Eds.), *Proceedings of the first workshop on applying NLP tools to similar languages, varieties and dialects* (pp. 58–67). Dublin, Ireland: Association for Computational Linguistics and Dublin City University. <https://aclanthology.org/W14-5307/> doi: 10.3115/v1/W14-5307
- Zampieri, M., Tan, L., Ljubešić, N., Tiedemann, J., & Nakov, P. (2015, September). Overview of the DSL shared task 2015. In P. Nakov et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the joint workshop on language technology for closely related languages, varieties and dialects* (pp. 1–9). Hissar, Bulgaria: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/W15-5401/>

A MULTILABEL INSTANCES IN DEV AND TEST SETS

Table 6: Overview of multilabel instances in *dev* and *test* set. BS: Bosnian, HR: Croatian, MN: Montenegrin, SR: Serbian.

Classes	Dev	Test
BS, HR	1,473	500
BS, HR, MN	0	51
BS, HR, MN, SR	119	0
BS, MN	1,128	2,029
BS, MN, SR	0	1,928
BS, SR	1,247	188
HR, SR	1,583	451
MN, SR	2,161	552
Total	7,711	5,699
% of set	21,2	13,9

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

ACOUSTIC TRENDS ACROSS SENTIMENT-LABELLED SPEECH IN THE CROATIAN PARLIAMENT

Ivan PORUPSKI¹, Nikola LJUBEŠIĆ^{1, 2, 3}

¹Jožef Stefan Institute

²University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Computer and Information Science

³Institute for Contemporary History

This paper presents an investigation of acoustic features and their relation to sentiment in Croatian parliamentary speeches. While most sentiment analysis research focuses on the sentiment prediction task and its evaluation, we examine the underlying relationships between acoustic characteristics and the expression of sentiment in formal political discourse. Using a large corpus of Croatian parliamentary recordings, we employ speaker-level averaging and paired testing, as well as text-based ground truth labeling to ensure acoustic features do not influence the sentiment classification. Our analysis reveals distinct acoustic patterns between positive and negative sentiment, with fundamental frequency (F0) demonstrating the strongest association, followed by intensity. Both features show increased values in association with negative sentiment compared to positive. Likewise, in the temporal domain, the syllable-based speech rate measure that excludes pauses showed a moderately strong effect, indicating slightly faster speech in negative sentiment. Higher F2 and F3 formants show modest associations with positive sentiment, potentially reflecting vocabulary differences. These preliminary findings contribute to the theoretical understanding of acoustic correlates of sentiment in formal speech contexts and establish a methodological framework for future cross-linguistic studies in various Slavic languages.

Keywords: sentiment analysis, acoustic features, parliamentary speech, Croatian language, low-level descriptors

1 OVERVIEW

1.1 Introduction

Sentiment analysis, the computational study of emotional tone and attitudes in communication, has evolved from simple lexicon-based approaches to sophisticated machine learning models. While text-based sentiment analysis has received extensive attention, the acoustic dimensions of emotional expression in speech remain underexplored.

Sentiment in speech manifests through acoustic properties including prosodic features (pitch, rhythm, stress), temporal characteristics (speech rate, pauses), and voice quality measures (jitter, shimmer). However, acoustic feature research has primarily focused on prediction tasks rather than understanding the underlying relationships between specific features and emotional expression.

Parliamentary speech represents a unique corpus characterized by formal register, political content, and structured discourse patterns. Political communication often involves strong emotional expressions within institutional constraints, making it an ideal domain for investigating acoustic-sentiment relationships and addressing the fundamental gap in our understanding of how sentiment is acoustically expressed in formal political discourse.

In this paper, we present the first systematic investigation of acoustic features and sentiment in Croatian parliamentary speech. Using speaker-level analysis and text-based ground truth labeling, we identify distinct acoustic patterns associated with positive and negative sentiment, with F0 and intensity emerging as the most influential features.

1.2 Related Work

Researchers concentrated on deriving information directly from the speech signal by separately analyzing prosodic, spectral, cepstral, temporal and voice quality dimensions in order to investigate their relationship to sentiment (Rong et al., 2009; Hassan, 2012; Mairesse et al., 2012; Zovato et al., 2019; Kamiloglu et al., 2020).

Prosodic features are the most commonly used set of features. These include the fundamental frequency (F0 or pitch) and its various derivatives (such as mean, range, variability, and contour shape). Contradictorily, Charfuelan and Schröder (2012) claim that there is no correlation at all between F0 contour features and sentiment, while Mairesse et al. (2012) found that negative sentiment is associated with flatter pitch (smaller range and lower variability), while positive sentiment is associated with steep pitch drops. The authors also show that 40% of relevant prosodic cues occur in the last 5 seconds of speech. Kamiloglu et al. (2020)

state that speech with positive sentiment has a higher and more variable F0. In addition to pitch, intensity measures—such as energy and loudness contours—may play an important role by capturing how forcefully a message is delivered, influencing the sentiment. Kamiloğlu et al. (2020) find that happy voices are generally louder with considerable variability in loudness.

Spectral and cepstral features constitute another critical category. Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) are widely used to represent the short-term spectral shape of speech. Their effectiveness in emotion recognition stems from their ability to capture subtle changes in the vocal tract configuration, which are altered by emotional state. While MFCC features are commonly employed in modeling speech for sentiment prediction purposes, their use for understanding the relationship between sentiment and acoustics remains very limited. Additionally, formant frequencies (especially F1 and F2) and other spectral descriptors such as spectral centroid, spectral slope, spectral tilt and energy distribution across frequency bands provide further detail about the voice’s timbre and resonant characteristics that may change with sentiment (Hassan, 2012).

Voice quality features add yet another layer of information. Parameters like jitter (cycle to cycle variations in F0), shimmer (cycle to cycle variations in energy), and harmonic-to-noise ratio (HNR) quantify micro-prosodic fluctuations in pitch and amplitude, reflecting the stability or irregularity of vocal fold vibrations (Varošanec-Škarić, 2005; Hassan, 2012). Jitter and glottal flow (reflected in measures such as spectral tilt and, by extension, shimmer) are suggested to trend positively with negative emotions (Ozdaz et al., 2004).

Duration-related (temporal) features may also be a factor in sentiment expression. These features, which include speech rate and the lengths of phonetic segments, capture temporal aspects of speech that may be modulated by emotional state (Hassan, 2012).

Such features are considered to be Low Level Descriptors (LLDs) of acoustic signals, as they only describe speech at the signal level.

While the aforementioned features have been extensively studied, most research in this domain has focused on acoustic-lexical fusion approaches rather than exploring the direct relationship between acoustic features and sentiment. Rozgić et al. (2012) and Kaushik et al. (2013) share the same approach of fusing acoustic features with lexical features extracted from automatic speech recognition (ASR) output to interpret emotion and sentiment respectively. Acoustic features include the segmental MFCC as well as low-level feature descriptors. Similarly, Pérez-Rosas et al. (2013) ex-

Average Fundamental Frequency (F0) by Sentiment (Praat)

Figure 1: Average population trend change of F0 by sentiment.

plore sentiment identification with the joint use of acoustic and linguistic, as well as visual modalities. For the acoustic modality, they chose to extract prosodic and spectral (MFCC) features, along with voice probabilities that represent an estimate of the percentage of voiced and unvoiced energy in the speech. They report an accuracy on the utterance-level of about 71% (linguistic modality) and 65% (acoustic modality), while combining the two yielded about 73% accuracy.

Li et al. (2019) explore sentiment analysis in customer service calls, applying the OpenSMILE toolkit (Eyben et al., 2010) on the utterance level to extract 988 acoustical features, notably intensity, loudness, F0 and MFCCs. For each feature, they compute functionals such as min/max value, mean, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness. The authors conclude how both acoustic-prosodic and lexical modeling is required for best results. They also note how lexical cues outperform acoustic cues for positive sentiment, while the reverse is true for negative sentiment.

A common limitation across these studies is that many authors extract features specifically for automatic classification, meaning no trends between acoustical features and sentiment were explored (Hassan, 2012; Charfuelan & Schröder, 2012; Bertero et al., 2016; Zovato et al., 2019). In many of these studies, the raw features are further encapsulated through statistical aggregations (mean values, standard deviations, ranges, percentiles, slopes, and regression coefficients) over entire utterances or dialogue turns. This statistical framing of the acoustical data enhances the robustness of the

correlations between these explicit measures and perceived sentiment without requiring modern neural network architectures.

However, the robustness of acoustic-sentiment correlations remains questionable. LLDs usually process an acoustic signal with frames that range from 20ms to 40ms, where the statistical properties of the signal are considered to be stationary. Yet, an experiment on sentiment detection shows that acoustic representations, particularly low-level descriptors (LLDs), do not perform well in classifying sentiment values for expressions across different noisy environments and spontaneous speech, at least within the CMU-MOSEI dataset (Samir, 2023). This suggests that there are no robust acoustical correlates to sentiment, especially in naturalistic speech.

Despite these challenges, the potential for acoustic features to capture sentiment-related information remains an open question, particularly in domain-specific contexts such as parliamentary speech, where the formal register and structured speaking patterns may yield more consistent acoustic-sentiment relationships than found in general conversational speech.

2 CONTRIBUTION AND HYPOTHESES

This paper presents an exploration of the relationship between acoustic features and semantic sentiment in parliamentary speech. To our knowledge, this is the first study to investigate such trends and associations in this domain. It is also the first study of this kind focused on the Croatian language.

While most related work in speech sentiment analysis is oriented toward optimizing prediction performance—including both classical feature-based approaches and modern end-to-end deep learning methods—our study takes a fundamentally different approach. Rather than treating acoustic features as means to an end for classification, we investigate them as the primary object of study to understand what acoustic differences exist between sentiment categories and how they manifest in formal political discourse.

Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

1. Methodologically clean sentiment labels: Our sentiment response variable, although automatically assigned, is based on predictions on text transcripts only, ensuring that acoustic features could not have been taken into account in the sentiment annotation process. This separation is critical for establishing genuine acoustic-sentiment associations.
2. Robust statistical framework: We perform our analysis on a large data collection, perform-

ing speaker-level averaging and paired testing, thereby controlling for individual speaker variation and reducing noise from automatic labeling.

3. Replicable framework: While we perform our analysis on a Croatian dataset, the methodological framework that we set up here will allow for comparable analysis of other ParlaSpeech datasets, currently available also in Serbian, Czech and Polish, enabling future cross-linguistic studies.
4. Complementary to prediction research: Unlike end-to-end approaches optimized for classification accuracy, our explicit feature analysis provides interpretable insights into the acoustic structure of sentiment expression, contributing to theoretical understanding rather than system performance.

Our work is deliberately exploratory rather than predictive. We acknowledge that end-to-end models may achieve superior classification performance, but they cannot reveal which acoustic dimensions—pitch, intensity, speech rate, voice quality—systematically vary with sentiment. Our findings establish acoustic baselines that can inform future work in cross-linguistic sentiment analysis, speaker verification under emotional variation, and theoretical models of prosodic affect signaling.

Given the aforementioned considerations, we attempt to find acoustical trends, specifically LLDs, that may describe notable differences between positive and negative sentiment in speech. To do so, we make the following hypotheses:

- **H1:** Positive and negative sentiment utterances exhibit distinct acoustic (prosodic, spectral, voice quality and temporal) features.
- **H2:** Acoustic features differ between male and female speakers across sentiment categories.

With this, we set up our research primarily as an exploratory study with the aim of developing more nuanced questions in the next iterations of our research.

3 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset

The ParlaSent model¹ (Mochtak et al., 2023) was used to infer the sentiment of the Croatian Parliamentary proceedings, specifically the ParlaSpeechHR-v3² enriched speech corpus. It is important to note that the corpus is representative of only parliamentary speech, in other words, public speech of professional speakers in political discourse.

¹<https://huggingface.co/classla/xlm-r-parlasent>

²<https://clarinsi.github.io/parlaspeech/>

3.2 Data Filtering

While the ParlaSpeech corpus is extensive, some filtering is required. All entries (utterances) lacking sentiment, Kaldi forced alignment and/or speaker information are dropped.

Only utterances which have a "Positive" or "Negative" value in the six-level sentiment schema are kept. With this we drop any entry from the middle of the sentiment spectrum, as this represents a first insight in the phenomenon of interest. This filtering reduces the full dataset of around 922k to about 306k entries.

Furthermore, all utterances shorter than 10 words and longer than 40 words are also removed. This filtration step is deemed necessary due to possibly erroneous sentiment labels in extremely short and extremely long utterances. This reduces the dataset to about 200k entries.

Finally, for pair-wise testing, all speakers that have less than 50 utterances in both positive and negative sentiment are removed. This reduces the number of speakers from 481 to 208, and the dataset to 137k entries.

The final distribution of utterances by sentiment and gender can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Eligible Speakers and Sentiment Samples by Gender

Gender	# Spkrs	Pos	Neg
Male (M)	149	31,868	105,844
Female (F)	59	11,925	31,166
Total	208	43,793	137,010

3.3 Investigated Features

Based on findings from previous research, we extract a comprehensive set of prosodic, spectral, voice quality and temporal features. Feature extraction is performed using three complementary tools: Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2001) and OpenSMILE's feature extractors GeMAPS (Eyben et al., 2015) and ComParE 2016 (Schuller et al., 2016). To ensure robust feature representation, all features are initially computed at the word level (words_align for HR and RS, words for CZ and PL) by calculating the median of non-zero values, which are subsequently averaged across the entire utterance to produce a single representative value per feature.

Prosodic: Pitch (F0) is measured in Hertz (Hz) and intensity in decibels (dB).

Spectral: The first three formants (F1, F2, F3) in Hz.

Voice quality: Jitter is measured as local jitter (cycle-to-cycle pitch variation, in %), and as smoothed jitter over 3 cycles (rap, in %). Shimmer is expressed both as local shimmer (cycle-to-cycle amplitude varia-

tion, in %) and in decibels (dB), with averaged shimmer (apq11) capturing smoothed variation over 11 cycles (in %). Harmonic-to-noise ratio (HNR) reflects the ratio of periodic to noise energy in the voice.

Temporal: Speech rate is expressed as the number of syllables per total duration, or syllables per duration excluding pauses (np). Word-based rate measures were considered as well, but were finally removed from the study due to reasons discussed in the results section.

Feature units vary slightly depending on the extraction tool. In GeMAPS, F0 is returned in semitones rather than Hz. In ComParE, intensity is reported as root mean square (RMS) energy without explicit units, and jitter and shimmer are expressed in seconds rather than percentages.

For the speech rate, the number of syllables is defined as the number of vowels /a, e, i, o, u/, including syllabic /r/ where valid.

3.4 Statistical methodology

To assess statistical significance, non-parametric tests from the Python scipy.stats (Virtanen et al., 2020) library are used.

Mann-Whitney's U Test is deployed on Population and Gender to check whether there's a statistically significant difference in the selected acoustic feature between utterances of positive and negative sentiment. To check for effect size, the Mann-Whitney U statistic is converted to the Rank-Biserial Correlation (RBC). A positive value correlates the acoustic feature to positive sentiment, while a negative value to negative sentiment.

However, since a varying amount of utterances belong to individual speakers, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test and its RBC are deployed on Paired-Speaker. Each speaker's positive and negative utterances are first averaged separately. The paired averages are then compared to see whether individual speakers consistently change their acoustic features when expressing different sentiments. This controls for individual speaker differences and tests if the same person sounds different in positive versus negative sentiment.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our findings reveal distinct acoustic patterns between positive and negative sentiment in Croatian parliamentary speech as shown in Table 2. The speaker-level averaging approach demonstrates stronger associations between specific acoustic variables and sentiment, providing a legitimate view for understanding underlying relationships. While this methodology would not be feasible for practical prediction purposes, it effectively illumi-

Table 2: Nonparametric test results for prosodic and temporal features across population-level sentiment, paired speaker sentiment, and population-level gender.

Feature	Population Sentiment			Paired Sentiment			Population Gender			
	p-value	RBC	P(Pos>Neg) OR	p-value	RBC	P(Pos>Neg) OR	p-value	RBC	P(M>F) OR	
Prosodic and Voice Quality Features (Praat)										
F0_avg	0.0000	0.158	0.4212	0.7276	-0.994	0.0385	0.0400	0.880	0.0600	0.0638
Intens_avg	0.0000	0.074	0.4630	0.8624	-0.574	0.2644	0.3595	0.304	0.3480	0.5336
<i>F1_avg</i>	0.0000	0.058	0.4709	0.8898	-0.393	0.3317	0.4964	0.221	0.3894	0.6379
<i>F2_avg</i>	0.0000	-0.055	0.5273	1.1155	0.257	0.5817	1.3908	0.053	0.4733	0.8986
<i>F3_avg</i>	0.0000	-0.080	0.5402	1.1750	0.287	0.5913	1.4471	0.222	0.3890	0.6366
Jitter_local	0.0000	0.071	0.4645	0.8673	-0.536	0.2885	0.4054	-0.347	0.6736	2.0637
<i>Jitter_rap</i>	0.1333	-0.004	0.5022	1.0089	-0.111	0.4327	0.7627	0.089	0.4555	0.8364
<i>Shimmer_local</i>	0.0000	-0.014	0.5071	1.0289	0.115	0.5385	1.1667	-0.468	0.7339	2.7582
<i>Shimmer_local_db</i>	0.0012	-0.010	0.5048	1.0195	0.073	0.5288	1.1224	-0.242	0.6209	1.6380
<i>Shimmer_apq11</i>	0.0000	-0.033	0.5166	1.0688	0.307	0.6202	1.6329	-0.376	0.6879	2.2042
<i>HNR_avg</i>	0.6856	-0.001	0.5006	1.0024	-0.216	0.3750	0.6000	0.338	0.3311	0.4951
Prosodic and Voice Quality Features (OpenSMILE - GeMAPS)										
F0_avg	0.0000	0.141	0.4295	0.7529	-0.992	0.0337	0.0348	0.886	0.0571	0.0606
Intens_avg	0.0000	0.106	0.4469	0.8081	-0.675	0.2404	0.3165	0.308	0.3458	0.5287
<i>F1_avg</i>	0.0000	0.032	0.4838	0.9371	0.063	0.5048	1.0194	-0.445	0.7226	2.6052
<i>F2_avg</i>	0.0000	0.023	0.4884	0.9548	-0.013	0.4712	0.8909	-0.439	0.7196	2.5660
<i>F3_avg</i>	0.3895	-0.003	0.5013	1.0051	0.177	0.5577	1.2609	-0.352	0.6761	2.0877
Jitter_local	0.0000	0.080	0.4602	0.8527	-0.631	0.2260	0.2919	-0.426	0.7128	2.4816
<i>Shimmer_local</i>	0.3045	-0.003	0.5015	1.0061	0.3627	0.6058	1.5366	-0.420	0.7098	2.4464
HNR	0.4276	0.002	0.4988	0.9953	-0.727	0.1923	0.2381	0.826	0.0872	0.0955
Prosodic and Voice Quality Features (OpenSMILE - ComParE_2016)										
F0_avg	0.0000	0.150	0.4249	0.7387	-0.994	0.0337	0.0348	0.874	0.0629	0.0671
Intens_avg	0.0000	0.079	0.4604	0.8532	-0.575	0.2885	0.4054	0.305	0.3473	0.5320
Jitter_local	0.0000	0.089	0.4553	0.8358	-0.657	0.2596	0.3506	-0.462	0.7311	2.7192
<i>Shimmer_local</i>	0.0063	-0.008	0.5041	1.0164	0.403	0.6635	1.9714	-0.447	0.7237	2.6191
HNR	0.0000	-0.083	0.5413	1.1802	0.0000	0.182	0.5577	0.562	0.2190	0.2804
Temporal Features										
<i>speech_rate_syll</i>	0.0006	-0.010	0.5051	1.0207	-0.175	0.4327	0.7627	0.014	0.4931	0.9728
<i>speech_rate_syll_np</i>	0.0000	0.021	0.4893	0.9583	-0.385	0.3365	0.5072	-0.084	0.5419	1.1828

Note: Population and Gender use Mann-Whitney's U-test, while Paired speakers use Wilcoxon Paired test. **P = Concordance Probability** (P = 0.5 means X = Y, P > 0.5 means X > Y). **OR = (Wilcoxon) Odds Ratio** (OR = 1 means X = Y, OR > 1 means X > Y). **RBC = Rank-Biserial Correlation** (effect size: small = 0.10, medium = 0.30, large > 0.50). Positive value corresponds with effect towards Positive (sentiment) or Male (gender).

nates the acoustic characteristics of sentiment in formal political discourse.

F0 (pitch) emerges as the strongest predictor of sentiment with the highest effect size (see Figure 1), followed by intensity, jitter and speech rate (see Appendix 5). This suggests that pitch variations play a crucial role in conveying emotional content in parliamentary speech.

Our results demonstrate consistency across all three feature extraction tools. Praat and OpenSMILE show comparable performance for pitch, intensity and jitter measurements. Jitter consistently correlates with negative sentiment, while increased shimmer is associated with positive sentiment, regardless of the extraction method. Even so, the voice quality features (jitter, shimmer and HNR) should be taken with some reserve, due to variations in recording conditions and other possible contributing noise.

The formant analysis reveals that higher F2 and F3 frequencies demonstrate modest associations with positive sentiment. A vowel frequency analysis shows that both male and female speakers in the corpus share the same vowel usage (/a/ 26.9%, /e/ 18.5%, /i/ 22.5%, /o/ 23.0% and /u/ 9.1%) across both sentiments, suggesting that the observed effects on F2 and F3 are probably due to acoustic sentiment trends, not lexicon trends. However, future work should control for both vowel and lexicon, and even articulation.

Our temporal feature analysis highlights the importance of discarding pauses when calculating speech rate. The syllable speech rate excluding pauses (silence) shows a higher effect size than the syllable speech rate including pauses. This opens up another temporal feature set around use of pause in speech, but we leave this direction for future work.

Word-based speech rate yielded even a large effect size, twice-as-high as the syllable-based one, and for the reason of this significant deviation, we performed additional investigations. In the end we identified the trend that speakers use shorter words on average in negative context, which increased word-based speech rate measures in negative contexts, and pumped up the speech rate effect size. Given this finding, we removed the word-based speech rate from our study due to the obvious lexicon-based confounder.

Future work should also investigate the impact of pauses and variation in speech rate, as our current analysis focuses on averaged measures only.

In the Appendix 5 we also plot gender-specific distributions. Most notably, while both male and female speakers had approximately the same F0 absolute value increase from positive to negative sentiment of about

11 Hz, the relative increase in F0 is 9.4% for men, but only 5.4% for women (Appendix Figure 2).

On the other hand, women show an on-average increase in intensity of 1.98 dB when communicating negative content, while for men this increase is of only 0.56 dB (Appendix Figure 3).

Another striking difference between genders can be observed in the speech rate, where men pronounce 1.2 syllables less per minute when communicating negative content, while women pronounce 10.2 syllables more per minute for the same sentiment. However, women tend to have a slightly slower average speech rate than men (Appendix Figure 5).

4.1 Limitations

Our ground truth sentiment labels rely on automatic sentiment classification of text transcripts, which may introduce classification errors. However, speaker-level averaging across 50+ utterances per sentiment category substantially mitigates the impact of individual misclassifications on our observed trends.

The focus on Croatian parliamentary speech limits direct generalizability to other languages and discourse contexts. However, our methodological framework is designed for cross-linguistic replication across the ParlaSpeech dataset collection (Croatian, Serbian, Czech, Polish).

Our exploratory approach prioritizes interpretability over prediction performance. We deliberately focus on explicit acoustic features rather than end-to-end learned representations, reflecting our research goal of understanding how sentiment is expressed acoustically rather than maximizing prediction metrics.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper presents a study of the dependence of prosodic, temporal and voice quality acoustic features on the semantic sentiment expressed in utterances of Croatian parliamentary debates. To the best of our knowledge, this study presents the first focused analysis of the sentiment phenomenon as most related studies explore these features just in the sentiment prediction task.

Our results show a series of interesting findings. First, the strongest factor shows to be F0. When averaged per speaker, it shows an extremely high effect size (RBC) of -0.994. This effect size shows that most of the 208 inspected speakers have a higher average pitch when communicating negative content than when communicating positive content. High effect sizes and same directions can be further observed for intensity and jitter.

Both male and female speakers share the same acoustic trends, albeit to varying degree.

While the findings may not significantly impact sentiment prediction performance, we consider them crucial for beginning to understand the relationship between acoustic features and sentiment in speech, a severely understudied area of research.

We consider this exploratory study to be just the first step in our explorations of sentiment in political communication, and speech in general.

REFERENCES

- Bertero, D., Siddique, F. B., Wu, C.-S., Wan, Y., Chan, R. H. Y., & Fung, P. (2016). Real-time speech emotion and sentiment recognition for interactive dialogue systems. In *Proceedings of the 2016 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing* (pp. 1042–1047).
- Boersma, P., & Weenink, D. (2001). Praat, a system for doing phonetics by computer. *Glott International*, 5(9/10), 341–345.
- Charfuelan, M., & Schröder, M. (2012). Correlation analysis of sentiment analysis scores and acoustic features in audiobook narratives. In *Proc. of the 4th international workshop on corpora for research on emotion sentiment & social signals (es3)* (Vol. 26, pp. 99–103).
- Eyben, F., Scherer, K. R., Schuller, B. W., Sundberg, J., André, E., Busso, C., ... others (2015). The geneva minimalistic acoustic parameter set (gemaps) for voice research and affective computing. *IEEE transactions on affective computing*, 7(2), 190–202.
- Eyben, F., Wöllmer, M., & Schuller, B. (2010). opensmile: the munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor. In *Proceedings of the 18th acm international conference on multimedia* (pp. 1459–1462).
- Hassan, A. (2012). *On automatic emotion classification using acoustic features*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Southampton.
- Kamiloğlu, R. G., Fischer, A. H., & Sauter, D. A. (2020). Good vibrations: A review of vocal expressions of positive emotions. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 27, 237–265.
- Kaushik, L., Sangwan, A., & Hansen, J. H. (2013). Sentiment extraction from natural audio streams. In *2013 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing* (pp. 8485–8489).
- Li, B., Dimitriadis, D., & Stolcke, A. (2019). Acoustic and lexical sentiment analysis for customer service calls. In *Icassp 2019-2019 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing (icassp)* (pp. 5876–5880).
- Mairesse, F., Polifroni, J., & Di Fabbrizio, G. (2012). Can prosody inform sentiment analysis? experiments on short spoken reviews. In *2012 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing (icassp)* (pp. 5093–5096).
- Mochtak, M., Rupnik, P., & Ljubešić, N. (2023, Sep). The parlament multilingual training dataset for sentiment identification in parliamentary proceedings. (arXiv:2309.09783). <http://arxiv.org/abs/2309.09783> (arXiv:2309.09783 [cs])
- Ozdas, A., Shiavi, R. G., Silverman, S. E., Silverman, M. K., & Wilkes, D. M. (2004). Investigation of vocal jitter and glottal flow spectrum as possible cues for depression and near-term suicidal risk. *IEEE transactions on Biomedical engineering*, 51(9), 1530–1540.
- Pérez-Rosas, V., Mihalcea, R., & Morency, L.-P. (2013). Utterance-level multimodal sentiment analysis. In *Proceedings of the 51st annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics (volume 1: Long papers)* (pp. 973–982).
- Rong, J., Li, G., & Chen, Y.-P. P. (2009). Acoustic feature selection for automatic emotion recognition from speech. *Information processing & management*, 45(3), 315–328.
- Rozgić, V., Ananthakrishnan, S., Saleem, S., Kumar, R., Vembu, A. N., & Prasad, R. (2012). Emotion recognition using acoustic and lexical features. In *Interspeech* (Vol. 2012, pp. 366–369).
- Samir, S. A. (2023). *Machine learning of emotional expressions in the wild from acoustic signals and text*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Université Grenoble Alpes [2020-....].
- Schuller, B., Steidl, S., Batliner, A., Hirschberg, J., Burgoon, J. K., Baird, A., ... Evanini, K. (2016). The interspeech 2016 computational paralinguistics challenge: deception, sincerity and native language.
- Varošanec-Škarić, G. (2005). *Timbar*. FF Press, Zagreb.
- Virtanen, P., Gommers, R., Oliphant, T. E., Haberland, M., Reddy, T., Cournapeau, D., ... SciPy 1.0 Contributors (2020). SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python. *Nature Methods*, 17, 261–272. doi: 10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2
- Zovato, E., Quinci, V., & Mairano, P. (2019). Modelling sentiment analysis scores and acoustic features of emotional speech with neural networks: A pilot study. *Audio Archives at the Crossroads of Speech Sciences, Digital Humanities and Digital Heritage. AISV*, 6, 407–416.

APPENDIX: POPULATION- AND SPEAKER-LEVEL PLOTS

Average Fundamental Frequency (F0) by Sentiment (Praat)

Average Fundamental Frequency (F0) by Sentiment and Gender (Praat)

Figure 2: Fundamental Frequency (F0) Average Analysis - Praat-based Extraction

- 1) **Change of F0 average in positive and negative Population Sentiment ($\Delta F0$):** Shows the distribution of F0 average changes across positive and negative sentiment conditions.
- 2) **Paired speaker analysis:** Displays n speakers with corresponding p-value and RBC (Rank-Biserial Correlation). The diagonal line indicates expected values, with data points representing averaged speakers who produced both positive and negative speech (n speakers total). Points are colored orange if the speaker is dominant in positive sentiment and blue if dominant in negative sentiment.
- 3) **Male (M) gender analysis:** Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for male speakers.
- 4) **Female (F) gender analysis:** Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for female speakers.

Average Intensity by Sentiment (Praat)

Average Intensity by Sentiment and Gender (Praat)

Figure 3: Intensity Average Analysis - Praat-based Extraction

- 1) Change of Intensity average in positive and negative Population Sentiment ($\Delta Intens$):** Shows the distribution of intensity average changes across positive and negative sentiment conditions.
- 2) Paired speaker analysis:** Displays n speakers with corresponding p-value and RBC (Rank-Biserial Correlation). The diagonal line indicates expected values, with data points representing averaged speakers who produced both positive and negative speech (n speakers total). Points are colored orange if the speaker is dominant in positive sentiment and blue if dominant in negative sentiment.
- 3) Male (M) gender analysis:** Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for male speakers.
- 4) Female (F) gender analysis:** Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for female speakers.

Local Jitter by Sentiment (Praat)

Local Jitter by Sentiment and Gender (Praat)

Figure 4: Jitter Average Analysis - Praat-based Extraction

Note: Mean of medians was used for statistical calculations, due to median of medians showing no change.

1) Change of Jitter average in positive and negative Population Sentiment (Δ Jitter): Shows the distribution of jitter average changes across positive and negative sentiment conditions.

2) Paired speaker analysis: Displays n speakers with corresponding p -value and RBC (Rank-Biserial Correlation). The diagonal line indicates expected values, with data points representing averaged speakers who produced both positive and negative speech (n speakers total). Points are colored orange if the speaker is dominant in positive sentiment and blue if dominant in negative sentiment.

3) Male (M) gender analysis: Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for male speakers.

4) Female (F) gender analysis: Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for female speakers.

Speech Rate (Syllable, Non-Paused) by Sentiment

Speech Rate (Syllable, Non-Paused) by Sentiment and Gender

Figure 5: Syllable Speech Rate (No Pause) Average Analysis - Praat-based Extraction

1) Change of Speech rate average in positive and negative Population Sentiment ($\Delta\text{Speech_rate}$): Shows the distribution of Speech rate average changes across positive and negative sentiment conditions.

2) Paired speaker analysis: Displays n speakers with corresponding p-value and RBC (Rank-Biserial Correlation). The diagonal line indicates expected values, with data points representing averaged speakers who produced both positive and negative speech (n speakers total). Points are colored orange if the speaker is dominant in positive sentiment and blue if dominant in negative sentiment.

3) Male (M) gender analysis: Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for male speakers.

4) Female (F) gender analysis: Shows the identical change of F0 average as in plot 1, but specifically for female speakers.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

GENDEREDNESS DICTATES THE CHOICE OF AGREEMENT WITH NUMERAL PHRASES IN SERBIAN

Stefan MILOSAVLJEVIĆ,¹ Jelena STOJKOVIĆ^{1, 2}

¹University of Graz

²Leipzig University

Building upon the findings of Milosavljević (2017) that semantic agreement is more frequent than previously reported with both finite and gendered predicates (participles or adjectives in copular constructions), we present a quantitative study on the role of predicate type in agreement with definite numeral phrases introduced by cardinal numerals in Serbian. Based on a sample of 731 examples drawn from the CLASSLA-web.sr corpus, we examine three types of predicates: non-gendered finite predicates, gendered participial predicates, and gendered adjectival predicates. Our results show that semantic agreement is more frequent with non-gendered finite predicates. We also examined differences in agreement patterns between gendered predicates involving participles and those involving adjectives. The results show that copular adjectival constructions are more likely to license semantic agreement compared to participial forms. We discuss these results in light of Milosavljević (2024), suggesting that the presence of a gendered predicate inhibits semantic agreement. Our results show that semantic agreement with numeral phrases is neither marginal nor extragrammatical, contrary to existing reports on agreement with numeral phrases in Slavic (e.g. Franks, 1995; Bošković, 2008, 2025). Since previous work in generative syntax on agreement with numeral phrases in Serbian (and Slavic) has focused almost exclusively on participial predicates, the observed difference between non-gendered and gendered predicates has significant implications for the nature of the features involved in agreement, particularly gender in contrast to number and person.

Keywords: subject-verb agreement, numeral phrases, grammatical gender, participles, finite predicates, Serbian

1 INTRODUCTION

Two possible patterns of subject-verb agreement are attested with numeral phrases in Serbian. Finite predicates may appear in either the third person singular or plural form (1), while participles may bear either neuter singular morphology or plural agreement matching the gender of the noun (2). In the present paper, these two agreement patterns are referred to as grammatical agreement (GAGR, singular) and semantic agreement (SAGR, plural), respectively.

(1) (Tih) pet devojaka trči /
those.GEN.PL five girl.GEN.F.PL run.3SG /
trče.
run.3PL

‘Those five girls are running.’

(2) (Tih) pet devojaka je
those.GEN.PL five girl.GEN.F.PL AUX.3SG
trčalo / su trčale.
run.PTCP.N.SG / AUX.3PL run.PTCP.F.PL

‘Those five girls were running.’

In Serbian numeral phrases, the noun following numerals like *pet* ‘five’ and higher invariably appears in the genitive plural form (also termed the ‘genitive of quantification’), as do any modifiers, like the demonstratives in (1)–(2), with the form syncretic across all genders. Be-

cause the noun is not in the nominative case and the numeral itself is arguably caseless, the availability of plural agreement is syntactically puzzling and is therefore often attributed to semantic factors.

A range of factors has been proposed to influence the appearance of SAGR with numeral phrases (cf. Corbett, 2006, 2010, 2023; Milosavljević, 2017, 2018a, 2018b, 2020 for overviews). These include animacy (animate subjects tend to prefer SAGR), agentivity (agentive subjects favor SAGR), word order (SAGR is more likely with preverbal subjects), individuation (more individuated subjects are prone to SAGR), numeral size (lower numerals more readily pattern with SAGR), verb type (SAGR is more compatible with finite predicates than with participles), and interpretation (distributive readings promote SAGR; see also Bosnić, 2016). This does not imply that SAGR is overall more frequent or acceptable than GAGR in the presence of these factors; rather, their presence increases the relative likelihood of SAGR compared to contexts from which they are absent.

Despite these observations, the dominant view in the literature on generative syntax is that GAGR is the default, or even the sole grammatical option. More specifically, GAGR is typically treated as a bona fide grammatical mechanism, whereas SAGR is often viewed as semantically driven and thus ‘extragrammatical’ (cf. Franks, 1994, 1995; Bošković, 2008, 2025; Šarić, 2014,

among others).¹ This perspective is sometimes supported by corpus data showing the relative infrequency of SAGR – for example, (Corbett, 2004) reports that SAGR accounts for only 7% of the cases in his study.

We challenge this view from a quantitative perspective, showing that SAGR is in fact predominant in certain configurations and just as syntactic as GAGR. In section 2, we present some recent research arguing in favor of SAGR as a syntactic process and sketch some additional factors relevant for the choice between SAGR and GAGR, leading to the hypotheses we test in the present paper. The methodology is presented in section 3. Section 4 presents the results of the present study, discussed in section 5. We conclude in section 6.

2 PREVIOUS APPROACHES AND EMERGING HYPOTHESES

In this section, we first present in more detail some approaches that treat SAGR with numeral phrases as purely semantic, extragrammatical, and marginal (subsection 2.1). We then turn to several recent approaches that analyze SAGR with numeral phrases as a syntactic process (subsection 2.2), and finally, we outline the key differences between finite predicates and participles as agreeing elements, which are often overlooked in discussions of agreement with NumPs in Slavic (subsection 2.3). In subsection 2.4, we formulate the hypotheses emerging from the observations presented in the preceding subsections.

2.1 Semantic agreement is *not* syntactic

Variable agreement with various types of quantified noun phrases (QNPs) has attracted a lot of attention in Slavic (and beyond), with the prevailing tenet being that grammatical (singular, cf. 3) agreement tends to dominate in formal registers and syntactically prominent positions. Semantic (plural in 3) agreement is reported as marginally present (Corbett, 2004), more acceptable in colloquial speech (Franks, 1995) or when the numeral phrase is topical (Bošković, 2008; Franks, 1994; Pesetsky, 1982; Bošković, 2006) or discourse-linked (Despić, 2011). As an illustration, we briefly discuss two influential approaches, from Franks and Bošković.

According to Franks (1994, 622) and Franks (1995, 116), GAGR (neuter singular) is “considered standard and far preferred by most speakers,” with SAGR (plural matching the gender of the noun) having the status of a “performance error”. Franks argues that GAGR reflects true syntactic agreement with the subject NP, whereas

the plural form instantiates “semantic agreement” with the cardinality of the head N (he marks it with a question mark in the examples provided). On his approach, the numeral phrase is an NP that receives the neuter singular value by default, due to the impossibility of the nominal features of the head noun to percolate to the maximal projection. This inhibition, in his view, arises from the inherent status of the genitive of quantification, which blocks percolation. As a result, SAGR cannot be derived by syntactic means and is instead available only as a marked “semantic” option (Franks, 1994, 1995).

A similar stance is taken by Bošković (2025), who reports that Serbo-Croatian “only fully allows the sg option” [= GAGR], with “the PL option being dispreferred”, though not entirely ruled out, possibly as a result of semantic agreement. On this account, only nominative subjects can induce SAGR, an option available in Russian but not in Serbo-Croatian. Therefore in the latter, numerals must be caseless, and SAGR (plural agreement, in his terminology) consequently cannot be syntactically licensed.

2.2 Semantic agreement is also syntactic

While interpretations of the variation between GAGR and SAGR outlined in the previous subsection ascribe the emergence of plural on the predicate with numeral phrases to the influence of semantics, there are numerous proposals that derive both options in Narrow Syntax, cf. Driemel and Stojković (2019); Wechsler and Zlatić (2000); Landau (2016); Danon (2013a, 2013b); Wechsler and Zlatić (2003); Milosavljević (2024), *inter alia*.

Viewing SAGR as marginal or extragrammatical is unwarranted, given that, at least in some structural configurations, SAGR emerges as the dominant pattern. For instance, based on quantitative data drawn from the Corpus of Contemporary Serbian (Vitas & Utvić, 2013), Milosavljević (2017, 2018a, 2018b) observes that definite/specific NumPs like those in (3), significantly favor SAGR. Specifically, with finite predicates, SAGR is even the dominant pattern, as shown in Table 1. This quantitative pattern illustrates how a corpus-based approach can help falsify claims based solely on individual intuitions: the fact that a syntactic/semantic environment in which SAGR is significantly preferred over GAGR exists may be taken to implicate that SAGR is neither marginal nor extragrammatical.

- (3) Tih / svih / pomenutih pet devojaka
 those all mentioned five girl.GEN.F.PL
 peva / pevaju.
 sing.3SG sing.3PL
 ‘Those / all / mentioned five girls are singing.’

¹To be fair, Bošković (2008) mentions three possibilities to analyze agreement with numeral phrases in Serbian, two with plural agreement as “semantic” and one where plural is a syntactic option. In Bošković (2025), only GAGR (singular) is treated as syntactic.

Table 1: Agreement patterns of finite predicates in Serbo-Croatian (corpus study; after Milosavljević, 2017)

<i>Agr Type</i>	<i>Def/Spec</i>	<i>-Def/Spec</i>
GAGR	66/186 (35%)	79/96 (82%)
SAGR	120/186 (65%)	17/96 (18%)

Table 1 shows that SAGR is predominant in definite/specific contexts, where it accounts for approximately two-thirds of the data. With indefinite and un-specific subject NumPs, by contrast, GAGR is highly preferred, covering more than 80%. When only examples with definite/specific but inanimate non-agentive subjects are considered, SAGR is still significantly more frequent, appearing in 65% (20/31) of cases.

Building on these data, Milosavljević (2024) argues that SAGR reflects a genuine syntactic process. It is argued that SAGR arises when numeral phrases are full DPs and undergo movement to the canonical subject position (Spec,IP). In contrast, GAGR emerges when such movement does not occur – either because the subject is a bare NumP (a “Small Nominal” without the D layer, in terms of Pereltsvaig, 2006) or a DP that remains in a lower position. In these cases, agreement is controlled by a null situational *pro*, which anchors the predicate to the utterance context.

There are two additional recent studies that treat SAGR as a genuine syntactic process. Driemel and Stojković (2019) propose the internal structure of NumPs like (4), in the spirit of Bošković (2008), where the functional head K assigns the genitive case to its complement i.e. NP (similarly to F in Bošković, 2008).

$$(4) \quad [_{KP} \text{QP} [_{K'} \text{K NP}]]$$

Unlike Franks (1995); Bošković (2025), both GAGR and SAGR are syntactic in this approach, with the agreement pattern depending on the relative order of operations \uparrow Agree \uparrow , \downarrow Agree \downarrow , Merge (and Move) on the K head. GAGR is the Default Agree:² when Merge applies first, both \uparrow Agree \uparrow and \downarrow Agree \downarrow succeed, leading to a clash. Another option for default to arise is the order in which both Agree operations are counter-fed by Merge. Both scenarios lead to failed agreement, repaired by insertion of default features (Preminger, 2014). SAGR is agreement with the noun, due to the order (5). Specifically, \uparrow Agree \uparrow is counter-fed by the late application of

²Bear in mind that for Driemel and Stojković (2019) n.sg on the participle can arise with higher numerals and other uninflecting quantifiers like *mnogo* ‘many’ from two scenarios: one is default insertion after failed agreement, while the other is successful agreement with the quantifier, presumably inherently n.sg. The motivation lies in the comparison with nominal or paucal quantifiers, confirmed to be grammatical with GAGR with the quantifier (singular or paucal), SAGR with the noun (plural), as well as default n.sg agreement.

Merge, which in turn feeds \downarrow Agree \downarrow with the features of N. The verb agrees with the KP (reflecting plural and the gender of the noun).

$$(5) \quad \uparrow \text{ Agree } \uparrow \gg \text{ Merge } \gg \downarrow \text{ Agree } \downarrow$$

Čulinović (2020) also treats both GAGR and SAGR, illustrated in (6), as syntactic.³ The internal structure of NumPs giving rise to GAGR is as in (7), where N-set in the sense of Kayne (2016), which is singular neuter, assigns the GenQ. NumPs that trigger SAGR have the structure as in (8), where ϕ assigns plural and feminine gender (Sauerland, 2004).

$$(6) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Pet} \text{ devojaka} \quad \text{je} \quad \text{zaradilo} \quad / \\ \text{five girl.GEN.F.PL AUX.3SG earn.PTCP.SG.N} / \\ \text{su} \quad \text{zaradile} \quad 20.000 \text{ dolara.} \\ \text{AUX.3PL earn.PTCP.PL.F 20,000 dollars} \\ \text{'Five girls earned 20,000 dollars.'} \end{array}$$

$$(7) \quad [_{N\text{-setP}} \text{NumP} [_{N\text{-set}'} \text{N-set} [_{DP} \dots]]]$$

$$(8) \quad [_{\phi P} [_{\phi'} \phi: \text{PL,F} [_{N\text{-setP}} \text{NumP} [_{N\text{-set}'} \text{N-set} [_{DP} \dots]]]]]$$

Milosavljević (2024)’s syntactic account considers only finite predicates, whereas other accounts only discuss complex forms with participles. However, the emerging empirical picture suggests that finite predicates and participles behave differently as agreeing patterns. These differences between agreeing items that do or do not include gendered forms, such as participles, lie at the center of our quantitative study.

2.3 Finite predicates vs. participles

Milosavljević (2017, 2018a) observes that in complex forms containing a participle, definiteness/specificity continues to play a significant role, albeit with a weaker effect than with non-gendered finite predicates. The contrast as in Table 2 emerges from the reported corpus study. As evident, SAGR with definite subjects is far more frequent than with indefinite subjects (34% vs. 6%). The portion of SAGR with definite NumPs with participial predicates is however significantly lower than SAGR with definite NumPs with non-gendered finite predicates (34% vs. 66%). Similar patterns emerge when only inanimate subjects are taken into account – 32% (6/19) of the examples are attested with SAGR with definite inanimate subjects. This suggests that while definiteness remains the key factor, the presence of a participle itself reduces the likelihood of SAGR with numeral phrases.

³According to (Čulinović, 2020), GAGR gives rise to only collective (five girls earned 20.000 dollars as a group), and SAGR to both collective and distributive interpretations (the latter: each girl in the set of five girls earned 20.000 dollars).

Table 2: SAGR with NumPs in present vs. past tense

<i>Semantic class of NumP</i>	<i>Present</i>	<i>Perfect</i>
Definite (+ modifier)	66% (N=91)	34% (N=86)
Definite (no modifier)	60% (N=30)	37% (N=27)
Epistemically specific	62% (N=13)	20% (N=35)
Non-definite/specific	18% (N=96)	6% (N=252)

Milosavljević (2024) suggests two possible factors that might influence these differences. The first one concerns the status of gender: this feature is only relevant for the agreement with participles and not with finite predicates. It might be inhibitory for SAGR as a ϕ -feature with the most opaque semantics, compared to person and number (Milosavljević, 2017, 2018a), at least for inanimate subjects (see section 5 for more).

From the perspective of how a sentence is anchored in discourse – either via a referential DP or a situation pronoun (recall from subsection 2.2 that, according to Milosavljević, 2024, SAGR with definite quantified numeral phrases is possible when they move to Spec,IP, thereby anchoring the sentence to the discourse) – it may also be the case that, with participial predicates, there is a higher probability for a sentence to be anchored via a situation pronoun. This seems especially plausible in the present-perfect interpretation of the past tense form in Serbian. At the very least, this suggests a hypothesis worth testing: namely, that present-tense situations are more likely to be anchored via individuals, whereas “past tense” situations are more likely to be anchored via situations.

2.4 Hypotheses

Milosavljević (2017)’s quantitative data on the prevalence of SAGR with finite predicates and the discrepancies between finite and participial predicates are based on data encompassing various semantic flavors, including both animate and inanimate subject phrases. As noted above, he reports that similar patterns are attested when only inanimates are considered, but this subset is based on very small samples: 31 examples with finite predicates and 19 with predicates involving participles. In the present paper, we test the following hypotheses using a more semantically unified class of examples and much larger samples. Specifically, as detailed in section 3, we focus exclusively on definite numeral phrases with inanimate subjects, drawing on a sample of 731 examples. The hypotheses are as follows:

- H1: With finite predicates, SAGR is more frequent than GAGR.
- H2: SAGR is more frequent with finite than with gendered predicates.

While Milosavljević (2017) focuses on gendered forms with participles, our quantitative study is concerned with two major forms including gendered agreeing items: complex verb forms with participles and copular constructions with adjectives. Since participial forms are always non-present-tense form (typically past tense or conditionals), copular constructions with adjectives may be about present tense situations. This enables us to confront gender on the agreeing pattern as one factor with the present (copular adjectival predicates) vs. non-present construal (participial constructions). Based on the observations laid out in subsection 2.3, we hypothesize the following:

- H3: SAGR is more frequent with gendered forms with present-tense construals (adjectival copular constructions) than with non-present-tense construal (participial constructions).

All three hypotheses have been confirmed by our quantitative study, as detailed in section 4. Before that, we describe our methodology in section 3. The results are subsequently discussed in section 5.

3 METHODOLOGY

Our quantitative data come from the dataset Milosavljević and Stojković (2025). This dataset comprises 731 examples extracted from CLASSLA-web.sr (Ljubešić et al., 2024), from the following genres: Forum, Information/Explanation, Instruction, Opinion/Argumentation, Promotion, and Prose/Lyrical. The dataset includes examples with definite numeral phrases, where the definiteness is signaled either by a demonstrative pronoun, or the universal quantifier *sav* ‘all’, marking maximality/exhaustivity. We extracted examples with neutral subject-verb order, with maximally two corpus words in between, and with numerals from *pet* (5) ‘five’ to *deset* (10) ‘ten’.⁴ Given the reported significance of word order and subject-verb distance for agreement (Milosavljević, 2017; Driemel & Stojković, 2019), the search queries were designed to minimize their influence; the queries also controlled for the format of numerals (verbal and numeric). The extracted examples are annotated for animacy by distinguishing the following five classes:

⁴The following queries were used for the extraction of examples: [tag!="S.*"] [word="ovih" | word="onih" | word="tih"] [lemma="pet" | lemma="deset" | lemma="šest" | lemma="sedam" | lemma="osam" | lemma="devet" | word="5" | word="10" | word="6" | word="7" | word="8" | word="9"] []{0,2} [tag="V.*"] for demonstratives and [tag!="S.*"] [word="svih"] [lemma="pet" | lemma="deset" | lemma="šest" | lemma="sedam" | lemma="osam" | lemma="devet" | word="5" | word="10" | word="6" | word="7" | word="8" | word="9"] []{0,2} [tag="V.*"] for *sav* ‘whole, all’.

- measure phrases, such as *tih 10% (+ N)* ‘these 10% (+ N)’, *onih 9km* ‘these 9km’, *tih pet minuta* ‘these five minutes’ etc.;
- inanimate entities, such as *ovih 10 stvari* ‘these 10 things’, *onih pet kašika* ‘these five spoons’, *ovih 5 faktora* ‘these 5 factors’ etc.;
- pseudoinanimate entities – entities that are inanimate in isolation, but stand for sentient and controlled actions (and thus metonymically for humans), such as *ovih 5 sudova* ‘these 5 courts’ (when the relevant courts make decisions i.e. denote institutions, not just buildings);
- animate entities that do not denote humans, such as *ovih pet mačića* ‘these five kittens’, *ovih devet golubova* ‘these nine pigeons’ etc.
- human entities, e.g. *tih deset ljudi* ‘these ten people’, *ovih pet igrača* ‘these five players’ etc.

In the present paper, we report the results of agreement with the second listed class. The first type of numeral subjects, which includes measure phrases, was not considered because these examples constitute a separate semantic class, which has been proposed in the literature to denote degrees rather than entities (see Matushansky & Ruys, 2014, 2015; Matushansky & Ionin, 2015; Milosavljević, 2024), and thus differs from typical inanimate *entities*. The last three classes all include either animate or pseudoinanimate entities, where the latter are effectively sentient and thus metonymically stand for animate referents; as such, they are closer to animate than to inanimate entities. The reason this study focuses on the inanimate nouns modified by the numerals lies in the fact that the animacy of numeral subjects is reportedly increasing the likelihood of semantic agreement (see Milosavljević, 2017 for an overview). By excluding all subjects remotely related to animacy, the study aims to reduce all factors that could contribute to higher numbers of SAGR in the dataset, based on the previous quantitative studies.

Two main classes of predicates were established: non-gendered finite predicates (9)–(14) and predicates containing a gendered form (15)–(20). The finite predicates were further subdivided into two types: typical verbal predicates with a finite main verb (9)–(10), and predicates with a finite copula. The copular predicates were then categorized as those with a nominal predicative (11)–(12) or those with an indeclinable predicative, a PP or an adverb (13)–(14). The gendered predicates were also subdivided into two types: those containing participial forms (15)–(16) and copular constructions with adjectival forms (17)–(20). Finally, the adjectival copular constructions were distinguished as having

either a participial copula (17)–(18) or a present-tense copula (19)–(20).

- (9) Proverite: *ovih 5 razlika* check these five difference.GEN.F.PL
otkrivaju istinu o vašoj ljubavnoj reveal.3PL truth about your love
vezi. relationship
 ‘Check: these 5 differences reveal the truth about your love relationship.’
- (10) *Svih tih šest zapisnika* all those.GEN.PL six record.GEN.M.PL
nalazi se u „Dosjeu Stepinac“. is.found REFL in file Stepinac
 ‘All those six records are found in the “Stepinac Dossier”.’
- (11) [...] *ovih 6 razloga* su pokazatelj these six reason.GEN.M.PL are indicator
da se to nikada neće desiti. COMP REFL that never NEG.will happen
 ‘[...] and these 6 reasons are an indicator that that this will never happen.’
- (12) [...] *ovih devet monitora* je samo these nine monitors.GEN.M.PL is only
jedan mali deo ponude domaćih one small part offer domestic
prodavaca hardvera [...] sellers hardware
 ‘[...] these nine monitors are just a small part of the offer from domestic hardware sellers [...]’
- (13) [...], *svih 10 studija* su na drugom all ten studios.GEN.M.PL are on second
i trećem spratu. and third floor
 ‘[...] all 10 studios are on the second and third floor.’
- (14) [...] *tih osam pesama* nije those eight songs.GEN.F.PL NEG.AUX.3SG
dosta [...] enough
 ‘[...] those eight songs are not enough [...]’
- (15) [...] *ovih sedam dokumenata* su these seven documents.GEN.M.PL AUX.3PL
postali osnova savremenog mita become.PTCP.M.PL basis modern myth
koji se i dalje širi which REFL still spreads
 ‘[...] these seven documents became the foundation of a modern myth that continues to spread’

- (16) [...] svih pet revolucija
all five revolutions.GEN.F.PL
doprinelo je produbljivanju
contribute.PTCP.N.SG AUX.3SG deepening
demokratskog iskustva.
democratic experience
'All five revolutions contributed to the deepening
of democratic experience.'
- (17) [...] svih 8 guma su
all eight tires.GEN.F.PL AUX.3PL
bile nove [...]
be.PTCP.F.PL new.F.PL
'[...] all eight tires were new [...]
- (18) [...] ovih sedam epizoda je
these seven episodes.GEN.F.PL AUX.3SG
bilo fantastično [...]
be.PTCP.N.SG fantastic.N.SG
'[...] these seven episodes were fantastic [...]
- (19) [...] tih pet planeta su
those five planets.GEN.F.PL AUX.3PL
poprilično velike [...]
quite big.F.PL
'[...] those five planets are quite big [...]
- (20) [...] ovih pet faktora je
these five factor.GEN.M.PL AUX.3SG
ključno za izbor pravog skladišta.
key.N.SG for choice right warehouse
'[...] these five factors are key for choosing the
right warehouse.'

To test the differences between the ratios of *SAGR* and *GAGR* across different categories (e.g. finite predicates vs. gendered predicates), we used the Chi-squared test for independence.

4 RESULTS

The results of our quantitative study are summarized in Table 3. The presented results confirm the three hypotheses formulated in subsection 2.4, now re-stated as quantitative patterns attested in the study:

- H1: With finite predicates, *SAGR* is more frequent than *GAGR* – 67.12% vs. 32.88% overall, and similar ratios also hold for all finite verb subcategories.
- H2: *SAGR* is more frequent with finite predicates than with verbs including gendered forms – 67.12% vs. 41.64% overall, and, as clear from Table 3, all subcategories of finite predicates are more frequent than any subcategory including a gendered predicate.

All relevant differences reported are statistically significant for the relevant comparisons ($p < 0.01$).

Among the examples with *SAGR*, four instances were attested in which the participles agree semantically in number, but the gender value on the participle does not match the one of the noun within the numeral phrase. Specifically, in three out of four such cases, the noun is feminine, but the participle takes the masculine form, as in (21). In one example, the noun is masculine, but the participle is (syncretic with) neuter. We discuss the theoretical implications of such "mismatches" in the next section.

- (21) A tih pet tačaka mogli
and those five point.GEN.F.PL can.PTCP.M.PL
bi da glase: [...]
be.COND COMP sound [...]
'And those five points could go as follows: [...]

- (22) On je pomogao da tokom naredne
he AUX helped COMP during next
godine, svih pet romana budu
year all five novel.GEN.M.PL be.3PL
objavljena za Amazon.
publish.PTCP.N.PL for Amazon
'He helped so that during the next year, all five
novels would be published through Amazon.'

5 DISCUSSION

The first important implication of our quantitative study is that *SAGR* with numeral phrases in Serbian is neither marginal nor "extragrammatical", as it accounts for approximately two-thirds of the examples with definite numeral phrases in finite predicate constructions. Even with gendered predicates, it has a significant share: more than 40% of examples. In the remainder of this section, we discuss the differences in the agreement patterns between finite and gendered predicates.

As stated above in subsection 2.3, two factors have been suggested in Milosavljević (2024) that might be responsible for the greater ratio of *SAGR* with finite predicates than with participles: gender and (non-)present-tense construals.

The *grammatical* gender feature is only relevant for the agreement of participles, but not for that of finite predicates. It may be inhibitory for subject agreement (*SAGR*) as a ϕ -feature with the most opaque semantics – compared to person and number (Milosavljević, 2017, 2018a) – or it may not be a ϕ -feature on D at all, but rather a grammatical feature on the noun or some lower (classifier) projection (Borer, 2005; Hachem, 2015; Arsenijević, 2017) (see Kramer, 2020 for a recent overview). Alternatively, it might not be a syntactic feature at all. Regarding the latter view, Arsenijević (2021), for instance, argues that gender is neither a syntactic nor

Table 3: Distribution of semantic vs. grammatical agreement by predicate type.

<i>Predicate type</i>	<i>N(Total)</i>	<i>SAgr</i>	<i>SAgr (%)</i>	<i>GAgr</i>	<i>GAgr (%)</i>
Finite predicates: all	438	294	67,12	144	32,88
• verbal predicates	351	232	66,10	119	33,90
• copular predicates with indeclinable predicatives	41	27	65,85	14	34,15
• copular predicates with nominal predicatives	46	35	76,09	11	23,91
Gendered predicates: all	293	122	41,64	171	58,36
• auxiliaries + participles	181	65	35,91	116	64,09
• auxiliaries + adjectival predicatives	112	57	50,59	55	49,11
• • participial auxiliaries + adjectival predicatives	25	8	32,00	17	68,00
• • non-participial auxiliaries + adjectival predicatives	87	49	56,32	38	43,68

a semantic feature, but instead derives from declension class and pragmatic markedness.

That gender-bearing forms such as participles possibly have a different controller has been argued in Milosavljević (2020), who considers cases where finite predicates (auxiliaries) agree in plural with NumP subjects, but participles do not match the gender feature of the noun. Two types of such examples are provided in (23) and (24). In both examples, the auxiliary is 3.PL. The participle is also plural, but its gender does not match the gender of the noun. In the former, the noun is neuter, and the participle takes the masculine gender. In the latter example, the situation is reversed: the noun is masculine, but the participle has the form characteristic of the neuter plural.

- (23) Ovih pet ostvarenja
 these five achievements.GEN.N.PL
 ispunili su uslove.
 fulfill.PTCP.M.PL AUX.3PL conditions
 ‘These five achievements have met the conditions.’

- (24) Pet radnika su
 five workers.GEN.M.PL AUX.3PL
 primila platu.
 receive.PTCP.N.PL salary
 ‘Five workers have received their salary.’

As presented in section 4, our dataset also attests four examples in which the gender on the participle does not match the gender on the noun within the numeral phrase. Related patterns of gender mismatches have been attested experimentally in Arsenijević and Mitić (2016) with coordinated subjects. Similarly, Corbett (1983) presents corpus data from Serbo-Croatian showing that two coordinated nouns of grammatical feminine gender may give rise to the masculine agreement on the participle. For Murphy and Puškar (2018), the root of this phenomenon lies in feature markedness – in a system where the & head is inherently plural and the acquired gender features are conflicting, masculine is cho-

sen by an optimality-theoretic impoverishment operation in the post-syntax, as the least marked gender value (Stankiewicz, 1986; Andrews, 1990; Arsenijević, 2017).

The idea that gender is a different controller of agreement than person and number is close in spirit to the distinction suggested in Wechsler (2011), where participles display concord (“classifier”) agreement, whereas finite predicates exhibit index (“pronominal”) agreement. The crucial role in agreement with finite predicates is performed by the person feature, which is pronominal in its essence. Milosavljević (2017, 2018a, 2018b, 2024) attributes the fact that definite NumPs favor SAgr with NumPs in finite forms to the person feature as a part of the bundle responsible for individuation of the referents, in terms of Matushansky and Ruys (2014, 2015); Matushansky and Ionin (2015). In this view, definite NumPs would favor SAgr in finite-verbs context because definiteness and person are a single category (Lyons, 1999; Stanković, 2016; Milosavljević, 2017, 2018a); cf. also Alexiadou et al. (2024) for a recent approach along these lines. Syntactically, this means that the person feature is on D and is interpretable there, as argued in Pereltsvaig (2006); Milosavljević (2024); Alexiadou et al. (2024).⁵ This renders D pronominal in its nature, in the sense that interpretable ϕ -features are inherently pronominal, as argued by Sauerland (2004).

The person feature has also been argued to be crucial for anchoring a sentence in discourse (Bianchi, 2003). Such anchoring by definite NumPs is a necessary condition for enabling SAgr, since only referential subjects can raise to IP to fulfill this anchoring function and thereby control agreement (Milosavljević, 2024). Namely, according to Hinterhölzl (2019, 2024b, 2024a), there are two possible ways to anchor a sentence: either via an individual or via a situation. SAgr emerges when there is a definite referential subject that performs

⁵While third person is often equated with the lack of person features (Benveniste, 1966; Den Dikken, 2019), the present analysis is in line with Ackema and Neeleman (2018); Grishin (2023).

the anchoring role. G_{AGR} emerges when the sentence is anchored via a situation (syntactically, *pro*). That is, the situation pronoun is the aboutness topic of the sentence (cf. also Erteschik-Shir, 1997; Basilico, 2003). The situation pronoun bears (what looks like) third-person singular by default, but this time, what looks like the third-person here is the absence of person. From this perspective, it may also be the case that in the past tense, or more generally, in complex forms including participles, there is a higher probability for a sentence to be anchored in context via situation, especially in the “present perfect” interpretation of the past tense form in Serbian. In the present tense, by contrast, there is a higher probability for a sentence to be anchored by an individual. This is also reflected in agreement patterns, that is, a higher probability of S_{AGR} with finite (present-tense) verbs than with verbs including participles.

In sum, participles are less likely to agree semantically due to their gender feature and their non-present-tense construal.

6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The presented quantitative investigation into agreement with quantified definite numeral phrases in Serbian – with a focus on inanimate nouns – confirms and extends the predictions of Milosavljević (2017). Based on a dataset of 731 examples from the CLASSLA-web.sr corpus, we find that semantic agreement is not only more frequent than grammatical agreement with finite predicates but also more likely with non-gendered finite verbal environments than with verbal environments involving gendered predicates like participles or adjectives in copular constructions. Furthermore, copular adjectival predicates exhibit a greater tendency toward semantic agreement than participial forms, supporting the arguments in Milosavljević (2024) that non-present (participial) forms inhibit semantic agreement, while present-tense contexts – including copular adjectival predicates – facilitate it, possibly due to the anchoring role of individuals vs. situations.

These findings challenge the received view in the existing literature (e.g. Franks, 1995; Bošković, 2008, 2025) that semantic agreement with quantified numeral phrases is marginal or extragrammatical. They also emphasize the importance of predicate type in licensing agreement patterns, suggesting a deeper divide in how features like gender (encoded in participles and adjectives) and person/number (typically active in finite predicates) interact with the agreement mechanism. Given that most prior generative analyses have centered on complex, gendered predicates, the clear contrast with finite forms revealed here opens new avenues for under-

standing the featural architecture underlying subject-verb agreement in Slavic.

7 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the three anonymous reviewers of ReLDI 2025, as well as the audiences at the ReLDI 2025 Conference (Palace of Science, Belgrade, September 25–26, 2025) and CLASSLA-Express 1.0 Plus: Corpora Meets AI (University of Graz, October 10, 2025) for their constructive criticism and valuable suggestions.

This research is funded in part by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF, Grant-DOI 10.55776/I6258). For the purpose of open access, the authors have applied a CC BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

REFERENCES

- Ackema, P., & Neeleman, A. (2018). *Features of Person: From the Inventory of Persons to Their Morphological Realization*. Cambridge, Massachusetts / London, England: The MIT Press.
- Alexiadou, A., Hein, J., Ilić, I., & Sauerland, U. (2024). The third person is present: An argument from determiners in generic statements. In *Proceedings of NELS 54* (pp. 1–14).
- Andrews, E. (Ed.). (1990). *Markedness Theory: the union of asymmetry and semiosis in language*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
- Arsenijević, B. (2017). Gender, like classifiers, specifies the type of partition: Evidence from Serbo-Croatian. *CLS*, 52, 21–37.
- Arsenijević, B. (2021). No Gender in ‘Gender Agreement’: On Declension Classes and Gender in Serbo-Croatian. *Balkanica et Slavia*, 1(1), 11–46. doi: 10.30687/BES/0/2021/01/001
- Arsenijević, B., & Mitić, I. (2016). On the number-gender (in)dependence in agreement with coordinated subjects. *Journal of Slavic Linguistics*, 24(1), 41–69.
- Basilico, D. (2003). The Topic of Small Clauses. *Linguistic Inquiry*, 34(1), 1–35. doi: 10.1162/002438903763255913
- Benveniste, E. (1966). Relationships of person in the verb. In *Problems in general linguistics* (pp. 195–204). Coral Gables: University of Miami Press.
- Bianchi, V. (2003). On finiteness as logophoric anchoring. In J. Guéron & L. Tasmowski (Eds.), *Temps et point de vue/tense and point of view* (pp. 213–246). Université Paris X.
- Borer, H. (2005). *In Name Only / Structuring Sense Vol. I*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. doi: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199263905.001.0001
- Bošković, Ž. (2006). Case and agreement with genitive of quantification in Russian. In C. Boeckx (Ed.), *Agreement systems* (pp. 99–121). Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins. doi: 10.1075/la.92.07bos
- Bošković, Ž. (2008). A minimalist account of Genitive of Quantification. In G. Zybatow, L. Szucsich, U. Junghanns, &

- R. Meyer (Eds.), *Formal description of Slavic languages. The 5th conference, Leipzig 2003* (pp. 270–287). New York: Peter Lang.
- Bošković, Ž. (2025). On (partially) quirky subjects, numeral subjects, and subject-oriented anaphor binding: Nominal and non-nominal subjects and their structural positions. *Linguistic Variation*, 1-29. doi: 10.1075/lv.24034.bos
- Bosnić, A. (2016). Distributivity and agreement mismatches in Serbian. In S. Halupka-Rešetar & S. Martínez-Ferreiro (Eds.), *Studies in language and mind* (pp. 77–101). Novi Sad: Faculty of Philosophy.
- Corbett, G. G. (1983). Slaganje predikata sa više subjekata u srpskohrvatskom jeziku. In *Naučni sastanak slavista u vukove dane: Referati i saopštenja* (Vol. 12, pp. 93–102).
- Corbett, G. G. (2004). *Number*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Corbett, G. G. (2006). *Agreement*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Corbett, G. G. (2010). Agreement in Slavic. *Glossos*(10), 1–61.
- Corbett, G. G. (2023). The Agreement Hierarchy and (generalized) semantic agreement. *Glossa: a journal of general linguistics*, 8(1), 1–39. doi: 10.16995/glossa.9164
- Čulinović, D. (2020). *Silence in a DP: A Classifier Analysis of Numerals in Serbo-Croatian (SC)*. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/54301571/Silence_in_a_DP_a_classifier_analysis_of_numerals_in_Serbo-Croatian-libre.pdf (Paper presented at FASL 26, Michigan Slavic Publications)
- Danon, G. (2013a). Agreement alternations with quantified nominals in Modern Hebrew. *Journal of Linguistics*, 49(1), 55–92. doi: 10.1017/S0022226712000333
- Danon, G. (2013b). Hebrew QNP agreement: towards an empirically based analysis. *Bucharest Working Papers in Linguistics*, 1, 5–23. doi: 10.1300/J123v53n01_15
- Den Dikken, M. (2019). The attractions of agreement: Why person is different. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10(APR), 1–18. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00978
- Despić, M. (2011). *Syntax in the absence of determiner phrase*. Ph.d. dissertation, University of Connecticut.
- Driemel, I., & Stojković, J. (2019). How to agree with a QNP. *Glossa: a journal of general linguistics*, 4(1), 1–32. doi: 10.5334/gjgl.584
- Erteschik-Shir, N. (1997). *The Dynamics of Focus Structure*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Franks, S. (1994). Parametric properties of numeral phrases in Slavic. *Natural Language & Linguistic Theory*, 12, 597–674. doi: 10.1007/bf00992929
- Franks, S. (1995). *Parameters of Slavic Morphosyntax*. New York / Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Grishin, P. (2023). Omnivorous third person agreement in Algonquian. *Glossa*, 8(1), 1–46. doi: 10.16995/glossa.8874
- Hachem, M. (2015). *Multifunctionality: The internal and external syntax of D- and W- Items in German and Dutch*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Utrecht University.
- Hinterhölzl, R. (2019, sep). Subjects, Topics, and Anchoring to the Context. *Syntax*, 22(2-3), 199–228. doi: 10.1111/synt.12179
- Hinterhölzl, R. (2024a). Complementizer Agreement and the Licensing of DPs: An Account in Terms of Referential Anchoring. *Languages*, 9(2), 1–12. doi: 10.3390/languages9020049
- Hinterhölzl, R. (2024b, dec). Giving content to expletive es in German. *Journal of Comparative Germanic Linguistics*, 27(1), 1–31. doi: 10.1007/S10828-023-09146-2/METRICS
- Kayne, R. S. (2016). *Some thoughts on one and two and other numerals*. (Manuscript. New York: New York University. URL <http://ling.auf.net/lingbuzz/002991>)
- Kramer, R. (2020). Grammatical Gender: A Close Look at Gender Assignment across Languages. *Annual Review of Linguistics*, 6, 45–66. doi: 10.1146/annurev-linguistics-011718-012450
- Landau, I. (2016). DP-internal semantic agreement: A configurational analysis. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory*, 34(3), 975–1020. doi: 10.1007/s11049-015-9319-3
- Ljubešić, N., Rupnik, P., & Kuzman, T. (2024). *Serbian web corpus CLASSLA-web.sr 1.0*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1931>. (ISSN 2820-4042)
- Lyons, C. (1999). *Definiteness*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Matushansky, O., & Ionin, T. (2015). *When cardinals agree (a catholic point of view)*. (Paper presented at the 48th Annual Meeting of the Societas Linguistica Europaea, September 2015, Leiden, Netherlands. HAL ID: halshs-01713832)
- Matushansky, O., & Ruys, E. (2014). 4000 Measure NPs: Another Pass Through the шлюз. In M. Szajbel-Keck, R. Burns, & D. Kavitskaya (Eds.), *Proceedings of fasl 23* (pp. 184–205). Ann Arbor, MI: Michigan Slavica Publishers.
- Matushansky, O., & Ruys, E. (2015). Measure for measure. In G. Zybatow et al. (Eds.), *Slavic grammar from a formal perspective: The 10th anniversary fasl conference* (pp. 317–330). Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang. doi: 10.1017/S0956618X00004774
- Milosavljević, S. (2017). *Kongruencija predikata sa subjektom iskazanim partitivnom brojnom sintagmom čiji je centar osnovni broj u savremenom srpskom jeziku*. MA thesis, University of Belgrade.
- Milosavljević, S. (2018a). Kongruencija glagolskog predikata sa subjekatskim sintagmama konstituisanim osnovnim brojem. *Zbornik Matice srpske za filologiju i lingvistiku*, LXI(2), 43–56.
- Milosavljević, S. (2018b). Kongruencija glagolskog predikata sa subjektom iskazanim partitivnom brojnom sintagmom čiji je centar osnovni broj u savremenom srpskom jeziku (istraživanje na testu prihvatljivosti). *Nasleđe*, 41, 63–79.
- Milosavljević, S. (2020). O odnosu muškog i srednjeg roda pri kongruenciji sa subjektom iskazanim brojnom sintag-

- mom u srpskom jeziku. *Philological Forum*, 6(2), 102–110.
- Milosavljević, S. (2024). *Finite verbs always agree syntactically with numeral phrases in Serbian: Evidence from definiteness/specificity*. (Paper presented at the 17th conference on Formal Description of Slavic Languages (FDSL-17), Masaryk University, Brno, November 20–22, 2024)
- Milosavljević, S., & Stojković, J. (2025). *Agreement with numeral phrases in Serbian*. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15697336
- Murphy, A., & Puškar, Z. (2018, nov). Closest conjunct agreement is an illusion. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory*, 36(4), 1207–1261. doi: 10.1007/S11049-017-9396-6/METRICS
- Pereltsvaig, A. (2006). Small Nominals. *Natural language & Linguistic Theory*, 24, 433–500. doi: 10.1007/s11049-005-3820-z
- Pesetsky, D. (1982). *Paths and Categories*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, MIT.
- Preminger, O. (2014). *Agreement and its failures* (Vol. 68). London, England: MIT Press.
- Šarić, A. (2014). *Numeral induced agreement mismatches in Serbo-Croatian*. Unpublished master's thesis, Utrecht University.
- Sauerland, U. (2004). *A Comprehensive Semantics for Agreement*. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=31c95b9abe9c790a076d2d2c88ed12108ee17304> (Paper presented at Phi-Workshop, McGill University, Montreal)
- Stankiewicz, E. (1986). *The Slavic Languages: Unity in Diversity*. De Gruyter. doi: 10.1515/9783110854978
- Stanković, B. (2016). DP u srpskom, jeziku bez člana. In B. Arsenijević & S. Halupka-Rešetar (Eds.), *Srpski jezik u savremenoj lingvističkoj teoriji* (pp. 101–121). Niš: Filozofski fakultet Univerziteta u Nišu.
- Vitas, D., & Utvić, M. (2013). *Korpus savremenog srpskog jezika (SrpKor), verzija SrpKor2013*. Grupa za jezičke tehnologije Univerziteta u Beogradu. <http://www.korpus.matf.bg.ac.rs/korpus>
- Wechsler, S. (2011). Mixed agreement, the person feature, and the index/concord distinction. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory*, 29(4), 999–1031. doi: 10.1007/s11049-011-9149-x
- Wechsler, S., & Zlatic, L. (2000). A theory of agreement and its application to Serbo-Croatian. *Language*, 76(4), 799–832.
- Wechsler, S., & Zlatic, L. (2003). *The many faces of agreement*. Stanford, CA: Centre for the Study of Language & Information.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

TORLAK THEME VOWELS IN THE VERBAL DOMAIN: A CORPUS-BASED STUDY

Stefan MILOSAVLJEVIĆ,¹ Marko SIMONOVIĆ,¹ Anđela BABIĆ,² Mirjana MIRIĆ,² Jelena STOJKOVIĆ^{1, 3}

¹University of Graz

²Institute for Balkan Studies, Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts

³Leipzig University

This paper presents the first quantitatively substantiated analysis of verbal morphology in Torlak, an understudied Western South Slavic and Balkan Slavic variety. While Torlak has a rich dialectological tradition, its verbal system remains underanalysed, with previous work largely limited to descriptive accounts. Building on data from the *Spoken Torlak Dialect Corpus 1.0* (Vuković, 2020), we develop a novel dataset of Torlak verbs annotated for both inflectional and derivational properties and compare the observed theme-vowel classes with those in standard BCMS, using the independently constructed *WeSoSlaV* database (Arsenijević et al., 2024a). Our results show that the Torlak system can be captured using the same set of theme-vowel classes as in standard BCMS, despite individual verbs occasionally shifting between classes. Additional corpus annotations reveal variation in the interaction between theme vowels and inflectional endings (present, aorist, imperfect), with Torlak showing a substantial amount of variation in some of the theme-vowel classes. Nonetheless, these differences do not warrant a reorganisation of the underlying TV class system. The study demonstrates how corpus-based methods can advance the analysis of underdescribed varieties and contribute to broader discussions of inflectional morphology in the South Slavic and Balkan Sprachbund contexts.

Keywords: verbs, theme vowels, inflection class, Torlak

1 INTRODUCTION

The focus of this paper is on the theme vowel (i.e. conjugation) classes in Torlak, an underinvestigated Western South Slavic and Balkan Slavic variety, encompassing the Prizren–Timok dialect area in Serbia and the adjacent, closely related dialects in western Bulgaria and the northern part of North Macedonia (Sobolev et al., 2023, 23). More precisely, we investigate theme vowels in the verbal domain of Torlak varieties spoken in the Timok Valley in southeastern Serbia.

This paper draws on data prepared within the project *What's in a Verb? Mapping Serbian Verbs Borrowed into Romani* (2024–2026), which investigates linguistic contact between the Prizren–Timok dialect of Serbian and the Gurbet variety of Romani spoken in southeastern Serbia. Focusing on verbs borrowed into Gurbet Romani (e.g. *radil/radisarda* < Serb. *radi* ‘work’), the project aims to uncover the internal structure of verbs in both language varieties, examining theme vowels, verbal affixes, and inflectional morphology. Through this analysis, the project seeks to provide a detailed understanding of these understudied linguistic systems.

The sociolinguistic context of Torlak highlights several challenges that influence linguistic research, as various extra-linguistic factors point to its endangerment. A substantial stigmatization of the “southern” dialect and its speakers has been reported in the literature (Šare & Stanković, 2011; Petrović, 2015; Vuković, 2024). This

extends to the younger generations of speakers in Serbia, who refrain from using the full range of dialectal features in their spoken language (Vuković et al., 2023).

Linguistic research on the Torlak varieties spoken in Serbia has a long-standing tradition (see Belić, 1905, among others). However, throughout the 20th century, Torlak was investigated primarily through the lens of traditional dialectology, with a detailed yet narrow focus on phonetic, lexical, and morphosyntactic descriptions of varieties spoken in particular villages or areas (see Ćirković et al., 2023 for a critical overview of the existing linguistic data on Torlak). Torlak has also been addressed in studies within Balkan linguistics (e.g. Mišeska Tomić, 2006), although the core of such studies typically centres on the most prominent Balkan linguistic features in specific varieties (e.g. see Vuković et al., 2022, 2023 for analyses of the postpositive article and analytical case marking in the Timok variety).

When it comes to the verbal system specifically, research on Torlak varieties has largely remained at the descriptive level. Previous dialectological studies are primarily limited to descriptions of inflectional morphology and tense formation (Sobolev et al., 2023 *inter alia*). Since most studies focus on specific varieties, their analyses will not be reviewed here. However, Belić’s study (1905) is noteworthy from the perspective of theme vowels for two reasons. First, it draws on data from various Torlak varieties spoken in Serbia, considering the

easternmost Timok–Lužnica dialect central. Second, it classifies verbs into five types (Serbian: *vrste*) and their subtypes (Serbian: *razredi*) based on numerous examples. Yet, Belić does not elaborate on the employed criteria and focuses on specific cases that diverge from the standard language and other dialects.

Apart from dialectological texts or isolated examples, Torlak has lacked modern, comprehensive linguistic resources until recently. Recent research has been significantly enriched by the development of various tools, such as dialectal datasets (Ljubešić et al., 2024) and an electronic corpus, *Spoken Torlak Dialect Corpus 1.0 (transcription)* (Vuković, 2020), allowing for more systematic and data-driven analysis of linguistic features and enhancing the visibility and relevance of Torlak (see also Vuković, 2021, 2024; Tang & Vuković, 2025, all focusing on the Timok data).

Building on these advances, our paper presents the first quantitative assessment of theme vowel classes in Torlak, moving beyond the traditional descriptive and dialectological approaches that have dominated previous work. Based on the data from the *Spoken Torlak Dialect Corpus 1.0 (transcription)* (Vuković, 2020), a new Torlak dataset was created, focusing on verbal inflectional and derivational properties, thereby enabling a more systematic and empirically grounded analysis of the Torlak verbal system. Also, by comparing the Torlak data to a parallel database of standard BCMS (Arsenijević et al., 2024a), we examine how theme vowel patterns align across the two systems. This comparative perspective allows us to demonstrate that, despite surface-level variation, the Torlak data can be accounted for using the same set of theme vowel classes established for BCMS.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 outlines the standard BCMS component of the *WeSoSlav* database, which serves as the methodological starting point for the Torlak annotations. In Section 3, we present the Torlak dataset, which consists of annotations of Torlak verbs extracted from Vuković (2020). Section 4 provides an overview of the distribution of theme vowel classes in the two samples and offers a preliminary comparison between the two distributions. In Section 5, we examine three morphological environments in which variation has been observed within theme vowel classes, asking whether the attested patterns warrant a reclassification of the theme vowel system. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 STANDARD BCMS DATASET: *WESOSLAV*

The morpho-phonological, derivational, and syntactic properties of standard BCMS verbal morphology have been compiled in the Annotated Database of the West-

ern South Slavic Verbal System (*WeSoSlav*; Arsenijević et al., 2024a; Marušič et al., 2022; Milosavljević et al., 2023; Arsenijević et al., 2024b). The database comprises 5,300 most frequent BCMS verbs and 3,000 most frequent Slovenian verbs, retrieved from the *srWaC*, *hrWaC*, *bsWaC*, and *meWaC* corpora for BCMS (Ljubešić & Klubička, 2014), and from *Gigafida*, the Slovenian national corpus, for Slovenian (Logar-Berginc et al., 2012). Each verb is annotated for a fixed set of over 40 different properties, including grammatical aspect, characteristic morphemes (the root, theme vowels, prefixes, suffixes) and their special properties (e.g. root allomorphy), lexical prosody, deverbal nominalizations etc. (Arsenijević et al., 2025).

In the remainder of this section, we outline aspects of the verbal domain in BCMS relevant for the Torlak database, as represented in *WeSoSlav*. We begin with the theme vowel classes (Section 2.1) and proceed to the annotation of derivational affixes (Section 2.2).

2.1 Theme vowels

For the purposes of the database, a theme vowel (TV) is taken to be a “syntactico-semantically empty formative”, the piece of morphology that follows the root and precedes the inflectional ending, traditionally considered as the determiner of the conjugation class (Oltra-Massuet, 1999, 2020), matched with the root based on semantic properties (Milosavljević & Arsenijević, 2022; Simonović & Mišmaš, 2022).

The exponents of theme vowels in BCMS can differ between different tenses, but generally two allomorphs are sufficient to capture the exponence of the theme vowel in the entire paradigm (i.e. describe the conjugation). For this reason, standard BCMS TV classes are represented as pairs of TV exponents: the first corresponds to the TV exponent in the infinitive, whereas the second is the TV exponent in the present tense. The TV classes implemented in the annotation in *WeSoSlav* for BCMS are summarised in Table 1.

As can be read off the overview, theme vowels typically have vocalic exponents. Excluding the bracketed segments,¹ the classes whose exponents involve consonantal material are: <a, je> and </, ne>. The PRS exponent of the <a, je> class is arguably floating, as it is generally realised as a palatalising element on the adjacent consonant (as seen in the example <plačemo> [platSemo] ‘cry.PRS.1PL’, which corresponds to the underlying /plak-je-mo/ in Table 1). In fact, it is only re-

¹The segments in round brackets in Table 1 are present in some regional variants: the Ekavian TV classes <e, i> and <e, e> have correspondents in Ijekavian <je, i> and <je, ije> and Ikavian <i, i> for both. Thus [e], [i], [je] and [ije] in these classes are all exponents of the *yat* phoneme – the more precise markers would be <ě, i> and <ě, ě>.

Table 1: Theme vowel classes in BCMS

TV class	Infinitive	Present.1PL	Gloss
a, a	pit-a-ti	pit-a-mo	‘ask’
i, i	vis-i-ti	vis-i-mo	‘hang’
a, je	plak-a-ti	plač-e-mo (/plak-je-mo/)	‘cry’
/, e	pas-∅-ti	pas-e-mo	‘graze’
u, e	gurn-u-ti	gurn-e-mo	‘push’
(j)e, i	gor-(j)e-ti	gor-i-mo	‘burn’
/, ne	sta-∅-ti	sta-ne-mo	‘stop’
a, i	struj-a-ti	struj-i-mo	‘flow’
a, e	(h)rv-a-ti	(h)rv-e-mo	‘wrestle’
(j)e, (ij)e	sm-(j)e-ti	sm-(ij)e-mo	‘be permitted’

alised as the segment [j] in the rare cases where the INF version introduces an additional segment [V]. This is illustrated, for example, with the forms of the verb <da-va-ti, da-je-mo> ‘give^{IPFV}’, which is the imperfective version of the verb <d-a-ti, d-a-mo> ‘give^{PFV}’.

The class </, ne> is exceptional, as it is the only TV class, along with the class <u, e>, which predominantly hosts perfective verbs. As argued in Štarkl et al. (2025), the class <u, e> (traditionally marked <nu/ne>) can be reanalysed as part of the class </, e>, where the [u] in the INF allomorph is considered part of the morpheme [n^u], associated with the perfective interpretation. A similar analysis, incorporating the class </, ne> into the class </, e>, is possible. An important advantage of such a reanalysis is that it would allow us to dispense with predominantly perfective and derived classes, as all seven TV classes in the revised system would contain morphologically simplex members, the overwhelming majority of which are imperfective. Even more importantly for our discussion, this revised system allows us to maintain that the realisational space for BCMS theme vowels is confined to a single vocalic slot.

2.2 Suffixes in *WeSoSlav*

WeSoSlav comprises multiple columns devoted to individual suffixes appearing in verbs. Three broad classes of suffixes were annotated in separate columns:

1. Verbal suffixes, including:

- secondary imperfectivisedrs consisting of more than just theme vowels;
- verbalisedrs used (also) in loanword integration, which consist of more than just theme vowels;
- other suffixes with a clear semantic contribution in the verbal domain (typically aspectual semantics, or diminution).

2. Multifunctional suffixes, also present in nominal and adjectival domains.

3. Suffix-like items and other ‘borderline’ morphemes.

We illustrate verbal suffixes using secondary imperfectivisers, which are among the most representative. Table 2 presents a common pattern found in Slavic languages: a verb triplet sharing the same root, ordered by increasing morphological complexity. The morphologically simplest verb is imperfective, the next one, with additional morphology, is perfective (often involving a prefix), and the most complex verb is a secondary imperfective, a suffixed version of the perfective verb. The suffix used to produce the secondary imperfective is termed secondary imperfectiviser (SI).

Table 2: Secondary imperfectivisation in BCMS

imperfective	perfective	sec. imperfective
čit-a-ti	iz-čit-a-ti	iz-čit-(a)-av-a-ti
read-TV-INF	out-read-TV-INF	out-read-TV-SI-TV-INF
‘read’	‘read out’	‘read out’

In *WeSoSlav*, suffixes that do not have a verbalising, aspectual or modifying function are annotated as multifunctional as they (a) arguably originate from a different category; (b) have a vague/opaque meaning (if any). A typical example is the suffix /-ar/ in Table 3.

Table 3: The multifunctional affix /-ar/

INF	1PL.PRS
krv- ar -i-ti	krv- ar -i-mo
blood-AR-TV-INF	blood-AR-TV-1PL
‘to bleed’	‘we bleed’

The suffix /-ar/ otherwise derives *nomina agentis*, like <slik-ar> ‘painter’ (cf. <slik-a> ‘painting-NOM.SG’ and <slik-a-ti, slik-a-mo> ‘paint’), but in the above example the base root + *ar* is not attested or interpretable.

Finally, the class of verbs annotated “Suffix-like items and other ‘borderline’ morphemes” contains verbs apparently following the structure (prefix+)root+TV, yet plausibly involving a more complex underlying morphology. Consider the illustration: the perfective verb <za-misl-i-ti> [PREF-think-TV-INF] ‘imagine’, has an imperfective counterpart <za-mišlj-a-ti> [PREF-think-TV-INF], which differs from the base verb both in its theme vowel and in the palatalised consonant cluster [ʃɫ] versus [sl]. As discussed in Simonović et al. (2023), these verbs arguably have a more complex underlying structure, e.g. /za-misl-i-a-ti/.

3 TORLAK DATASET

In this section, we present the Torlak dataset, containing verbs from Vuković (2020) that are annotated for inflectional and derivational properties. The dataset consists of a main component, in which the most common Torlak verbs are annotated for a set of inflectional and derivational features (discussed in Section 3.1), and three complementary datasets that target specific inflectional contexts (discussed in Section 3.2). The datasets, accompanied by a detailed description, have been published as Milosavljević et al. (2025).

3.1 The main dataset

The main dataset consists of 3,085 verbs extracted from the *Spoken Torlak Dialect Corpus 1.0* (Vuković, 2020).² As indicated in Vuković (2020), the corpus consists of semi-orthographic transcripts of 86.5 hours of recordings from locations evenly distributed throughout the Timok area of the Torlak dialect zone (see Vuković, 2021 for a detailed description of the corpus).

The procedure for obtaining the verbs was as follows. The 5,000 most frequent verbal lemmas were extracted from the corpus. Two native-speaker annotators (the first two authors of the dataset) first reviewed the full set to identify actual verbs and eliminate incorrectly marked entries resulting from typos, erroneous lemmatisations or similar issues. Following this procedure, the dataset comprises a total of 3,085 verbs. The resulting dataset was then annotated for the following properties:

- third person present tense form;
- active participle in the feminine singular form;
- theme vowel class;
- suffix (whether the verb contains a derivational suffix);
- root allomorphy (whether or not it is exhibited between the present tense and the participle form).

In annotating these properties, the instructions developed for the database *WeSoSlaV*, as described in Section 2 (for more details, see Arsenijević et al., 2024a; Arsenijević et al., 2025), were followed with some modifications. The following notes on the annotation procedure are in order.

INFLECTIONAL FORMS. The third person present tense forms and the participle forms are given as attested in the Torlak corpus. If these forms were not attested, they were reconstructed by the native speaker annotators. Since Torlak does not have an infinitive form and since no single form suffices to identify the conjugation pattern of the verb, in the remainder of the paper we use the combination of the participle and the third person

present tense to identify Torlak verbs. For example, for the original lemma *uzeti* ‘take’, based on the standard BCMS infinitive, we use <uze-l-a, uz-ne>.

THEME VOWEL CLASSES. Similar to *WeSoSlaV*, the TV classes identifying the conjugation pattern are annotated as pairs of TVs, where the first theme vowel originates from the participle as a non-finite form and the second from the present tense form.

ROOT ALLOMORPHY. Any unpredictable difference in the exponence of the root morpheme (i.e. the material preceding the TV) between the non-finite and finite form of the verb is defined as root allomorphy. This definition excludes instances of predictable phonologically conditioned allomorphy like <pis-a-l-a, piš-e> ‘write’. For instance, the verb <raz-ne-l-a, raz-nes-e> ‘blow up’ exhibits root allomorphy displayed by the contrast between [ne] and [nes].

SUFFIXES. The annotation in this column departs considerably from *WeSoSlaV*, where three classes of suffixes or suffix-like morphemes were annotated (see subsection 2.2). For the Torlak dataset, it was only annotated whether a verb contains a derivational suffix, assigning the value 1 if there is an overt suffix and 0 otherwise. While the line is necessarily somewhat arbitrary, the aim was to annotate as “containing derivational suffixes” only those verbs that exhibit overt suffixal material realised by dedicated segments. This means that verbs derived by ablaut (e.g. <s-klap-a-l-a, s-klap-a>, the secondary imperfective of <s-klop-i-l-a, s-klop-i> ‘put together’) or by consonant mutation (e.g. <iz-mišlj-a-l-a, iz-mišlj-a>, the secondary imperfective of <iz-misl-i-l-a, iz-misl-i> ‘make up’) were not counted as having derivational suffixes. Moreover, only affixes that are never part of the TV material were annotated as derivational. For this reason, the suffix /-n-/, which precedes the theme vowels <u, e> and may be analysed as part of a theme vowel in the TV class </, ne>, was not considered a derivational suffix. By contrast, the suffix /-k-/ in <na-sec-k-a-la, na-sec-k-a> ‘cut’ was treated as derivational, since it is never a part of a TV exponent.

In addition to these properties, the dataset contains information on the frequency of verb lemmas as retrieved from the *Spoken Torlak Dialect Corpus 1.0* (Vuković, 2020).

3.2 Complementary datasets

This subsection introduces the three additional datasets that were used to explore potential variation in the behaviour of different TV classes across finite-verb environments, specifically in the third person plural present tense, aorist, and imperfectum.

²The corpus was accessed at https://www.clarin.si/noske/run.cgi/corp_info?corpname=torkak.

3.2.1 PRESENT TENSE: THIRD PERSON PLURAL

Since the third person plural forms of the present tense have no formal properties in common, in order to obtain an initial sample, a regular expression was used that targeted some common plural subject forms followed by a verb. Specifically, the following query was employed: `[word="oni" | word="one" | word="ljudi" | word="žene" | word="deca" | word="déca" | word="oní" | word="oné" | word="žéne" | word="ljúdi"] [tag="V.*"]`, with both accentual variants as transcribed in Vuković (2020). From the resulting 692 concordances, those containing verbs in the PRS.3PL form were manually extracted, yielding a total of 323 verb tokens. These were then subjected to further annotation.

In addition to standard metadata columns (ID, corpus reference, left and right context, and KWIC), the dataset is annotated for the following properties:

- whether the concordance contains a PRS.3PL form,
- corresponding PTCP.F form,
- TV class,
- derivational relationship between the PRS.3PL and the respective PRS.3SG form.

A preliminary analysis of this initial annotation has shown that the variation within TV classes is restricted to a single class: <a, a>, where three patterns are attested for deriving the PRS.3PL form from the verbal base (V-BASE). The majority of verbs from this class are present with the standard BCMS ending [ju], while forms with the hiatus [au] and only [u] are also attested. The patterns are exemplified in Table 4.

Table 4: Patterns of 3PL.PRS forms in Torlak

pattern	3PL.PRS	3SG.PRS	gloss
V-BASE + [a] + [ju]	<primaju>	<prima>	‘receive’
V-BASE + [a] + [u]	<uzimau>	<uzima>	‘take’
V-BASE + [u]	<igru>	<igra>	‘play’

As the next step, the aim was to determine whether any of the verbs specialise in taking only one of the three patterns, which would suggest that the <a, a> class should be split into two subclasses. In the original sample, [ju] is by far the most common ending employed, occurring in 36 out of 46 tokens. To assess whether specific verbs tend to specialise in particular PRS.3PL endings, targeted searches were conducted for the eight verbs that appeared in the initial sample with one of the two less frequent patterns. For instance, for the verb <uzim-a-l-a, uzim-a>, the query was `[word="(ú|u)z(í|i)m(áj|a|jú|a|ju|á|a|ú|au|u|ú)"]`. These searches yielded 228 concordances, presented in a separate document and annotated for the PRS.3PL ending.

3.2.2 AORIST

To obtain a sample of aorist forms, a search was conducted targeting the forms ending in -še, as this is the ending common to all third person plural aorist forms in Torlak. Specifically, the query `[word=".+še" & word!="više" & word!="dodúše" & word!="náše" & word!="váše"]` was used. Verbs in the aorist were manually extracted from the resulting forms. This yielded a total of 701 verb tokens, further annotated in a separate table. In addition to the columns identifying examples (ID, left and right context, KWIC, and the reference of the example in the Torlak corpus), the dataset is annotated for the following properties:

- the TV class;
- the vowel preceding inflection;
- variation – whether the verb exhibits variation in its aorist forms (e.g. the verb <im-a-l-a, im-a> ‘have’ appears as either <imaše> or <imadoše> in the AOR.3PL);
- aspect (1 = perfective, 0 = imperfective).

3.2.3 IMPERFECTUM

Since several forms in the imperfectum end in /-še/, the initial sample was obtained using the same query as for the aorist, after which the actual imperfectum forms were manually extracted and annotated in a separate table. The resulting dataset comprises a total of 545 verb tokens with their concordances. As the ending /-še/ appears in both singular and plural imperfectum forms in the Timok varieties of Torlak, this dataset is also annotated for number (singular vs. plural), in addition to the other properties annotated in the aorist dataset.

4 THEME VOWEL CLASSES IN STANDARD BCMS VS. TORLAK

In this section, we outline the distribution of TV classes in standard BCMS (Section 4.1) and in the Torlak samples (Section 4.2), before comparing the two patterns in Section 4.3. The main finding of this comparison is that the ten TV classes previously used to describe standard BCMS can also be used to capture Torlak verbs.

4.1 Standard BCMS

WeSoSlav identified ten TV classes (plus a small class of defective verbs) in Western South Slavic. In Table 5 we provide TV classes arranged by size in standard BCMS (Marušič et al., 2022; Arsenijević et al., 2025).

This overview does not take into account that multiple verbs may share the same root and verbal suffixes, which are typically always followed by the same theme vowel. For instance, the imperfective BCMS verb <pit-a-ti> ‘to ask’ and its prefixed perfective counter-

Table 5: Theme vowel classes by size in BCMS

theme vowel class	frequency (%)	infinitive	present 1PL	gloss
a, a	1702 (32.1%)	pit-a-ti	pit-a-mo	'ask'
i, i	1601 (30.2%)	vis-i-ti	vis-i-mo	'hang'
a, je	1029 (19.4%)	plak-a-ti	plač-e-mo (/plak-je-mo/)	'cry'
/, e	298 (5.6%)	pas-∅-ti	pas-e-mo	'graze'
u, e	258 (4.9%)	gurn-u-ti	gurn-e-mo	'push'
e, i	184 (3.5%)	gor-(j)e-ti	gor-i-mo	'burn'
/, ne	124 (2.3%)	sta-∅-ti	sta-ne-mo	'stop'
a, i	62 (1.2%)	struj-a-ti	struj-i-mo	'flow'
a, e	19 (0.4%)	hrv-a-ti	hrv-e-mo	'wrestle'
e, e	17 (0.3%)	razum-(j)e-ti	razum-(ij)e-mo	'understand'
(defective)	6 (0.1%)	ht(j)e-ti	hoće-mo	'want'

parts <u-pit-a-ti> and <za-pit-a-ti> are counted as three separate verbs of the <a, a> class. Similarly, <imit-ir-a-ti> 'to imitate', <irit-ir-a-ti> 'to irritate', and <organiz-ir-a-ti> 'to organise' all contain the derivational suffix /-ir-/, consistently followed by the theme vowel <a, a>. It is therefore relevant to consider the size of TV classes in simplex verbs, i.e. verbs that consist only of a root, a theme vowel, and an inflectional ending, and do not include derivational suffixes. The distributions of TV classes across all verbs, suffixless verbs, and simplex verbs are shown in Table 6.

When it comes to suffixed verbs, the TV classes <a, a> and <a, je> are the most frequent. Specifically, the class <a, a> accounts for 40% of all verbs with a verbal suffix (703/1753), whereas the class <a, je> accounts for 38% of such verbs (661/1753). The class <i, i>, while the most frequent overall, does not derive verbs with a verbal suffix, although it is frequently found with multifunctional suffixes, accounting for 68% of such verbs (90/132).

4.2 Torlak

The frequency of TV classes in Torlak is given in Table 7 for all verbs and for suffixless verbs.

As clear from Table 7, the most frequent class is <i, i>, both when all the verbs are considered (1085/3085 i.e. 35.17%) and when only verbs without a suffix are taken into account (1081/2651 i.e. 40.78%). The second largest class is <a, a> (851/3085 i.e. 27.59% of all verbs), followed by the class <a, je> (13.19% of all verbs). The three smallest classes, each accounting for slightly more than 1 percent of cases, are <e, e> (1.46%), <a, i> (1.43%), and <a, e> (1.26%). When it comes to the suffixed verbs, the <a, a> and <a, je> classes account together for more than 98% of all suffixed verbs (423/431 i.e. 98.14%). Specifically, the most productive class is <a, je> (235/431 i.e. 54.52%), while the class <a, a> accounts for 188/431 (43.62%) of all suffixed verbs.

4.3 Comparison

As noted above, the most important finding from the comparison of BCMS and Torlak verbal theme vowels is that verbs in both varieties can be described using the same set of theme vowels. Some more specific similarities and differences can be summarised as follows. First, in both samples, the three most frequent classes are <i, i>, <a, a>, and <a, je>. Among all verbs, the <a, a> class is the most frequent in the standard BCMS sample, followed by the <i, i> class, whereas in the Torlak sample, the opposite pattern is observed: the <i, i> class is the most frequent, followed by <a, a>. In both samples, the <a, je> class ranks third in frequency.

When considering suffixed verbs, the <a, a> class remains the most frequent in the data from standard BCMS. In contrast, in the Torlak sample, the <a, je> class appears to be more productive, that is, more commonly used in the formation of derived verbs. It should be noted, however, that the annotation of suffixes in the two samples did not follow exactly the same criteria, so the observed differences may partly reflect this methodological discrepancy. In both samples, the classes <a, e>, <a, i>, and <e, e> are the least productive. However, a difference in their frequency is observed: in Torlak, the <e, e> class is the most frequent among the three, whereas in standard BCMS, it is the least frequent.

These patterns show a notable degree of consistency in how TV classes are distributed across the datasets. The continued predominance of the <i, i> class points to the lasting influence of inherited inflectional patterns in Torlak.

Table 6: Theme vowel classes across different derivational categories in BCMS

theme vowel class	all verbs	all verbs (%)	suffixless verbs	suffixless verbs (%)	simplex verbs	simplex verbs (%)
a, a	1702	32.11	524	19.45	187	27.54
i, i	1601	30.21	1430	53.08	324	47.72
a, je	1029	19.42	171	6.35	50	7.36
/, e	298	5.62	298	11.06	36	5.30
u, e	258	4.87	0	0	0	0
e, i	184	3.47	176	6.53	50	7.36
/, ne	124	2.34	0	0	0	0
a, i	62	1.17	53	1.97	19	2.80
a, e	19	0.36	19	0.71	5	0.74
e, e	17	0.32	17	0.63	3	0.44
defective	6	0.11	6	0.22	5	0.74
Total	5300	100	2694	100	679	100

Table 7: Theme vowel classes in Torlak

TV class	all verbs	all verbs (%)	suffixless verbs	suffixless verbs (%)	PTCP.F.SG	3SG.PRS	gloss
i, i	1085	35.17	1081	40.78	rabotila	raboti	'work'
a, a	851	27.59	663	25.01	pokarala	pokara	'scold'
a, je	407	13.19	172	6.49	vrzala	vrže	'tie'
/, e	245	7.94	245	9.24	porasla	poraste	'grow'
u, e	169	5.48	169	6.37	izlegnula	izlegne	'hatch'
e, i	100	3.24	99	3.73	volela	voli	'love'
/, ne	88	2.85	88	3.32	rekla	rekne	'tell'
e, e	45	1.46	43	1.62	smela	sme	'be allowed'
a, i	44	1.43	43	1.62	trčala	trči	'run'
a, e	39	1.26	38	1.43	posipala	posipe	'strew'
defective	12	0.39	11	0.41	bila	je	'be'
Total	3085	100	2651	100			

5 THEME VOWEL CLASSES AND VARIATION IN TORLAK

In this section, we focus on the specific inflectional forms in which our preliminary research revealed variation within TV classes. Specifically, the third person present tense, the aorist, and the imperfectum. This part of the study is guided by the question of whether any of the observed cases of variation warrant further restructuring of the system of TV classes. For instance, in cases where verbs belonging to the same class systematically select different sets of inflected forms.

5.1 Present tense: third person plural

As discussed in 3.2, our initial sample of PRS.3PL forms consisted of 323 verb tokens. The PRS.3PL endings attested in this sample are summarised in Table 8. The patterns that do not match standard BCMS are marked grey and represent the cases where Torlak verbs exhibit the exceptional endings [au] and [u].

It is worth noting that the initial sample may have been too small to capture all the variation present in the data and certainly displays some idiosyncrasies, particularly within the smaller classes. For instance, the <e, e> class is represented only by the verb <uzela, uzme>

which displays root allomorphy and is not included in our main dataset, as its more prominent variant <uzela, uzne> (from the </, ne> class) is included there.

Table 8: PRS.3PL endings in Torlak

TV class	PTCP.F.SG	PRS.3SG	PRS.3PL	Gloss
i, i	rabotila	raboti	rabote	'work'
a, a	igrala	igra	igraju igrau igru	'play'
a, je	vrzala	vrže	vržu	'tie'
/, e	porasla	poraste	porastu	'grow'
u, e	vrnula	vrne	vrnu	'return'
e, i	volela	voli	vole	'love'
/, ne	rekla	rekne	reknu	'tell'
e, e	uzela	uzme	uzmu	'take'
a, i	potrčala	potrči	potrču	'run'
a, e	zvala	zove	zovu	'call'
defective	bila	je	su	'be'

Despite this caveat, we expect the sample to be sufficient for capturing variation in the larger classes. As shown in Table 8, and as mentioned above, the only class that displays variation in this sample is the <a, a>

class. In the initial sample, out of the 46 3PL.PRS forms from the <a, a> class, 36 appear with the ending [ju] (e.g. <igraju> ‘play.3PL.PRS’), 4 appear with the ending [au] (e.g. <igrau> ‘play.3PL.PRS’), and 6 follow the pattern “- [a] + [u]” (e.g. <igru> ‘play.3PL.PRS’).

At the subsequent step, all eight verbs that displayed one of the non-dominant patterns – either patterned with [au] or with “- [a] + [u]” – were targeted in separate searches to determine whether any of them specialised in taking one of the two endings. Such specialisation would warrant splitting them off from the <a, a> class. The results are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: The PRS.3PL endings in 8 verbs from the <a, a> class in Torlak

PTCP.F.SG	3SG.PRS	3PL.PRS			gloss
		[ju]	[u]	-[a]+[u]	
imala	ima	80	47	8	‘have’
igrala	igra	22	9	3	‘play’
oterala	otera	7	11	2	‘oust’
uzimala	uzima	4	7	2	‘take’
smatrala	smatra	2	2	0	‘regard’
zaključala	zaključa	1	2	0	‘lock’
povatala	povata	1	0	2	‘catch’

The distributions in Table 9 show that no single verb uses only the non-dominant patterns in the 3PL.PRS. While a broader dataset will be necessary for a final generalisation, it seems quite probable that free variation or regional variation within the Timok area underlies the observed distribution of variants.

5.2 Aorist

The aorist form consists of the root, the vowel preceding the inflection, the inflectional aorist marker, and the agreement ending. Consider <plak-a-s-mo> /cry-VOWEL-AOR-AGR/ ‘we cried’ as an illustration. Our aim is to predict the vowel preceding the inflection based on the TV class and to investigate potential variation in this regard.

The general pattern, also found in standard BCMS, is as follows: the vowel preceding the inflection matches the vowel of the root + TV complex, if present; otherwise, the vowel [o] is inserted between the root and the inflectional suffix(es).

From the perspective of TV classes, the patterns can be summarised as follows:

- For all verbs whose participial theme vowel is overt, this theme vowel precedes the inflectional ending. For example, the verb <čitala, čita> ‘read’ (class <a, a>) has the third person plural aorist form <čit-a-še> ‘they read’.
- For verbs whose theme vowel is non-overt (classes </, e> or </, ne>), there are two possibilities:

- If the root ends in a vowel, this vowel precedes the inflection. For example, the verb <uzela, uzne> ‘take’ (class </, ne>) has the third person plural aorist form <uz-e-še> ‘they took’.
- If the root is consonant-final, the vowel [o] is inserted before the inflection. For instance, the verb <rekla, reče> ‘say’ (class </, e>) has the third person plural aorist form <rek-o-še> ‘they told’.

The correlation between TV classes and the vowel preceding the inflectional ending is quite strong in the data, but the data also reveal deviations from the general tendencies, indicating variation. This correlation is summarised in Table 10, with token-based frequencies.

Table 10: Correlation between theme vowels and vowels preceding aorist inflection in Torlak

TV	vowels preceding inflection					total
	[a]	[e]	[i]	[o]	[u]	
/, e	12	10	15	182	0	219
/, ne	5	30	0	14	0	49
a, a	116	0	0	2	0	118
a, i	3	0	0	0	0	3
a, je	22	0	0	0	1	23
e, e	0	9	0	0	0	9
e, i	0	19	0	5	0	24
i, i	0	0	213	1	0	214
u, e	0	0	0	2	34	36
total	161	67	226	206	35	695

While virtually all verbs from the <a, a> class have the vowel [a] in the aorist (116/118 tokens), two instances are attested with the vowel [o], characteristic of the </, e> class: <imadoše>, alongside the regular form <imaše> (from the verb <imala, ima> ‘have’), and <pričoše>, alongside <pričaše> (from <pričala, priča> ‘tell’). The first case (<imadoše>) may suggest a more complex case of root allomorphy in this verb, while the second form (<pričoše>) is actually ambiguous between the aorist and the third person plural imperfectum form, and may therefore not constitute a true exception.

Similarly, the class <a, je> is attested, expectedly, with the pre-inflectional vowel [a] in most cases (22/23). The only (apparent) exception is the verb token <otruše>, from the verb <otrovala, otruje> ‘poison’. This exception is only apparent, as the participle of this verb has two variants: <otrovala>, but also <otrula>, revealing the plausible base for <otruše>.

Five tokens of the class <e, i> are attested with the vowel [o] instead of the expected [e]. All of them are the tokens of the verb <videla, vidi> ‘see’: <vidoše>. This might be an indication of its reanalysis in terms of the </, e> class, given that the participle form <vidla> is also attested in parallel to <videla>. However, it remains note-

worthy that the form <vidla> is attested in 4 examples, while the more frequent form <videla> appears in 86 attestations. One token of the class <i, i>, out of 214, has [o] instead of the expected <i, i> (213/214): <turoše>, alongside more regular <turiše>, from the verb <turila, turi> ‘put’.

Finally, the <u, e> class regularly appears with the vowel [u] in the aorist, except for two tokens of the verb <dignula, dignu> ‘lift’: <digoše>. This is likely a reflex of variation between classes </, ne> and <u, e>, since the same verb can have the participle form <digla>, in addition to <dignula>. Conversely, the aorist <dignuše> is also possible, alongside <digoše>.

5.3 Imperfectum

The imperfectum form consists of the root, the vowel preceding the inflection, the inflectional imperfectum marker, and the agreement ending. Consider <im-a-še-mo> /have-VOWEL-IFM-AGR/ ‘we had’. As above, our aim is to predict the vowel preceding the inflection based on the TV class and to investigate potential variation in this regard. The emerging quantitative pattern is summarised in Table 11.

Table 11: Correlation between theme vowels and vowels preceding imperfectum inflection in Torlak

TV	vowels preceding inflection				total
	[a]	[e]	[i]	[o]	
0, e	0	16	0	0	16
a, a	123	1	0	0	124
a, e	24	13	0	2	39
a, i	2	0	0	0	2
a, je	5	4	0	1	10
e, e	0	1	0	0	1
e, i	0	4	0	0	4
i, i	0	26	2	1	29
u, e	0	2	0	0	2
Total	157	67	2	4	230

Several general tendencies can be read off the table:

- Classes </, e>, <e, e>, <u, e>, <e, i>, and <i, i> give rise to the imperfectum vowel [e]. That is, if the present-tense theme vowel is [e] or [i] and the participial theme vowel is not [a], then the pre-inflectional vowel is [e].
- Classes <a, a> and <a, i> display the pre-inflectional vowel [a].
- Classes <a, e> and <a, je> display pre-inflectional vowels [a] and [e].

Starting with the classes that exhibit the least variation, the following generalisations on the attested variation can be made:

- Four extremely small classes show no variation: <e, e>, <e, i>, <u, e> all display the pre-inflectional vowel [e]. The class <a, i> displays the pre-inflectional vowel [a].
- The class <i, i> has the pre-inflectional vowel [e] in 26/29 verbs, with three exceptions, out of which two with the vowel [i]: <juriše> ‘chased’, <veliše> ‘said’, and one with the vowel [o]: <žaloše> ‘pitied’.
- The class <a, a> also behaves mostly as expected, displaying the pre-inflectional vowel [a] in 123/124 cases. The only exception is the verb <pričala, priča> ‘tell’, which is attested once as <pričeše>, and otherwise, and more frequently, as <pričaše> (seven times).
- The class <a, e> generally has the pre-inflectional [e], except for the verb <zvala, zove> ‘call’, which can have the form <zvaše> attested 13 times, in addition to the form <zoveše>.
- Finally, the class with the greatest variation is <a, je>. Here, five verb tokens have the pre-inflectional [a] (e.g. <kazala, kaže> ‘say’ → <kazaše>), and four have the pre-inflectional vowel [e] (e.g. <vrzala, vrže> ‘tie’ → <vržeše>). This variation is exhibited also at the level of the same verb. The verb <sme(j)ala, sme(j)e> ‘laugh’ is attested with both [a] (<smejaše>) and [e] (<smeše>). Interestingly, the same verb is also attested with the vowel [o] (<smejoše>).

6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this contribution, we presented the first quantitatively substantiated analysis of the TV (conjugation) classes in Torlak. The main finding is that the classification into TV classes developed for standard BCMS can, in general, be applied to Torlak. A more detailed comparison between the two systems revealed several distributional differences, especially in the 3PL.PRS, where Torlak employs additional inflectional endings in free variation. Future research will show whether these differences reflect characteristics of the two samples or deeper structural distinctions between the systems.

Finally, a fine-grained consideration of specific inflectional forms that diverge from standard BCMS revealed several interesting cases of variation, which we hope will be addressed in future research. However, these patterns of variation do not appear to be of a kind that would necessitate a reclassification of the Torlak TV system.

7 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is primarily funded by the Austrian Agency for International Cooperation in Education and Research (OeAD) and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, under the project *What’s in a verb? Mapping Serbian verbs borrowed into Romani*

(RS03/2024; 337-00-216/87). It is also funded in part by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF, Grant-DOI 10.55776/I6258), and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, through the funding of the Institute for Balkan Studies SASA, based on the Agreement on the Implementation and Financing of Scientific Research Work in 2025, no. 451-03-136/2025-03 dated 27 January 2025. For the purpose of open access, the authors have applied a CC BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

We would like to thank the three anonymous reviewers of ReLDI 2025, as well as the audiences at the ReLDI 2025 Conference (Palace of Science, Belgrade, September 25–26, 2025) and CLASSLA-Express 1.0 Plus: Corpora Meets AI (University of Graz, October 10, 2025) for their constructive criticism and valuable suggestions.

REFERENCES

- Arsenijević, B., Gomboc Čeh, K., Marušič, F. L., Milosavljević, S., Mišmaš, P., Simić, J., ... Žaucer, R. (2024a). *Database of the Western South Slavic Verb HyperVerb 2.0 – WeSoSlaV*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1846> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- Arsenijević, B., Marušič, F. L., Milosavljević, S., Mišmaš, P., Simonović, M., & Žaucer, R. (2024b). *Database of the Western South Slavic Verb HyperVerb (WeSoSlaV) – Deverbal Nominalizations* [dataset]. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14230589
- Arsenijević, B., Marušič, F. L., Milosavljević, S., Mišmaš, P., Simonović, M., & Žaucer, R. (2025). *Hyperspacing the verb: The interplay between prosody, morphology, syntax and semantics in the Western South Slavic verbal domain*. Language Science Press. (Manuscript submitted for publication)
- Belić, A. (1905). *Dijalekti istočne i južne Srbije*. Srpska kraljevska akademija.
- Ćirković, S., Konior, D. V., Sobolev, A. N., & Mirić, M. (2023). Challenges for Torlak Data Collection. *Zeitschrift für Slavische Philologie*, 79(1), 81–122.
- Ljubešić, N., Galant, N., Benčina, S., Čibej, J., Milosavljević, S., Rupnik, P., & Kuzman, T. (2024, June). DIALECT-COPA: Extending the standard translations of the COPA causal commonsense reasoning dataset to South Slavic dialects. In Y. Scherrer, T. Jauhainen, N. Ljubešić, M. Zampieri, P. Nakov, & J. Tiedemann (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Eleventh Workshop on NLP for similar languages, varieties, and dialects (vardial 2024)* (pp. 89–98). Mexico City, Mexico: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.vardial-1.7/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.vardial-1.7
- Ljubešić, N., & Klubička, F. (2014, April). bs,hr,srWaC - web corpora of Bosnian, Croatian and Serbian. In *Proceedings of the 9th web as corpus workshop (WaC-9)* (pp. 29–35). Gothenburg, Sweden: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/W14-0405> doi: 10.3115/v1/W14-0405
- Logar-Berginc, N., Krek, S., Erjavec, T., Grčar, M., Halozan, P., & Šuster, S. (2012). *Gigafida 2.0 – korpus pisne standardne slovenščine* (Tech. Rep.). Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Centre for Language Resources and Technologies. <http://www.gigafida.net>
- Marušič, F. L., Žaucer, R., Mišmaš, P., Arsenijević, B., Simonović, M., Milosavljević, S., ... Simić, J. (2022). *Database of the Western South Slavic verb HyperVerb 1.0*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1683> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- Milosavljević, S., & Arsenijević, B. (2022). What differentiates Serbo-Croatian verbal theme vowels: content or markedness? *Glossa: a journal of general linguistics*, 7(1). doi: 10.16995/glossa.8535
- Milosavljević, S., Babić, A., & Simonović, M. (2025). *Mapping out the Torlak verb* [Data set]. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15736920
- Milosavljević, S., Mišmaš, P., Simonović, M., Arsenijević, B., Gomboc Čeh, K., Marušič, F. L., ... Žaucer, R. (2023). *Database of the Western South Slavic verb HyperVerb – derivation*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1855> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- Mišeska Tomić, O. (2006). *Balkan Sprachbund Morpho-syntactic Features*. AA Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Springer.
- Oltra-Massuet, I. (1999). On the constituent structure of Catalan verbs. *MIT Working Papers in Linguistics*, 33, 279–322.
- Oltra-Massuet, I. (2020). Conjugation class. In *Oxford research encyclopedia of linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. doi: 10.1093/acrefore/9780199384655.013.545
- Petrović, T. (2015). „Južnjački dijalekti“ između jezika, kulture i politike. Fabrika knjiga.
- Simonović, M., & Mišmaš, P. (2022). Lowest theme vowels or highest roots? an ‘unaccusative’ theme-vowel class in slovenian. *Glossa: a journal of general linguistics*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.16995/glossa.5809> doi: 10.16995/glossa.5809
- Simonović, M., Milosavljević, S., & Arsenijević, B. (2023). Serbo-Croatian secondary imperfectivisers consist of theme vowels. *Journal of Slavic Linguistics*, 31(FASL 30 extra issue). <http://ojs.ung.si/index.php/JSL/article/view/178>
- Sobolev, A. N., Mirić, M., Konior, D. V., & Ćirković, S. (2023). Torlak: Areal Embedding and Linguistic Characteristics. *Zeitschrift für Slavische Philologie*, 79(1), 23–46.
- Štarkl, E., Simonović, M., Milosavljević, S., & Arsenijević, B. (2025). The Western South Slavic verbal suffix nV/ne is a diminutive affix with a theme vowel. In B. Gehrke, D. Lenertová, R. Meyer, D. Seres, L. Szucsich, & J. Zaleska (Eds.), *Formal advances in Slavic linguistics 2022* (pp. 619–655). Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Tang, L., & Vuković, T. (2025). NLP for preserving Torlak, a vulnerable low-resource Slavic language. In *Proceedings of the 31st international conference on computational linguistics* (Vol. Part F2064, pp. 6338–6347).
- Vuković, T. (2020). *Spoken Torlak dialect corpus 1.0 (transcription)*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1281> (Slove-

nian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)

- Vuković, T. (2021). *Representing variation in a spoken corpus of an endangered dialect: the case of Torlak* (Vol. 55) (No. 3). doi: 10.1007/s10579-020-09522-4
- Vuković, T. (2024). *Empirical Approaches to Variation. The Case of Timok Variety of Torlak*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Zurich.
- Vuković, T., Escher, A., & Sonnenhauser, B. (2022). Degrees of non-standardness: Feature-based analysis of variation in a Torlak dialect corpus. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 27(2), 220–247. <http://www.jbe-platform.com/content/journals/10.1075/ijcl.20014.vuk>
- Vuković, T., Mirić, M., Escher, A., Ćirković, S., Miličević Petrović, M., Sobolev, A., & Sonnenhauser, B. (2023). Under the Magnifying Glass: Dimensions of Variation in the Contemporary Timok Variety. *Zeitschrift für Slavische Philologie*, 79(1), 153–194.
- Šare, A., & Stanković, S. (2011). O fenomenu lingvicizma među srbijskom akademskom filološkom elitom. In *Dijalekat – dijalekatska književnost* (pp. 46–54). Leskovački kulturni centar.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

TOWARDS BENCHMARKING TEXT CLASSIFICATION FOR SOUTH SLAVIC LANGUAGES IN THE ERA OF LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

Taja KUZMAN PUNGERŠEK,¹ Peter RUPNIK,¹ Ivan PORUPSKI,¹ Nikola LJUBEŠIĆ^{1, 2, 3}

¹Department of Knowledge Technologies, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia,
{taja.kuzman,peter.rupnik,ivan.porupski,nikola.ljubestic}@ijs.si

²Faculty of Computer and Information Science, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Institute of Contemporary History, Ljubljana, Slovenia

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Keywords: LLM evaluation, text classification, South Slavic languages, sentiment identification, topic classification, genre identification

1 INTRODUCTION

Until recently, fine-tuned BERT-like models provided state-of-the-art performance on text classification tasks. With the rise of instruction-tuned decoder-only Transformer models, commonly referred to as the large language models (LLMs), the field has increasingly moved toward zero-shot and few-shot prompting. However, despite the growing interest in this topic, the majority of evaluations of LLMs used in text classification tasks are limited only to English (Sun et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2025; Kostina et al., 2025; Zhao et al., 2024).

In this work, we evaluate the performance of current language models in South Slavic languages, where research on text classification tasks included in our study has, until recently, been limited or even non-existent (Kuzman & Ljubešić, 2023; Mochtak et al., 2024; Kuzman & Ljubešić, 2025). We compare traditional non-neural machine learning methods, fine-tuned BERT-like models, and a range of open-source and closed-source LLMs across three tasks: sentiment identification in parliamentary speeches, news topic classification, and genre identification in web texts.

2 BENCHMARKING DATASETS

The topic classification task is evaluated on the Croatian and Slovenian IPTC test datasets (Kuzman & Ljubešić, 2025) (around 300 text instances per language), manually annotated with 17 topic labels from the top level of the IPTC NewsCodes Media Topic hierarchical schema (IPTC, n.d.). For sentiment annotation, we use the freely-available Bosnian, Croatian, English, and Serbian ParlaSent sentiment identification datasets (Mochtak et al., 2024, 2023) (190 to 2600 instances per language), labelled with 3 categories. In addition, models are evaluated on the Croatian, English, Macedonian, and Slovenian GINCO genre datasets (Kuzman et al., 2023) (80 to 270 instances per language), annotated with 8 genre

labels. To prevent large language models from incorporating the test datasets during their training phase, the test datasets are not publicly available, except for the ParlaSent datasets. Access to other datasets is granted on request from the authors of this contribution.

3 METHODOLOGY

We evaluate the main machine learning approaches that have recently been used for our selection of text classification tasks. We focus on the comparison between the freely available fine-tuned BERT-like models – the XLM-R-ParlaSent (Mochtak et al., 2024) model for sentiment identification in parliamentary texts, the X-GENRE classifier (Kuzman et al., 2023; Kuzman & Ljubešić, 2024) for automatic genre identification, and the IPTC News Topic classifier (Kuzman & Ljubešić, 2025) for news topic classification – the open-source and closed-source LLMs, and the traditional non-neural machine learning methods, namely the Naive Bayes classifier and support vector machines (SVMs). Our selection of LLMs includes closed-source OpenAI GPT models, that is, the GPT-3.5-Turbo (*gpt-3.5-turbo-0125*) (OpenAI, 2023), GPT-4o (*gpt-4o-2024-08-06*) (OpenAI, 2024b) and the GPT-4o-mini (*gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18*) (OpenAI, 2024a); and three open-source models, namely, the Meta LLaMA 3.3 model (Meta, 2024), the Gemma 3 model (Gemma Team et al., 2025) and the DeepSeek-R1-Distill model (Guo et al., 2025) (*DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-14B*). All instruction-tuned large language models are used in a zero-shot prompting setup, meaning that they receive only a task description and label definitions. The code for the model evaluation, including the prompts, and analysis of the results are published at <https://github.com/TajaKuzman/Benchmarking-Text-Classification-on-South-Slavic>.

Figure 1: Micro-F1 and macro-F1 scores across models and languages on the sentiment classification test datasets.

Figure 2: Micro-F1 and macro-F1 scores across models and languages on the automatic genre identification test datasets.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our results show that Transformer-based language models consistently outperform traditional non-neural machine learning methods. The latter fail to deliver satisfactory results on all selected text classification tasks. More precisely, the Naive Bayes classifier and the SVM yield results below 0.50 in both micro-F1 and macro-F1 across all tasks, which renders them ineffective for reliable classification in these tasks. In addition to the relatively simplistic architectures of these two machine learning methods, their poor performance might also be attributed to the fact that they were trained on multilingual datasets, which introduces noise in vocabulary that is used to generate numerical representations on which these models are trained. They are less capable of an effective generalisation when faced with linguistically diverse input, which more sophisticated Transformer-

Figure 3: Micro-F1 and macro-F1 scores across models and languages on the news topic test datasets.

based models handle better due to their contextual embeddings and deep learning capabilities.

When comparing the fine-tuned BERT-like models with the large language models (LLMs), a consistent pattern emerges across all three tasks: LLMs, especially GPT-4o (OpenAI, 2024b), demonstrate strong zero-shot performance, often matching or surpassing fine-tuned BERT-like models. The best large language models, used through prompting, achieve micro-F1 and macro-F1 scores between 0.72 and 0.78 on sentiment identification (see Figure 1), between 0.70 and 0.80 on genre identification (Figure 2), and 0.77 on topic classification (Figure 3). On sentiment identification task, we find that both open-source and closed-source LLMs achieve performance that is comparable or even higher to that of a fine-tuned BERT-like model trained on a large manually-annotated sentiment dataset. In contrast, fine-tuned BERT-like models outperform most LLMs on automatic genre identification and topic classification tasks. These tasks depend on predefined label sets based on specific guidelines, and the strong performance of fine-tuned BERT-like models indicates that domain-specific fine-tuning on labelled data still offers an advantage over the general knowledge leveraged by LLMs models in zero-shot settings.

Additional disadvantage of the large language models is that they are significantly more computationally expensive than fine-tuned BERT-like models, and when accessed via an API, they also tend to be more costly. In this regard, fine-tuned BERT-like models offer a key advantage because of their lower computational and financial requirements. In addition, they can be trained on LLM-annotated data using the recently introduced LLM teacher-student paradigm (Kuzman & Ljubešić, 2025), which considerably reduces the effort needed to de-

Table 1: Comparison of model performance on sentiment identification on English and South Slavic languages, using averaged macro-F1 scores obtained on South Slavic datasets (Bosnian, Croatian, Serbian).

Model	English	South Slavic
GPT-4o	0.771	0.732
Gemma 3	0.768	0.718
LLaMA 3.3	0.749	0.698
GPT-4o-mini	0.733	0.654
GPT-3.5-Turbo	0.700	0.633
DeepSeek-R1-Distill	0.617	0.587

velop task-specific models. Another limitation of LLMs, as revealed by the experiments, is their occasional deviation from the defined label set.

The sentiment identification test data comprise datasets in South Slavic languages and English that were constructed with the same methodology. Thus, they also allow for a comparison of the performance of LLMs on English, a highly resourced language, with South Slavic languages, which are significantly less represented in the pretraining and instruction-tuning datasets used to develop LLMs. We find that LLMs perform better on the English dataset, but the differences in macro-F1 scores are relatively small, ranging from 3 to 8 points (see Table 1). Interestingly, even the open-source LLaMA 3.3 model (Meta, 2024), which is reported to support only eight languages, which do not include South Slavic languages, does not exhibit a significant performance drop when applied to South Slavic languages compared to English.

5 CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

In this work, we evaluated how well current machine learning technologies handle text classification tasks in South Slavic languages. Our results show that Transformer-based models, i.e., the fine-tuned BERT-like models and the instruction-tuned decoder-only large language models (LLMs), clearly outperform traditional non-neural methods that were commonly used before the emergence of Transformers. The LLMs used with prompting, where only a brief task description and labels are provided, achieve strong results in all tasks and languages, particularly the closed-source GPT-4o model. Their performance is comparable to that of fine-tuned BERT-like models specialised for the tasks. Interestingly, LLMs perform similarly in English and South Slavic languages, with only minor drops in micro-F1 and macro-F1 scores. This suggests that the gap in multilingual performance is smaller than expected, even for open-source models not explicitly dedicated to these languages.

This study represents only an initial step to systematically benchmark text classification performance in South Slavic languages. Although our evaluation includes three diverse classification tasks, some of the test datasets remain relatively small. Future work will aim to increase dataset sizes, include more South Slavic languages and dialects, and introduce additional classification tasks. As new large language models continue to emerge rapidly, it will also be important to establish ongoing evaluations to track whether their performance continues to improve, particularly on South Slavic languages.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the developers of the llm.ijs.si service (Marić et al., 2025) for establishing the LLM inference platform deployed at the Jožef Stefan Institute, which provided convenient access to the open-source large language models used in this study. We also thank the annotators of the test datasets for their diligence and the time devoted to manual annotation, which resulted in the high-quality evaluation datasets used in this work. Lastly, we would like to thank the CLASSLA knowledge centre for South Slavic languages and the Slovenian CLARIN.SI infrastructure for their valuable support.

This work was supported in part by the projects “Spoken Language Resources and Speech Technologies for the Slovenian Language” (Grant J7-4642), “Large Language Models for Digital Humanities” (Grant GC-0002), the research programme “Language Resources and Technologies for Slovene” (Grant P6-0411), all funded by the ARIS Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency, and the research project “Embeddings-based techniques for Media Monitoring Applications” (L2-50070), co-funded by the Klipping d.o.o. agency.

REFERENCES

- Gemma Team, Kamath, A., Ferret, J., Pathak, S., Vieillard, N., Merhej, R., ... others (2025). Gemma 3 technical report. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.19786*. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2503.19786>
- Guo, D., Yang, D., Zhang, H., Song, J., Zhang, R., Xu, R., ... others (2025). DeepSeek-R1: Incentivizing Reasoning Capability in LLMs via Reinforcement Learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.12948*. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2501.12948?>
- IPTC. (n.d.). *Groups of NewsCodes*. <https://iptc.org/standards/newscodes/groups/#descrncd>. (Accessed October 29, 2024)
- Kostina, A., Dikaiakos, M. D., Stefanidis, D., & Pallis, G. (2025). Large language models for text classification: Case study and comprehensive review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.08457*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.08457>
- Kuzman, T., & Ljubešić, N. (2023). Automatic genre identification: a survey. *Language Resources and Evaluation*, 1–34. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/s10579-023-09695-8.pdf>

- Kuzman, T., & Ljubešić, N. (2024). *Multilingual text genre classification model X-GENRE*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1961> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- Kuzman, T., & Ljubešić, N. (2025). LLM Teacher-Student Framework for Text Classification With No Manually Annotated Data: A Case Study in IPTC News Topic Classification. *IEEE Access*, 13, 35621-35633. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/jiel8/6287639/6514899/10900365.pdf> doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3544814
- Kuzman, T., Mozetič, I., & Ljubešić, N. (2023). Automatic Genre Identification for Robust Enrichment of Massive Text Collections: Investigation of Classification Methods in the Era of Large Language Models. *Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction*, 5(3), 1149–1175. <https://www.mdpi.com/2504-4990/5/3/59>
- Marić, N., Koloski, B., Demšar, D., Javoršek, J. J., & Džeroski, S. (2025). Running large language models locally: design and operational insights with llm.ijs.si. *International conference AI for science 2025: Ljubljana, Slovenia, 22.09.2025-26.09.2025*, 77. https://ai4science.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/AI4Science_Book_of_Abstracts-4.pdf
- Meta. (2024). *Llama 3.3 Model Card*. https://github.com/meta-llama/llama-models/blob/main/models/llama3_3/MODEL_CARD.md. (Accessed: June 26, 2025)
- Mochtak, M., Rupnik, P., & Ljubešić, N. (2024). The ParlaSent Multilingual Training Dataset for Sentiment Identification in Parliamentary Proceedings. In *Proceedings of the 2024 joint international conference on computational linguistics, language resources and evaluation (lrec-coling 2024)* (pp. 16024–16036). <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lrec-main.1393/>
- Mochtak, M., Rupnik, P., Meden, K., & Ljubešić, N. (2023). *The multilingual sentiment dataset of parliamentary debates ParlaSent 1.0*. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1868> (Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI)
- OpenAI. (2023). *ChatGPT General FAQ*. <https://help.openai.com/en/articles/6783457-chatgpt-general-faq>. Author. (Accessed: June 26, 2025)
- OpenAI. (2024a). *GPT-4o mini: advancing cost-efficient intelligence*. <https://openai.com/index/gpt-4o-mini-advancing-cost-efficient-intelligence/>. (Accessed: June 26, 2025)
- OpenAI. (2024b). *Hello GPT-4o*. <https://openai.com/index/hello-gpt-4o/>. (Accessed September 11, 2024)
- Sun, X., Li, X., Li, J., Wu, F., Guo, S., Zhang, T., & Wang, G. (2023). Text Classification via Large Language Models. In *Findings of the association for computational linguistics: Emnlp 2023* (pp. 8990–9005). <https://aclanthology.org/2023.findings-emnlp.603/>
- Zhang, Y., Wang, M., Li, Q., Tiwari, P., & Qin, J. (2025). Pushing the limit of LLM capacity for text classification. In *Companion proceedings of the acm on web conference 2025* (pp. 1524–1528). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3701716.3715528>
- Zhao, H., Chen, Q. P., Zhang, Y. B., & Yang, G. (2024). Advanc-

ing Single and Multi-task Text Classification through Large Language Model Fine-tuning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.08587*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.08587>

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

EMBEDDING TEXT IN EMOTION AND EVOCATION VECTOR SPACES

Mihailo ŠKORIĆ¹ Ranka STANKOVIĆ¹

¹University of Belgrade, Faculty of mining and geology

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Keywords: Language Modeling, Embedding, Emotion, Evocation, Serbian

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, there has been a steady increase in interest in the field of sentiment and emotion analysis, with much of the progress in emotion classification driven by industry demands, particularly the need for improved understanding of customer satisfaction and the extraction of similar insights. Traditionally, this task was handled by employing machine learning techniques over a labeled dataset (Alm et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2023) or by fine-tuning various pre-trained language models on the emotion classification task (Adoma et al., 2020). These methods produce binary outputs (in both single-label and multi-label classification), meaning that an emotion is either detected or not detected, resulting in the loss of more nuanced emotional content, such as emotion intensity. Although we can build a more value-specific dataset (Mohammad & Bravo-Marquez, 2017) or use probability-based scores for emotion labels to help address this issue, a more straightforward solution would be to directly embed the text in the emotion vector space, enabling the quantification of emotion intensity across multiple dimensions.

This paper dives into the building of such embedding models by training them on a text-labeled dataset of social media posts in Serbian. The used dataset, which will be presented in the following section, is labeled only with emotions and not their intensities, because of that, regression is used to train the model to predict emotion intensity vectors. Additionally, we explore the concept of emotion evocation (the ability of a message to induce an emotional response) via embedding the text in a vector space that reflects potential emotional responses elicited in readers. Evocation vectors, which were also not labeled in the dataset, are extracted as emotion vectors of replies to the original text. The dual embedding spaces, emotion and emotion evocation, are designed to provide a more comprehensive representation of both the emotions expressed in text and their potential emotional impact, which can be used for visualization or as an input for downstream classification.

2 DATASET

The base dataset used for this research, *Social-Emo.Sr* (Šošić, 2025) consists of 16,670 *X* (*Twitter*), and 17,930 *Reddit* posts written in Serbian and manually annotated for one or more of the eight basic emotions, according to (Plutchik, 1965): joy, trust, fear, surprise, sadness, anticipation, anger, and disgust. To create the final training set of text-vector pairs, the following columns of the dataset were used:

- **id** – The id of the specific entry, derived from the *conversation_id* (*Twitter*) or *submission_id* (*Reddit*).
- **text_lat** – Textual content of the post;
- **gold_labels** – A list of emotion labels, consolidated from multiple annotator inputs.
- **referenced_tweets_id** – A list of id-s *Twitter* post is a reference to (for *Twitter* entries only).
- **parent_id** – An id of the post *Reddit* post is a reference to (for *Reddit* entries only).

For each reference made using *referenced_tweets_id* or *parent_id*, both emotion and emotion evocation embeddings for the text in *text_lat* (from the referenced post) were produced using the assigned *gold_labels*. Emotion embeddings were assigned using labels from the referenced post, and evocation embeddings were produced using the labels from the referee post. This is done under the assumption that the referenced post evoked emotions similar to those present in the referee post.

All of the textual labels from *gold_labels* were mapped to integer values representing emotion dimension indices, so, given a set of mapped gold labels from the referenced post $L^1 \subseteq \{0..7\}$, and a set of mapped gold labels from the referee post $L^2 \subseteq \{0..7\}$ resulting embedding vector v is defined as follows:

$$v_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \in \{L^1\} \text{ or } i-8 \in \{L^2\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

for $i \in \{0..15\}$

Figure 1: Architecture of a singular emotion and evocation embedding model, where n is the number of input words, m is the word-embedding dimension (1024), and M is the pooling output dimension (also 1024). Color red represents the word-embedding model, yellow the mean-pooling layer, and blue-green represents the dense layer for emotion and evocation embedding.

The transformation resulted in a set of 15,412 unique pairs of texts and 16-dimensional embeddings, 8 for emotions and 8 for emotion evocations. This set was then shuffled and split using an 8-1-1 ratio to obtain training, validation, and test splits for the experiment.

3 MODELS

To build combined models for emotion and evocation embedding, two approaches were envisioned, both using the *sentence transformers* architecture (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019) and *Jerteh355* (Škorić, 2024) Serbian embedding language model (355 million parameters) as the base word-embedding model.

Since sentence transformers are typically trained using text triplets or pairs with similarity values, only two of their loss functions support vector inputs: *MSELoss* (Mean Squared Error Loss) and *MarginMSELoss*, both intended for knowledge distillation from a *teacher* model to a *student* model of the same embedding dimension. We can, however, set the student model's embedding dimension to match the set of possible labels, and provide the *teaching* embeddings directly from the training dataset.

3.1 Single Emotion and Evocation Model

The first approach employed a simple sentence transformer architecture, consisting of the base word-embedding model, one mean pooling layer, and one dense layer with 16 outputs: 8 for emotions and 8 for emotion evocations (Figure 1).

The training of the model was conducted using the prepared training and validation splits and default hyperparameters (batch size 8, learning rate of $5e-5$ etc.) for one epoch, which resulted in a model that embeds text in 16 dimensions, where the first 8 are for the expressed emotions intensity and the latter 8 for the intensity of emotions the text possibly evokes.

3.2 Combined Emotion and Evocation Model

The second approach also employed the sentence transformer architecture but involved training of two separate models, which were later merged: one for embedding in the emotion space and another for embedding in the evocation space.

As in the first example, each model consisted of a base transformer model, a mean pooling layer, and a dense layer, except that the dense layers had an output dimension of 8. For each row in the prepared dataset, the first 8 dimensions of the embedding vector were used to train the emotion embedding model, while the latter were used to train the evocation embedding model.

While this approach allows for the usage of separate training sets for each respective model, their later merge comes with a constraint: the word embedding model weights must be frozen for the training of at least one model. To minimize this loss, we first perform full training of the emotion embedding model and then fine-tune it using the evocation embedding dataset while freezing the parameters of the word embedding component. This ensures that the output dense layers receive identical inputs in both models, enabling their integration into a single combined model (Figure 2).

This model has the following components:

1. A single word-embedding model, which can be copied from either initial models.
2. A single mean pooling layer with the same output dimension as each initial model.
3. A new *mapping* dense layer, used to duplicate the output of the pooling layer, as the new embedding layer's input dimension is doubled in size. This is accomplished by initializing a dense layer without bias, with the input dimension matching the output dimension of the pooling layer, and the output dimension being twice as large. To ensure the output of this layer is equal to two concatenated replicas of the input, the

weights are set as follows:

$$w_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } j-i \in \{0, n-1\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

for $i \in \{0 \dots n-1\}$, $j \in \{0 \dots 2n-1\}$

where w is weight, i is the input index, j is the output index, and n is the input dimension.¹ Also, it is necessary to eliminate any activation functions that could corrupt the value pass-through.²

- Finally, a new embedding dense layer, with an input dimension double the size of the pooling layer output and the output dimension of 16, which aims to encapsulate the embedding layer weights from both initial models. To accomplish that, the weights and biases for this layer are set as follows:

$$w_{ij} = \begin{cases} w_{ij}^1 & \text{if } i < n \text{ and } j < 8 \\ w_{i-n, j-8}^2 & \text{if } i \geq n \text{ and } j \geq 8 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

for $i \in \{0 \dots 2n-1\}$, $j \in \{0 \dots 15\}$

$$b_j = \begin{cases} b_j^1 & \text{if } j < 8 \\ b_{j-8}^2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

for $j \in \{0 \dots 15\}$

where w and b are the weights and bias in the new dense layer, w^1 and b^1 are the weights and bias of the embedding layer from the first pre-trained model, w^2 and b^2 are the weights and bias of the embedding layer from the second pre-trained model, i is the input index, j is the output index, and n is the original input dimension.

Just like the single embedding model (section 3.1), this model outputs a single embedding vector with a dimension of 16, where 8 values represent the intensity of emotions expressed in the text and 8 represent the emotion evocation intensity. An example of the outputs is visualized in Figure 3.

¹The same can be accomplished by creating a custom forwarding function, but that would require later users to enable *trust remote code* parameter to run the model, which is not advisable. This approach bypasses that issue.

²Sentence transformers dense layers use Hyperbolic Tangent (Tanh) activation by default, and there is no option for linear activation, since it does not exist in the reference module, *PyTorch*. We can, however, still perform the pass-through by *planting* PyTorch placeholder, argument-insensitive operator, *nn.Identity*, as the activation function for this layer.

Figure 2: Architecture of a combined emotion and evocation embedding model, where n is the number of input words, m is the word-embedding dimension (1024), and M is the pooling output dimension (1024). Word-embedding modules are depicted in red, mean-pooling layers in yellow, dense layers for emotion embedding in blue, and dense layers for evocation embedding in green. Purple represents the mapping dense layer. Colored arrows represent layer origins for the final model (bottom) from the initial emotion (top left) and evocation (top right) embedding models.

Figure 3: *There's a lot of traffic, so I'll be a little late.* – Difference between calculated emotion (left) and emotion evocation intensities (right).

4 DISCUSSION

The paper details the construction of emotion and emotion evocation embedding vector spaces through the training of a series of sentence-transformer models.

Two different approaches for the creation of these dual (emotion and emotion evocation) embeddings are presented, one where both embedding spaces are entangled during training, and the other where those spaces are separated. When testing the mean square error loss of these models against the test dataset, we find that the second model is slightly better for embedding emotions (0.0779 to 0.0822), but it is significantly worse for embedding emotion evocations (0.1800 to 0.1441).

These findings come at no surprise, since the first model was fully trained for evocation embedding and the second one was merely fine-tuned. The disadvantage of the fine-tuning approach is even clearer when we calculate the loss between the test set emotion embeddings and the supposed evocation embeddings using a second model (0.0867), meaning the model is still embedding text in the original, emotion, rather than the fine-tuned evocation space. If we subject the first model to this test, we get a value of 0.1262, meaning the spaces are further apart.

All in all, the paper demonstrates that it is possible to build separate emotion and emotion evocation vector spaces for text embedding, enhancing the granularity of emotion analysis, and hopefully paving the way for improved sentiment analysis applications and emotionally intelligent systems. The embedding of text in these specialized vector spaces offers a powerful tool for researchers and practitioners to dissect and better under-

stand the complex emotional landscape of written language. Finally, it shows that the models can be taught to produce granular emotional intensities from a non-granular dataset.

The discrepancy between emotion and evocation spaces also indicates the possibility of learning emotion evocation embeddings through the emotions of social media post references, which is still largely unexplored and could have a potential applicative impact in various fields: social media monitoring and marketing, psychological studies, or even human-computer interaction.

There are, however, several limitations inherent to this study that should be acknowledged:

Training Set Configuration: The study opted for a simpler approach by not utilizing the obvious advantage of separate emotion and evocation training sets for the combined model. This decision was made to avoid overcomplicating the paper. However, the inclusion of non-referenced posts in the training set for the second could have potentially impacted the results. Additionally, the strict limit on the number of fine-tuning epochs for the evocation embedding model may have further negatively influenced this model's performance.

Evaluation Limitations: The evaluation of the embedding model against the test set presents some challenges. Given the differences in granularity, it is uncertain whether this evaluation method is entirely sufficient. Typically, the performance of embedding models is assessed through downstream tasks, which were beyond the scope of this paper, thus, the evaluation provided here may not be fully conclusive. Extensive evaluation using repeated tests on a variety of downstream tasks with defined baselines is necessary to better un-

derstand the model's capabilities, so it will be a part of future research.

Model usability: The models developed in this study were built using experimental methods on a single dataset, not previously established or thoroughly super-evaluated. Further validation on more diverse and well-established datasets is necessary to confirm the robustness and applicability of these models in real-world scenarios.

5 CONCLUSION

We introduce a novel approach to embedding textual data into two distinct but complementary vector spaces: one capturing the emotions explicitly expressed in the text, and the other modeling the potential emotional evocation for readers. Leveraging a manually annotated Serbian-language social media corpus, we trained sentence transformer-based models to represent texts in an interpretable 16-dimensional embedding space, split evenly between emotion and emotion evocation intensities.

We presented two modeling strategies: a single model jointly trained on both emotion and evocation targets, and a modular approach combining separately trained models. While the first approach yielded better alignment between the two embedding spaces and stronger evocation performance, the second offered architectural flexibility and interpretability. The results suggest that even coarse, non-granular labels can be transformed into fine-grained affective embeddings through thoughtful model design.

These findings contribute to ongoing efforts in affective computing and NLP by enabling more nuanced representations of emotional content in text. Embedding-based approaches of this kind have promising implications for downstream applications such as sentiment tracking, emotionally aware dialogue systems, psychological profiling, and digital media analysis.

Future work should aim to refine evocation modeling with dedicated datasets, explore multilingual generalization, and validate the proposed models through comprehensive downstream tasks. The distinct separation between expressed and evoked emotion vectors also opens the door for new research into the dynamics of emotional resonance in social and mediated communication.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #7276, *Text Embeddings – Serbian Language Applications – TESLA*.

REFERENCES

- Adoma, A. F., Henry, N.-M., & Chen, W. (2020). Comparative analyses of bert, roberta, distilbert, and xlnet for text-based emotion recognition. In *2020 17th international computer conference on wavelet active media technology and information processing (iccwamtip)* (pp. 117–121).
- Alm, C. O., Roth, D., & Sproat, R. (2005, October). Emotions from text: Machine learning for text-based emotion prediction. In R. Mooney, C. Brew, L.-F. Chien, & K. Kirchoff (Eds.), *Hlt:2005:1* (pp. 579–586). Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada: acl. <https://aclanthology.org/H05-1073.pdf>
- Liu, X., Shi, T., Zhou, G., Liu, M., Yin, Z., Yin, L., & Zheng, W. (2023). Emotion classification for short texts: an improved multi-label method. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, *10*(1), 1–9. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-023-01816-6.pdf>
- Mohammad, S., & Bravo-Marquez, F. (2017, September). WASSA-2017 shared task on emotion intensity. In A. Balahur, S. M. Mohammad, & E. van der Goot (Eds.), *Wassa:2017:52* (pp. 34–49). Copenhagen, Denmark: acl. <https://aclanthology.org/W17-5205.pdf> doi: 10.18653/v1/W17-5205
- Plutchik, R. (1965). What is an emotion? *The Journal of psychology*, *61*(2), 295–303.
- Reimers, N., & Gurevych, I. (2019, 11). Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks. In *Proceedings of the 2019 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing*. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084>
- Škorić, M. (2024). *Novi jezički modeli za srpski jezik*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.14379>
- Šošić, M. (2025). *Modelovanje moralnih i emocionalnih aspekata jezika u klasifikaciji konverzacionih tekstova (modeling moral and emotional language aspects in conversational texts classification)*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mathematics. (PhD disertation (submitted))

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

FROM NAMES TO PLACES: SERBIAN ENTITY LINKING THROUGH THE LENS OF GIS

Ranka STANKOVIĆ,¹ Saša PETALINKAR,² Milica IKONIĆ NEŠIĆ³

¹University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mining and Geology, Serbia

²Society for Language Resources and Technology - JERTEH, Serbia

³University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philology, Serbia

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Keywords: Named Entity Recognition, Named Entity Linking, Wikidata, Serbian

1 INTRODUCTION

Named Entity Linking (NEL) is one of the fundamental tasks in Natural Language Processing (NLP), involving the identification of named entity mentions (such as persons, organizations, locations, and events) and their linking to canonical entries in structured knowledge bases such as Wikidata (Vrandečić & Kröttsch, 2014) or DBpedia (Auer et al., 2007). This process transforms unstructured text into structured semantic representations, thereby enhancing the performance of downstream NLP applications such as sentiment analysis, question answering, and knowledge base population. The importance of NEL is especially pronounced in domains such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), where linking textual mentions of locations to geospatial coordinates enables spatial reasoning and visualization (Berragan et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2023; Jones & Purves, 2008).

Despite extensive research in NEL, the task remains particularly challenging for morphologically rich and low-resource languages like Serbian (Ikonić Nešić, Petalinkar, Stanković, Utvić, & Kitanović, 2024). Multilingual and cross-lingual entity linking models often struggle with complex inflectional morphology, where a single entity may appear in many surface forms. This linguistic variability complicates both candidate generation and entity disambiguation (Ikonić Nešić, Petalinkar, Stanković, & Škorić, 2024), limiting the applicability of existing systems trained primarily on English or other high-resource languages.

Previous work has demonstrated the utility of domain-specific NEL systems. For example, tools like ScispaCy (Neumann et al., 2019) and REL (Van Hulst et al., 2020) have achieved success by tailoring linking strategies to biomedical and general-purpose contexts, respectively. Similarly, the SrpCNNeL model (Ikonić Nešić, Petalinkar, Stanković, Utvić, & Kitanović, 2024) represents the first CNN-based approach to NEL in Serbian, trained on three core entity types: persons, organizations, and locations. It builds upon SrpCNNeL2, a

named entity recognizer developed using Serbian literary corpus (Stanković et al., 2021) and news corpora (Vitas et al., 2025), as well as synthetic data derived from lexical database Leximirka (Stanković et al., 2018) and Wikidata.

In this paper, we present ongoing work on transformer-based models for Serbian named entity linking, which focuses on geospatial entities and integrates with GIS platforms for enhanced visualization and analysis. Our objectives are threefold: (i) to improve entity linking accuracy by accounting for inflectional morphology, (ii) to enable spatial mapping of linked locations using geocoordinates from Wikidata, and (iii) to develop tools for visualizing geolocated entities extracted from diverse textual sources.

This work bridges the gap between entity linking and spatial reasoning by developing NEL models that are linguistically aware and geospatially enabled. In doing so, it contributes to the broader goals of digital humanities, geographic information retrieval, and low-resource NLP.

The Section 2 describes the model architecture and training procedures; Section 3 details the data preparation and knowledge base construction; Section 4 presents evaluation results and analysis; and Section 5 outlines conclusions and future work.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Model Training and Pipeline Configuration

We trained NEL models using the spaCy command-line interface. The annotated datasets were first converted into spaCy's binary format and partitioned into training and development sets. A knowledge base was constructed for entities in set using definitions extracted from Wikidata, which were stored in a separate directory. Inflected forms of canonical forms of entities were set as aliases. The definitions were vectorized using the `jerTEH335-ner1` (Ikonić Nešić, Petalinkar, Stanković, & Škorić, 2024).

¹https://huggingface.co/Tanor/sr_pner_tesla_j355

The pipeline architecture consisted of four components:

- transformer backbone incorporating either TeslaXLM and Jerteh-355 pretrained models;
- Named Entity Recognizer (NER);
- sentence segmenter module (sentence tagger);
- entity linking component.

2.2 Output Generation and Integration

The two best-performing models: TeslaXLM and Jerteh-355_NER+NEL were then employed to annotate raw text across multiple output formats. These included structured HTML representations, *WebAnno v3-compatible .tsv* files (via a custom-made converter used for INCEPTION (Klie et al., 2018)), and GIS-ready data layers (using GeoJSON²). This ensured compatibility with both linguistic annotation platforms and geospatial analysis tools, enabling broader applications of the linked entities in domain-specific downstream tasks.

3 DATA

The creation of the *srGeoTESLA* dataset involved two annotation methods: semi-automatic (*srGeoTESLA-SA*) and fully automatic (*srGeoTESLA-FA*). For *srGeoTESLA-SA*, automatic annotation with manual corrections was applied to 51K sentences sourced from novels, newspapers, and legal documents. Fully automatic annotation included two methods: sentence generation based on templates and legacy lexical resources and gazetiers from Leximirka (Stanković et al., 2018; Lazić & Škorić, 2019), named (*srGeoTESLA-lex*), and automated generation using ChatGPT 4.0 (*srGeoTESLA-chat*).

The complete *srGeoTESLA* dataset comprises 73K sentences with 47K entities annotated for NER type and Wikidata QIDs. Of these, 35K entities (1.9K unique) represent geolocations, reflecting the dataset’s primary goal of geolocation recognition and linking in Serbian texts. The work on dataset preparation is still ongoing task and when it reach 150K sentences.³

The NER tagset is inspired by categories established within European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC) development (Krstev & Stanković, 2021; Stanković et al., 2021; Frontini et al., 2020): personal names (PERS), locations (LOC), organizations (ORG), professions and titles (ROLE), demonyms (DEMO), artworks (WORK), and events (EVENT). Most frequent class are LOC (37K), PERS (14K), ORG 11K).

The dataset was pre-annotated for NER with different models (Krstev et al., 2014; Ikonić Nešić, Petalinkar,

Stanković, Utvić, & Kitanović, 2024), since the development of this dataset spanned through several years and different tools were used. For manual correction of pre-annotated dataset, INCEPTION tool was used. The sentences were annotated by many trained annotators and all annotations have been cross-checked by an expert.

Assigning Wikidata IDs (QIDs) is a task known as entity linking. Since no successful linking model for Serbian was available, pre-annotation was not possible. In INCEPTION, a dedicated layer with a Wikidata-based knowledge base was established. Within the LOC category, 36,000 mentions (97.4%) were successfully linked to their corresponding canonical entries (QIDs) in Wikidata. In addition to ambiguities in Wikidata, another issue was that some entities were not present in Wikidata. For some of these, we added new items, but others remained unlinked, with NIL assigned as the annotated value.

4 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

To evaluate the practical applicability and domain-specific performance of various NEL models, we conducted a focused evaluation utilizing a specialized dataset: the *sr-geography* corpus. This corpus, specifically curated to represent a distinct domain, comprises 710 sentences totaling 2,297 words, extracted from Serbian elementary school geography textbooks (Dinić-Marinković, 2017). This dataset provides a challenging testbed for assessing model robustness and generalization capabilities beyond general-domain text.

The *sr-geography* corpus is rich in geolocational named entities, comprising a total of 746 annotated mentions. These entities are distributed across several predefined categories critical for geography texts, including country (42.2%), city (17.6%), continent (10.6%), mountain (9.0%), river (7.2%), sea (5.0%), island (3.5%), ocean (2.1%), peninsula (1.6%), planet (0.4%), and geographic region (0.8%). Evaluating models on this dataset is particularly relevant as it allows us to assess their ability to identify and link entities primarily belonging to location-based categories, which exhibit specific linguistic patterns and potential ambiguities. Collectively, these 746 mentions correspond to 211 unique Wikidata identifiers (QIDs), indicating a moderate level of entity ambiguity and diversity that models must handle during the linking process.

We evaluated three models on this corpus, specifically focusing on their performance in identifying and linking these geolocational entity types: a conventional CNN-based model serving as our baseline (SRPCNNEL) (Ikonić Nešić, Petalinkar, Stanković, Utvić, & Kitanović, 2024), and two BERT-based models, Tes-

²<https://geojson.org/>

³The final version of datasets and models will be publicly available at <https://huggingface.co/te-sla>.

1aXLM_NER+NEL and Jerteh-355_NER+NEL. Model performance was quantified using standard metrics derived from True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN) (Table 1).

The baseline SrpCNEL model achieved 435 TP, with 7 FP and 312 FN on the *sr-geography* dataset. While this yielded a high precision of approximately 0.984, its recall was significantly lower at about 0.582, resulting in an F1-score of approximately 0.734.

In contrast, the more advanced BERT-based models demonstrated superior performance within this domain. The TeslaXLM_NER+NEL model successfully identified 588 TP, incurring 40 FP and 159 FN. This corresponds to the precision of 0.936, recall of 0.787, and F1-score of 0.855. Similarly, the Jerteh-355_NER+NEL model yielded 582 true positives, with 42 FP and 165 FN, achieving the precision of 0.933, recall of 0.779, and an F1-score of 0.849 (Table 1).

A comparative analysis of these results highlights the substantial performance gain achieved by the BERT-based models on the *sr-geography* corpus compared to the CNN baseline. Although the baseline model maintained very high precision by making fewer false positive predictions, its significantly lower recall indicates a substantial number of missed entities.

The BERT models, while exhibiting slightly lower precision, achieved considerably higher recall, leading to a significantly better balance between identifying correct entities and avoiding false positives, as reflected in their notably higher F1-scores. The TeslaXLM_NER+NEL model slightly edged out the Jerteh-355_NER+NEL model in overall F1-score on this specific dataset, suggesting a marginal advantage in this domain.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we presented an end-to-end NEL pipeline for the Serbian, capable of transforming raw text into rich, geospatial visualizations. The pipeline includes entity recognition, disambiguation via Wikidata, and two complementary forms of output: (1) an interactive Streamlit web application based on annotated HTML, and (2) structured GeoJSON exports suitable for GIS platforms such as QGIS.

To support this system, we trained two transformer-based NEL models each based on a different pretrained model: a multilingual model with 561 million parameters (TeslaXLM), and a smaller monolingual model with 355 million parameters (jerteh-355). Both NEL models demonstrated strong performance on a specialized geography corpus. While the larger multilingual model achieved slightly better F1-scores, it remains inconclu-

sive whether this advantage stems from its multilingual pretraining or simply its increased size.

Crucially, beyond intrinsic evaluation, we applied these models to annotate five novels from the Serbian ELTeC corpus, extracting and visualizing location entities. These outputs are accessible both via a public Streamlit viewer hosted online and as downloadable GeoJSON datasets. This demonstrates a clear path from linguistic annotation to practical applications in digital humanities and education.

Unlike prior studies that often isolate model development from applied use, our work offers a fully integrated pipeline, from raw text to interactive map, intended for real-world deployment. We believe this approach can serve as a valuable resource for teachers, researchers, and developers working with Serbian language materials in both computational linguistics and cultural heritage domains.

Future work will expand the dataset with labeled texts from diverse genres and broaden entity categories to include lakes, provinces, and regions. Wikipedia-based prompts will be used to enhance contextual diversity in training data and reduce ambiguity.

The presented work opens the possibility for further improvements toward designing to go beyond just geomapping data but also to answer spacial queries submitted in natural language. The conversion to RDF will be performed as in (Stanković et al., 2024), so the incorporation of NIF annotations will provide the exploration of annotated data using SPARQL queries.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #7276, *Text Embeddings – Serbian Language Applications – TESLA*.

REFERENCES

- Auer, S., Bizer, C., Kobilarov, G., Lehmann, J., Cyganiak, R., & Ives, Z. (2007). DBpedia: A Nucleus for a Web of Open Data. In K. Aberer et al. (Eds.), *The semantic web* (pp. 722–735). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Berragan, C., Singleton, A., Calafiore, A., & Morley, J. (2023). Transformer based named entity recognition for place name extraction from unstructured text. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 37(4), 747–766.
- Dinić-Marinković, M. D. (2017). *Obim i struktura vokabulara udžbenika za drugi ciklus obaveznog obrazovanja*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Univerzitet u Beogradu, Filološki fakultet.
- Frontini, F., Brando, C., Byszuk, J., Galleron, I., Santos, D., & Stanković, R. (2020). Named entity recognition for distant reading in ELTeC. In *Clarin annual conference 2020*.

Table 1: Evaluation of NEL over different models.

model		TP	FP	FN	Prec.	Recall	F1-score
SrpCNNEl	(baseline)	435	7	312	0.984	0.582	0.731
TeslaXLM_NER+NEL	516 mil.par.	588	40	159	0.936	0.787	0.855
Jerteh-355_NER+NEL	355 mil.par.	582	42	165	0.933	0.779	0.849

- Hu, Y., Mai, G., Cundy, C., Choi, K., Lao, N., Liu, W., ... Joseph, K. (2023). Geo-knowledge-guided GPT models improve the extraction of location descriptions from disaster-related social media messages. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 37(11), 2289–2318.
- Ikonić Nešić, M., Petalinkar, S., Stanković, R., & Škorić, M. (2024). BERT downstream task analysis: Named Entity Recognition in Serbian. In *14th International Conference on Information Society and Technology – ICIST 2024* (pp. 333–347).
- Ikonić Nešić, M., Petalinkar, S., Stanković, R., Utvić, M., & Kitanović, O. (2024). SrpCNNEl: Serbian Model for Named Entity Linking. In *2024 19th Conference on Computer Science and Intelligence Systems (FedCSIS)* (pp. 465–473).
- Jones, C. B., & Purves, R. S. (2008). Geographical information retrieval. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 22(3), 219–228. doi: 10.1080/13658810701626343
- Klie, J.-C., Bugert, M., Boullosa, B., de Castilho, R. E., & Gurevych, I. (2018). The inception platform: Machine-assisted and knowledge-oriented interactive annotation. In *Proc. of the 27th international conference on computational linguistics* (pp. 5–9). ACL. <http://tubiblio.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/106270/>
- Krstev, C., Obradović, I., Utvić, M., & Vitas, D. (2014). A system for named entity recognition based on local grammars. *Journal of Logic and Computation*, 24(2), 473–489.
- Krstev, C., & Stanković, R. (2021). Novels and Authors of the Serbian ELTeC Collection. *Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities*, 21(2). Retrieved 2022-02-17, from https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/2021.21.2.13_en
- Lazić, B., & Škorić, M. (2019). From DELA based dictionary to Leximirka lexical database. *Infotheca–Journal for Digital Humanities*, 19(2), 00–00. (<https://doi.org/10.18485/infoteka.2019.19.2.4>)
- Neumann, M., King, D., Beltagy, I., & Ammar, W. (2019). ScispaCy: Fast and Robust Models for Biomedical Natural Language Processing. In *Proceedings of the 18th bionlp workshop and shared task*. ACL. doi: 10.18653/v1/w19-5034
- Stanković, R., Krstev, C., Lazić, B., & Škorić, M. (2018). Electronic dictionaries—from file system to lemon based lexical database. In *6th workshop on linked data in linguistic (ldl-2018), towards linguistic data science*.
- Stanković, R., Krstev, C., Todorović, B. Š., & Škorić, M. (2021). Annotation of the Serbian ELTeC Collection. *Infotheca–Journal for Digital Humanities*, 21(2), 43–59. (<https://doi.org/10.18485/infoteka.2021.21.2.3>)
- Stanković, R., Milica, I. N., Perišić, O., Škorić, M., & Kitanović, O. (2024). Towards semantic interoperability: Parallel corpora as linked data incorporating named entity linking. In *The 9th workshop on linked data in linguistics: Resources, applications, best practices (ldl-2024)@Irecoling-2024* (pp. 115–125).
- Van Hulst, J. M., Hasibi, F., Dercksen, K., Balog, K., & de Vries, A. P. (2020). Rel: An entity linker standing on the shoulders of giants. In *Proceedings of the 43rd international acm sigir conference on research and development in information retrieval* (pp. 2197–2200). doi: 10.1145/3397271.3401416
- Vitas, D., Stanković, R., & Krstev, C. (2025). The Many Faces of SrpKor [O фамилији корпуса савременог српског језика СрпKор]. In *Proc. of the international conference south slavic languages in the digital environment judig* (p. 3-28). University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philology. doi: 10.18485/judig.2025.1.1.ch1
- Vrandečić, D., & Krötzsch, M. (2014). Wikidata: a free collaborative knowledgebase. *Communications of the ACM*, 57(10), 78–85. (<https://doi.org/10.1145/2629489>)

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

FROM BILINGUAL LEARNERS' DICTIONARY TO DYNAMIC PLATFORM FOR LEARNERS: TOWARDS AI-AUGMENTED JAPANESE-CROATIAN (WAKU) AND JAPANESE-SERBIAN (WASE) LANGUAGE LEARNING RESOURCE

Irena Srdanović¹

¹Juraj Dobrila University of Pula

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Keywords: learner's dictionaries, Japanese-Croatian-Serbian learner resources, AI-augmented dynamic platforms, LLMs in lexicography

1 INTRODUCTION

In the context of the rapid development of digital lexicography and the increasing usage of large language models (LLMs), the ways in which language learners access dictionaries and learning resources are undergoing significant change, while the future of lexicography is being questioned (Suzuki et al., 2020; Tarp, 2023; De Schryver, 2023; Jakubiček & Rundell, 2023). Traditional bilingual learner dictionaries are expected to redefine their role, be complemented, and gradually evolve into dynamic, interactive platforms that integrate multiple data sources, adaptive presentation of information, and artificial intelligence tools.

This extended abstract presents the Japanese–Croatian learner's e-dictionary (Srdanović, 2018; 2020), named WaKu (*Wa* 'Japanese', *Ku* 'Croatian'), and outlines its potential development into a broader Japanese–Croatian–Serbian educational resource, WaKuSe. The WaKu project emerged as a response to the concrete needs of Japanese language learners with a Croatian background, while its planned expansion into the Japanese–Serbian learner's e-dictionary WaSe (*Wa* 'Japanese', *Se* 'Serbian'), which together comprise the multilingual WaKuSe resource, explores the potential for wider applicability and systematic reuse of existing lexicographic data.

An especially important dimension of this development concerns resources for less-represented languages and language pairs (Lew, 2024). While Japanese is a globally prominent language, Croatian and Serbian, which are closely related South Slavic standard languages (Ljubešić & Lauc, 2021), are still relatively underrepresented in high-quality learner resources for Japanese.

The focus of the paper is placed on conceptual and methodological considerations related to the use of large language models as support tools in lexicographic editing and

data expansion. The aim is to demonstrate how an existing bilingual learner dictionary can be reconceptualized as the core of a future dynamic language learning platform in an AI-enhanced environment.

2 FROM STUDENT-DRIVEN DICTIONARY TO MULTILINGUAL RESOURCE

The Japanese–Croatian learner's dictionary WaKu has been developed within teaching and research activities at Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, with the active involvement of students of Japanese as a foreign language (Srdanović, 2018; 2020). The initial goal was to create a dictionary that reflects learners' actual needs, based on the textbooks and materials used in formal instruction, and enriched with additional resources including examples provided bilingually.

The dictionary has been designed in three modules. The first module covers core vocabulary from beginner and intermediate Japanese language textbooks used at the study program, the second module expands the lexical base to include frequent general vocabulary beyond the textbooks content, and the third module focuses on specialized domains such as tourism, linguistics, and art history. This modular structure enables the dictionary to expand while allowing flexibility in addressing the needs of different learner profiles.

The microstructure of WaKu is learner-oriented, including not only headwords, transcriptions, and translations, but also grammatical information, usage patterns, collocations, and bilingual examples presented in multiple scripts (kanji, kana, and romaji). Particular attention has been given to securing consistency of data and its operability in multiple formats (specified spreadsheet format, XML structure), which is essential for future automation and integration with AI-based tools.

The concept of WaKuSe builds on the close linguistic relationship between Croatian and Serbian. Given their high degree of mutual intelligibility, the existing Japanese–Croatian resource can be adapted and extended to the Japanese–Serbian language pair with relatively limited additional effort. Rather than developing a new dictionary from scratch, the project explores methods for reusing and systematically adapting existing lexicographic data, thereby reducing development time and resource demands.

3 CONCEPTUAL USE OF LLMs AS LEXICOGRAPHIC ASSISTANTS

Within the development of the WaKuSe resource, the potential role of large language models, specifically ChatGPT as a representative LLM, has been explored as a form of lexicographic assistance. In this extended abstract, the emphasis is placed on the conceptual framework for LLM use.

In the initial phase, LLMs are considered to be used as support for the following stages of lexicographic work:

- (1) preliminary checks of data consistency, including transcription and grammatical labeling;
- (2) identification of potential errors, omissions, and inconsistencies;
- (3) initial transfer, translation, and adaptation of lexicographic data between closely related target languages.

As the data has been created in collaboration with a diverse group of students, the mentioned stages (1) and (2) become highly relevant for detecting inconsistencies and possible mistakes. However, the use of an AI-augmented approach does not imply the replacement of human editors. Instead, this approach points toward a redefinition of editorial workflows, in which routine and repetitive tasks can be partially delegated to AI tools, while final decisions, editing, and quality control remain with human experts. The effectiveness of this collaboration depends heavily on prompt design, data structure, and iterative interaction with the model, but is expected to provide better results than either a solely AI-based approach or exclusively human editing. At the same time, it opens up novel approaches for lexicographers in the design and adaptability of lexicographic data and highlights the need for collaboration with a range of specialists.

In the context of WaKuSe, LLMs are regarded as an important element within a broader framework of tools that support the transition from a static dictionary to a dynamic learning platform. Rather than functioning solely as a

reference resource, the platform is envisioned as an interactive environment that adapts to learners' proficiency levels and learning goals while integrating AI-enhanced functionalities.

4 TOWARDS DYNAMIC, LEARNER-CENTERED LANGUAGE LEARNING PLATFORMS

The development of WaKu and WaSe aligns with a broader shift from static dictionaries toward multifunctional, learner-centered language learning platforms. One example of such a platform currently under development is SmirAI, a virtual cultural and language tutor targeted at future Japanese-speaking tourism specialists in the Croatian context (Srdanović et al., 2025). SmirAI also incorporates lexicographic data within a dynamic, learner-centered language learning platform designed for a specific purpose.

Contemporary learners expect fast access to information, authentic usage examples, multimodal content, and opportunities for personalization. In this context, dictionaries increasingly serve as integral components of the learning process within platforms rather than standalone reference tools.

A future platform based on the WaKuSe concept could incorporate advanced search capabilities, adaptive presentation of information according to learners' proficiency levels, links to corpora and other open resources, as well as elements of gamification, user motivation (Dangubić, 2024), and progress tracking. The integration of LLMs further enables interactive features, such as context-sensitive explanations or the generation of learner-tailored examples.

In conclusion, this extended abstract demonstrates how a student-driven bilingual learner dictionary can evolve into a multilingual, AI-augmented language learning platform. By emphasizing conceptual, methodological, and pedagogical perspectives, it positions the WaKuSe initiative within ongoing discussions on the future of lexicography and language education in the age of artificial intelligence, while maintaining a strong focus on users, learning contexts, and the communicative functions of dictionaries.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is part of the institutional project *Japanese language and society: basic concepts and empirical analysis* (10/1/2023-9/30/2027), Juraj Dobrila University of Pula (project leader: Irena Srdanović), as well as the institutional project *From Dynamic Vocabulary to Virtual Interaction: Development of a Foreign Language Learning Model in Tourism Using Corpora, Artificial Intelligence, and Extended*

Reality (10/1/2025-9/30/2029), Juraj Dobrila University of Pula (project leader: Irena Srdanović).

REFERENCES

- Dangubić, S. (2024) *Primjena igrifikacije u učenju japanskog jezika*. Pula: Sveučilište Jurja Dobrile u Puli. MA thesis. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://zir.nsk.hr/islandora/object/unipu%3A9878>
- De Schryver, G-M. (2023) Generative AI and Lexicography: The Current state of the art using ChatGPT. In *Int J Lexicogr: ecad021*. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://academic.oup.com/ijl/article/36/4/355/7288213>
- Lew, R. (2024). Dictionaries and lexicography in the AI era. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(426). Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-024-02889-7>
- Ljubešić, N. & Lauc, D. (2021) BERTiC - The Transformer Language Model for Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian. In *Proceedings of the 8th Workshop on Balto-Slavic Natural Language Processing*, 37–42. Association for Computational Linguistics. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://aclanthology.org/2021.bsnlp-1.5/>
- Jakubiček, M., & Rundell, M. (2023). The end of lexicography? Can ChatGPT outperform current tools for post-editing lexicography? In M. Medved, M. Měchura, C. Tiberius, I. Kosem, J. Kallas, & M. Jakubiček (Eds.), *Proceedings of the eLex 2023 conference: Electronic lexicography in the 21st century*, 508–523. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from http://elex.link/elex2023/wp-content/uploads/16_30-The-end-of-lexicography.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Srdanović, I. (2018) Engaging Students in Creating Bilingual Online Learner's Dictionaries: General and Specializing in Tourism. In: *International Symposium Japanese Language Learning for New Generations: Book of Abstracts*, Pula. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://ffpu.unipu.hr/images/50023838/Book%20of%20Abstracts%20Symposium%20in%20Pula%202018.pdf>
- Srdanović, I. (2020). From Specialized Web Corpora of Tourism to a Learner's Dictionary. *Rasprave Instituta za hrvatski jezik*, 46 (2), 1059-1083. <https://doi.org/10.31724/rihji.46.2.31>
- Srdanović, I., Smajić, A., Rovis, M. (2025) SmirAI: Prototype of a Virtual Cultural Tutor. In: *Traces of the Past, Horizons of the Future: Exploring Japan at the Crossroads of Humanities, Technology, and Global Dialogue: Book of Abstracts*, Pula. Retrieved November 20, 2025, from <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1SRce7ItXJalW8Csi095wvPYHe5cE4UBP/view>
- Suzuki, T., Shimizu, Y., Nakamura, A. & Shibuya, H. (2020). Kaigai no daigaku ni okeru Nihongo gakushūsha no tsūru shiyō jōkyō no kaimei: ICT jidai ni okeru kyōshi no kyōiku sekkei riterashī no kōjō o mezashite [What kinds of learning tools Japanese language learners in the overseas universities are using: To improve teachers' instructional design literacy in highly developed ICT environments]. *Journal of Japanese Studies*, 10 (*Nihongo nihongaku kenkyū*), 23–48. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1010286980761435264>
- Tarp, S. (2023). Eppur si muove: Lexicography is Becoming Intelligent!. *Lexikos*, 33(2), 107-131. Retrieved July 18, 2025, from <https://lexikos.journals.ac.za/pub/article/view/1841>

TAMING CROATIAN NEWS WITH TAKELAB RETRIEVER

Ana Barić, Marko Čuljak, Laura Majer

TakeLab, University of Zagreb

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Keywords: news corpora, discourse analysis, Croatian language resources

1 INTRODUCTION

Following technological advancements throughout history, the news media have evolved substantially. Despite significant reshaping, news remains a vital source of information, serving as a valuable resource for examining both how the world is represented and how language is used to shape those representations. However, having experienced massive growth, the news media landscape is increasingly difficult to navigate.

Most commonly, news from various outlets is aggregated and queried through general-purpose search engines. While powerful, those engines often produce incomplete and biased results, leaving users unsure which articles are omitted, how results are ranked, and why certain content is prioritized. This limitation presents a particular challenge for researchers working in fields that rely on news data, such as political science, media studies, and psychology, where accurate and comprehensive access to information is essential for meaningful analysis. Likewise, areas focused on language, such as computational linguistics and natural language processing (NLP), require clean data from verified sources.

In contrast, much of the information online is unstructured and of inconsistent quality. Another key problem in any language-focused discipline is acquiring diverse and unbiased data in languages other than English. For instance, while platforms like Ground News (*Ground News*, n.d.) are available for English, there is no similar platform or resource for South Slavic languages or their corresponding media sphere. The closest regional match is arhiv.rs¹, an archive of digitized newspapers, which is defunct as of 2017. To combat the lack of platforms for news analysis tailored to researchers in academia, we develop Retriever (Dukić et al., 2024), a search engine for Croatian news. Throughout this extended abstract, we describe the main components of the Retriever platform and demonstrate its utility through published studies in which the TakeLab Retriever corpus was essential.

2 TAKELAB RETRIEVER PLATFORM & CORPUS

Retriever allows researchers to analyze content from 33 Croatian news outlets, with publication dates spanning from January 2000 to the present. The crawling process is constantly ongoing, with thousands of articles being added daily. Retriever's key feature is its search functionality, which allows users to include semantic constraints based on topics or named entities mentioned in the articles. The results are presented in an aggregated form, including the temporal trends of the search term's frequency as well as the metadata such as publication dates, news outlets, and links to the corresponding set of retrieved articles.

Equipped with state-of-the-art models for NLP, Retriever automatically processes the retrieved articles, categorizing them into appropriate topics and enriching them with part-of-speech tags, dependency parse trees, and named entity annotations with links to Wikidata (Vrandečić, 2012). The interaction among all the components is shown in Figure 1. For the implementation details about the system for article retrieval and semantic processing, and an analysis of the performance of named entity annotation components, please see the Retriever technical report (Dukić et al., 2024), and a student thesis on Croatian entity linking (Galić, 2025).

The platform can be accessed through its web application.² The search engine is available to both affiliated and independent researchers for non-commercial, research-oriented use. To apply for platform access, interested users are required to fill in the form provided on the aforementioned website.

In addition to being a platform with an advanced search functionality, Retriever is incredibly valuable as a corpus. With Retriever, we have compiled and processed an unbiased archive spanning from the year 2000 onward, comprising of 10 million news articles as of November 2024 from 33 news outlets. In Figure 2, we present an example of article count distribution over the collection period for a given query.

¹<http://www.arhiv.rs>

²<https://retriever.takelab.fer.hr>

Figure 1: TakeLab Retriever pipeline. The pipeline consists of two types of modules: core and external. The core modules include a tokenizer, a sentencizer, and a lemmatizer. The external modules include a low-quality article detector, a topic classifier, and entity-linking components.

3 APPLICATIONS

We utilized the corpus for various tasks, ranging from political science topics such as sentiment and clickbait for news headlines, as well as fact-checking to applications in the computational linguistics domain, such as training diachronic embeddings. We will now list several studies we conducted on top of the corpus.

3.1 Sentiment analysis

Sentiment analysis has become a prevalent approach in media communications for understanding how the portrayal of different actors and events shapes public perception. Within this context, sentiment directed to particular actors and tone analysis of news headlines are especially significant, since headlines often serve as attention-grabbers and affect readers' interpretations. To this end, we leverage Retriever's database to compile STONE (Barić et al., 2023), a novel dataset comprised of 2880 Croatian news headlines labeled with sentiment towards named entities and the general tone of the headlines. We collect headlines by using the TakeLab Retriever corpus and extract named entities using BERTiC (Ljubešić & Lauc, 2021) specialized for NER. Each headline is then labeled by six annotators using a ternary scheme ('positive', 'negative', 'neutral') for sentiment and tone. Furthermore, we fine-tune several baselines and transformer-based language models in a multi-task setting to investigate whether tone information could benefit the classification of targeted sentiment. We find that multi-task training indeed aids performance, and analyze in depth the results using dataset cartography (Swayamdipta et al., 2020).

In follow-up work, we expand our study of sentiment analysis to large language models (LLMs), using STONE

along with two other sentiment datasets for zero- and few-shot classification (Juroš et al., 2024). We construct prompts with varying levels of prescriptiveness, inspired by two opposing data annotation paradigms for subjective tasks (Rottger et al., 2022): lower prescriptiveness permits more variation, while greater prescriptiveness limits it. For STONE, we show that fine-tuned BERTiC (Ljubešić & Lauc, 2021) outperforms various LLMs across prompt configurations, demonstrating the potential of smaller language models specialized for the respective language group and the strength of fine-tuning for subjective tasks.

3.2 Clickbait detection

Another prevalent analysis of news media concerns *clickbait*, a phenomenon defined as a statement designed to make readers want to click a hyperlink, especially when the link leads to content of dubious value (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). In our work, we compile CLIC, a novel dataset for clickbait analysis in Croatian (Anđelić et al., 2025), comprised of headlines annotated as 'clickbait' or 'not clickbait'. The headlines are collected from the Takelab Retriever corpus, spanning across 20 years and multiple outlets. The final dataset consists of 2907 headlines with 5 annotations each, to account for subjectivity in perceiving clickbait.

Surprisingly, the ratio of positive to negative labels is around 50 percent, consistent throughout the years. To determine the viability of automated clickbait detection, we fine-tune several models and compare them to zero- and few-shot prompting on various LLMs. Our experiments show that fine-tuned BERTiC again achieves superior overall performance, while LLMs improve if clickbait features are explicitly included in prompts.

Figure 2: TakeLab Retriever web application search result for *migracije* (*migration*) in combination with the topics ECONOMY, BUSINESS and FINANCE, and CONFLICTS, WAR and PEACE on 33 Croatian news outlets, with no articles hidden from the results.

3.3 Fact-checking

A report published by FullFact (FullFact, n.d.), a major British fact-checking organisation, highlights that monitoring and identifying claims is the most laborious and challenging stage of the fact-checking process. To address this, as part of the EDMO – EU’s largest interdisciplinary network for countering disinformation (EDMO, n.d.) – we developed *ClaimSearch*, a platform designed for early claim detection. The core of the system is a vector database comprising claims extracted from articles in the Takelab Retriever corpus, published since 2021. Each article is segmented into sentences, embedded using a custom embedding model, and stored in the vector database. For any input claim, semantically similar claims are retrieved based on vector similarity. This approach offers a major advantage over traditional string-based search, as it allows for the detection of paraphrases and semantically equivalent statements rather than relying solely on exact wording. Using *ClaimSearch*, fact-checkers can efficiently identify similar claims across different news outlets, enabling them to trace the spread and evolution of disinformation. Beyond claim-level analysis, the system can also be a foundation for analyzing disinformative narratives (Grbeša et al., 2024). Unlike explicit false claims, disinformative narratives tend to be more subtle and diffuse, spreading across multiple media sources and over time. To analyze such narratives, potential narratives are first identified – often by monitoring discussions across various media spaces and in different countries. For each narrative, the associated disinformative claims that reinforce it are then constructed, along with paraphrases of these claims, which are then used as input into the *ClaimSearch* to retrieve related instances. Finally, LLMs are employed to filter out false positives. This workflow enables the temporal and cross-outlet analysis of disinformative narratives, providing a powerful tool for understanding the dynamics of online misinformation.

3.4 Linguistic Shifts

Another angle for using a large news database like Retriever is to analyze how word meanings change over time using diachronic word embeddings. By following the methodology proposed by Hamilton et al. (2016), we train skip-gram word2vec embedding models (Mikolov et al., 2013) for non-overlapping 5-year periods in the timespan of 2000-2025 using the Retriever database and ensure that the embeddings are compatible across periods via the Procrustes alignment (Schönemann, 1966). To assess the quality of embeddings, we use word-similarity datasets for Croatian and find a moderate positive correlation between human-judgment scores and word embeddings. Next, we assess the capability of embeddings to capture topical and sentiment shifts. We curate the words for three major topics relevant both globally and locally (COVID-19, EU, and technological advancements), and find that embeddings accurately reflect the topical change. We extend the evaluation to quantify sentiment shift on news headlines and entire news articles. We find that embeddings from later periods bias sentiment classifiers trained on independent news corpora towards positive sentiment (and vice versa), which aligns with the observed increase in positive news at the expense of neutral reporting.

4 CONCLUSION

TakeLab Retriever is a specialized search engine for Croatian online news. Its scale and rich semantic information available for each indexed article make it a compelling resource for researchers across social science disciplines. We demonstrate Retriever’s potential for academic research by outlining five studies published in peer-reviewed publications for which the corpus was instrumental. Hoping to inspire further research on Croatian news and thereby accelerate social science, we continue to maintain the Retriever platform and collect recently published news articles.

REFERENCES

- Andelic, M., Sipek, D., Majer, L., & Snajder, J. (2025, July). What makes you CLIC: Detection of Croatian clickbait headliness. In J. Piskorski, P. Přebáň, P. Nakov, R. Yangarber, & M. Marcinczuk (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 10th workshop on slavic natural language processing (slavic nlp 2025)* (pp. 116–123). Vienna, Austria: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2025.bsnlp-1.14/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2025.bsnlp-1.14
- Barić, A., Majer, L., Dukić, D., Grbeša-zenzerović, M., & Snajder, J. (2023, May). Target two birds with one SToNe: Entity-level sentiment and tone analysis in Croatian news headlines. In J. Piskorski et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 9th workshop on slavic natural language processing 2023 (slavicnlp 2023)* (pp. 78–85). Dubrovnik, Croatia: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2023.bsnlp-1.10/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2023.bsnlp-1.10
- Dukić, D., Petričević, M., Ćurković, S., & Šnajder, J. (2024). *Takelab retriever: Ai-driven search engine for articles from croatian news outlets*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.19718>
- EDMO. (n.d.). *Edmo eu*. Retrieved October 31, 2025, from <https://edmo.eu/>
- FullFact. (n.d.). *“the challenges of online fact checking.”*. Retrieved October 31, 2025, from <https://fullfact.org/media/uploads/coof-2020.pdf>
- Galić, F. (2025). *Entity linking methods for croatian news articles*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Zagreb. Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing.
- Grbeša, M., Vučković, M., Majer, L., Gjurković, M., Šnajder, J., & Dukić, D. (2024). Admo report - content analysis of disinformation and narratives related to the war in ukraine. <https://admohub.eu/en/research/report-content-analysis-of-disinformation-and-narratives-related-to-the-war-in-ukraine/>
- Ground news. (n.d.). Retrieved October 26, 2025, from <https://ground.news/>
- Hamilton, W. L., Leskovec, J., & Jurafsky, D. (2016, August). Diachronic word embeddings reveal statistical laws of semantic change. In K. Erk & N. A. Smith (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 54th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics (volume 1: Long papers)* (pp. 1489–1501). Berlin, Germany: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/P16-1141/> doi: 10.18653/v1/P16-1141
- Juroš, J., Majer, L., & Snajder, J. (2024, August). LLMs for targeted sentiment in news headlines: Exploring the descriptive-prescriptive dilemma. In O. De Clercq, V. Barriere, J. Barnes, R. Klinger, J. Sedoc, & S. Tafreshi (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 14th workshop on computational approaches to subjectivity, sentiment, & social media analysis* (pp. 329–343). Bangkok, Thailand: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.wassa-1.27/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.wassa-1.27
- Ljubešić, N., & Lauc, D. (2021). Bertić – the transformer language model for bosnian, croatian, montenegrin and serbian. In *Proceedings of the eighth workshop on balto-slavic natural language processing (bsnlp 2021)* (pp. 37–42). Kiev, Ukraine: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). *Clickbait*. In *Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary*. Retrieved October 27, 2025, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/clickbait>
- Mikolov, T., Sutskever, I., Chen, K., Corrado, G. S., & Dean, J. (2013). Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 26.
- Rottger, P., Vidgen, B., Hovy, D., & Pierrehumbert, J. (2022, July). Two contrasting data annotation paradigms for subjective NLP tasks. In M. Carpuat, M.-C. de Marneffe, & I. V. Meza Ruiz (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2022 conference of the north american chapter of the association for computational linguistics: Human language technologies* (pp. 175–190). Seattle, United States: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.naacl-main.13/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.13
- Schönemann, P. H. (1966). A generalized solution of the orthogonal Procrustes problem. *Psychometrika*, 31(1), 1–10.
- Swayamdipta, S., Schwartz, R., Lourie, N., Wang, Y., Hajishirzi, H., Smith, N. A., & Choi, Y. (2020, November). Dataset cartography: Mapping and diagnosing datasets with training dynamics. In B. Webber, T. Cohn, Y. He, & Y. Liu (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2020 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing (emnlp)* (pp. 9275–9293). Online: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2020.emnlp-main.746/> doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-main.746
- Vrandečić, D. (2012). Wikidata: a new platform for collaborative data collection. In *Proceedings of the 21st international conference on world wide web* (p. 1063–1064). New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2187980.2188242> doi: 10.1145/2187980.2188242

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

COMTEXT.SR – A COMMUNITY-SUPPORTED PROJECT TO DEVELOP OPEN LANGUAGE RESOURCES FOR SERBIAN

Vuk BATANOVIĆ,¹ Lenka BAJČETIĆ,^{1, 2} Aleksandra TODOROVIĆ,^{1, 2} Tanja SAMARDŽIĆ³

¹Innovation Center of the School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade

²School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade

³IDSIA USI-SUPSI

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Keywords: open access, text domain, legal texts, named entities, Serbian, Ekavian, Ijekavian

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the availability of open language resources for Serbian text processing has slowly but surely increased. A significant contribution to this developing trend has been provided by the ReLDI project (Samardžić et al., 2015), which led to the creation of the first publicly available reference corpora in Serbian – SETimes.SR (Batanović, Ljubešić, & Samardžić, 2018; Batanović et al., 2023) and ReLDI-NormTag-NER (Miličević & Ljubešić, 2016; Ljubešić et al., 2023). The SETimes.SR corpus, belonging to the newswire domain, was manually annotated in terms of tokenization and sentence segmentation, morphosyntax according to the MULTEXT-East v6 and UPOS standards, lemmas, dependency syntax according to the Universal Dependencies standard, and named entities using a basic five class schema including person, organization and location names. The ReLDI-NormTag-NER-sr corpus, belonging to the Twitter/X domain, was annotated with the same information, except for syntactic dependencies. The two ReLDI corpora provided the data to train or fine-tune various NLP models for Serbian, most notably the CLASSLA-Stanza package (Ljubešić et al., 2024) and various variants of the BERTiC large language model (Ljubešić & Lauc, 2021). In addition to these larger corpora, several smaller, task-specific manually annotated corpora have been published, mostly consisting of newswire (Batanović, Cvetanović, & Nikolić, 2018; Batanović & Miličević Petrović, 2022), blog (Batanović et al., 2016, 2020), or literary texts (Stanković et al., 2021; Šandrih Todorović et al., 2021).

All these previous efforts were driven by academic research and were predominantly guided by the availability of source texts. This primary criterion made newswire texts, Twitter and blog posts, and literary works obvious choices, due to the ease of obtaining sufficient quantities of texts from these domains, mostly from the Internet. However, this left many textual domains, often more complex ones, completely neglected

in terms of language resource development. Similarly, all previous research heavily emphasized the more widely spoken Ekavian pronunciation of Serbian, while dedicated resources and models for the Ijekavian pronunciation were all but non-existent.

2 THE COMTEXT.SR PROJECT

The COMtext.SR initiative has been launched as an attempt to address the growing market and societal needs for open NLP resources for Serbian in specific domains, such as legal, medical, financial, etc. One of the founding principles of the initiative is that all results (datasets, models, codebases) should be published under maximally permissive licenses, allowing both for their academic and commercial use. In addition, it aims to generate parallel resources for both Ekavian and Ijekavian pronunciations of Serbian. The COMtext.SR methodology is based on the creation of high quality, manually annotated and verified datasets for various NLP tasks and their subsequent use in fine-tuning and evaluating specialized large language models.

After extensive consultations with around 50 interested parties, including government representatives, domestic and foreign IT companies and NGOs, as well as legal tech experts, this initiative was formalized as a community-funded project. Project implementation is led by the Innovation Center of the School of Electrical Engineering in Belgrade, with assistance from the Regional Linguistic Data Initiative Centre regarding data annotation and quality assurance. Discussions with project partners identified the legal domain as the most common point of interest, making it the initial focus for project activities.

3 PROJECT TASKS AND EXPECTED RESULTS

The first major goal of the project is to improve the quality of text search in the legal domain. To that end, work is under way to address the NLP tasks of tokenization, morphosyntactic tagging, lemmatization, and named entity recognition. Solving these tasks also al-

tools for the creation of tools for anonymizing sensitive and personally identifiable information, automatic document indexing and linking, improved document classification, etc. For morphosyntax the MULTEXT-East v6 standard is followed, while for named entities a special schema adequate for the Serbian legal domain is being devised. In order to train and evaluate models for these NLP tasks, it is necessary to compile a sufficiently large corpus of legal texts, preferably containing at least 100 thousand tokens, in line with the sizes of the existing SETimes.SR and ReLDI-NormTag-NER-sr corpora. Legal experts from domestic law firms are being consulted to ensure the corpus covers a breadth of legal document types, such as laws, verdicts, contracts, statements, etc. The corpus will be made available in parallel Ekavian/Ijekavian versions. Data annotation is performed manually, either directly or, where possible, by checking and correcting the outputs of current best models. Fine-tuned models for morphosyntactic tagging, lemmatization and NER will be released in separate Ekavian and Ijekavian versions via the HuggingFace platform, while all project results will be publicly available at the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/ICEF-NLP/COMtext.SR>

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work presented here was supported by the COMtext.SR project and partially supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovations under grant no. 451-03-136/2025-03/200223. The research was partially conducted in the premises of the Palace of Science, Miodrag Kostić Endowment.

REFERENCES

- Batanović, V., Cvetanović, M., & Nikolić, B. (2018). Fine-grained semantic textual similarity for Serbian. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2018)* (pp. 1370–1378). Miyazaki, Japan.
- Batanović, V., Cvetanović, M., & Nikolić, B. (2020). A versatile framework for resource-limited sentiment articulation, annotation, and analysis of short texts. *PLOS ONE*, 15(11), e0242050. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0242050
- Batanović, V., Ljubešić, N., & Samardžić, T. (2018). SE-Times.SR — a reference training corpus of Serbian. In *Proceedings of the 2018 Conference on Language Technologies and Digital Humanities (JT-DH 2018)* (pp. 11–17). Ljubljana, Slovenia.
- Batanović, V., Ljubešić, N., Samardžić, T., & Erjavec, T. (2023). *Serbian linguistic training corpus SETimes.SR 2.0*. Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1843> (hdl:11356/1843)
- Batanović, V., & Miličević Petrović, M. (2022). Cross-level semantic similarity for Serbian newswire texts. In *Proceedings of the 13th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference (LREC 2022)* (pp. 1691–1699). Marseille, France.
- Batanović, V., Nikolić, B., & Milosavljević, M. (2016). Reliable baselines for sentiment analysis in resource-limited languages: The Serbian movie review dataset. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2016)* (pp. 2688–2696). Portorož, Slovenia.
- Ljubešić, N., Erjavec, T., Batanović, V., Miličević, M., & Samardžić, T. (2023). *Serbian Twitter training corpus ReLDI-NormTagNER-sr 3.0*. Slovenian language resource repository CLARIN.SI. <http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1794> (hdl:11356/1794)
- Ljubešić, N., & Lauc, D. (2021). BERTić — the transformer language model for Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian. In *Proceedings of the Eighth Workshop on Balto-Slavic Natural Language Processing (BSNLP 2021)* (pp. 37–42). Kiev, Ukraine: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Ljubešić, N., Terčon, L., & Dobrovoljc, K. (2024). CLASSLA-Stanza: The next step for linguistic processing of South Slavic languages. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Language Technologies and Digital Humanities (JT-DH 2024)* (pp. 235–258). Ljubljana, Slovenia.
- Miličević, M., & Ljubešić, N. (2016). Tviterasi, tviteraši or twit-teraši? Producing and analysing a normalised dataset of Croatian and Serbian tweets. *Slovenščina 2.0*, 4(2), 157–189. doi: 10.4312/slo2.0.2016.2.156-188
- Samardžić, T., Ljubešić, N., & Miličević, M. (2015). Regional linguistic data initiative (ReLDI). In *Proceedings of the Fifth Workshop on Balto-Slavic Natural Language Processing* (pp. 40–42). Hissar, Bulgaria.
- Stanković, R., Krstev, C., Šandrih Todorović, B., & Škorić, M. (2021). Annotation of the Serbian ELTeC Collection. *Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities*, 21(2), 43–59. doi: 10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.2.3
- Šandrih Todorović, B., Krstev, C., Stanković, R., & Ikonić Nešić, M. (2021). Serbian NER & beyond: The archaic and the modern intertwined. In *Proceedings of the International Conference Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing (RANLP 2021)* (pp. 1252–1260). doi: 10.26615/978-954-452-072-4_141

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

